

**UNIVERSITÀ
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Beyond the Message. The Impact of the Messenger on the Shaping of Migration Attitudes: A Survey Experiment in Italy

Relatore

Professor Pettrachin Andrea

Correlatori

Professoressa Caponio Tiziana

Professor Conzo Pierluigi

Candidata

Viola De Franco

Matricola 00983864

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INTRODUCTION

Migration has increasingly dominated the political arena, emerging as one of the most critical and contentious issues. As a result, influencing public opinion on migration has become a crucial strategy for political leaders and civil actors. At one pole, left-wing activists typically strive to cultivate positive or at least neutral feelings, advocating for policies that support immigration, social cohesion, and prevent conflicts. On the opposite side, right-wing parties often emphasize public anxieties related to security and cultural concerns, portraying migrants as potential threats and aligning their messages with prevailing public fears. In such a polarized context, strategic communication is key for each political camp to sway public opinion in their favor on the issue of migration. Beyond political parties, numerous other actors, particularly from civil society, are also actively engaged in shaping the discourse on migration. (Dennison, J., & Dražanová, L., 2018).

However, despite ongoing efforts, academic research is still in the process of defining which communication strategies are most successful at positively influencing public attitudes toward migration, trying to grasp the critical factors of message effectiveness. Within the realm of NGOs, particular emphasis is placed on the role of the messenger, whose influence is broadly acknowledged. Consistently, theories such as Identification Theory, Elaboration Likelihood Model, and Learning Theory provide frameworks for understanding how messengers impact public attitudes. As many grassroots and civil organizations claim, a well-crafted message may fall flat if not delivered by a credible and relatable figure. Recent researchers alike emphasize the need for strategic communication that carefully engages messengers who are authentic, trusted, and relatable, ensuring they can speak to the target audience in a language and manner that resonates. The strategic selection of messengers, therefore, may be paramount in efforts to shift or shape public opinion on this complex issue (Dennison, J., 2020).

In examining the characteristics that make messengers effective or ineffective, a body of research has emerged that identifies three key attributes as particularly influential in shaping public attitudes: credibility, relatability, and authority (Hovland, C. I. et al. 1953; Mills, J., & Aronson, E., 1965; Miller, G. R., & Burgoon, M., 1978). According to scholars, politicians, in particular, leveraging these attributes, wield significant influence over public opinion, with their in-group supporters often viewing them as reliable sources (Hovland et al., 1953; Mills & Aronson, 1965, Alto Analytics, 2019). Studies show that messages from in-group members (e.g., a politician from the same political party as the audience), are more persuasive, aligning with Social Identity and Social Norms Theories (Turner et al., 1979; Lupia, 1994; Druckman, 2001; Eshbaugh-Soha, 2010). The Partisan Cueing Effect and Messenger Effect further reveal a cognitive bias where people tend to judge the validity of information based on the source's identity rather than content, emphasizing the importance of the messenger in

strategic communication (Kassin, 1983; Nicholson, S. P., 2011; Marks & Martin, 2019; Brader, T., et al. 2020): Collectively, these studies underscore a critical theoretical consensus: the messenger is just as vital as the message itself in strategic communication.

Despite the wealth of theoretical discussions on the qualities of effective messengers and their potential influence on public opinion, there remains a notable gap in empirical studies that test these theories in real-world scenarios, particularly within the context of communication campaigns related to migration. While many studies have explored different communication strategies aimed at fostering positive attitudes toward migration - including correcting information, appealing to emotions or self-interest, emphasizing common ground or diversity, and using various descriptions of migrants - there is still a lack of focus on the effects of specific messengers, despite their significance in NGO and academic circles (Dennison, J., 2020; Dennison, J., 2022).

Hence, the experiment aims to explore the extent to which the individual delivering a message contributes to shaping opinions and attitudes. Specifically, this research asks “*Does the identity of the messenger influence the agreement levels of respondents on statements regarding immigration?*”

To answer the research question, the study employs an RTC methodology, wherein the sample is divided into several groups, including treatment and control groups. The treatment groups receive the intervention(s); whilst the control receives no intervention, serving as a baseline for comparison. In this specific case study, the sample is randomly assigned to three different groups, namely two Treatments and a Control Group.

Respondents in the Control Group are first asked general questions about their attitudes on migration, immigrants, and the political landscape, establishing a baseline for assessing overall pro- or anti-immigration sentiments and political affiliations. Due to the random assignment, it is possible to project the results of the control group onto the entire sample (e.g., if 40% of the control group holds anti-immigrant sentiments, then approximately 40% of the whole sample would be expected to identify as anti-immigrant). Treatment Group 1 is exposed to pro-migration messages from an anonymous source, while Treatment Group 2 receives the same messages from well-known messengers who typically identify with anti-immigrant and right-wing positions. This dual-treatment setup allows for an examination of the effects of positive messages on migration attitudes, further providing a primary parameter to measure the influence of the messenger’s identity.

The research is structured to test the hypothesis that the identity of the messenger significantly influences respondents’ agreement with statements regarding immigration. It assumes that knowledge of who is delivering a statement—referred to as the messenger—can substantially alter a respondent’s level of agreement or disagreement with the statement's content

(Verschuereen, 2008; Nicholson, 2011; Collett & Petrovic, 2014; Tufte, 2017; Marks & Martin, 2019; Brader et al., 2020; Strawser, 2021). Building on this, the research further hypothesizes that respondents will show higher levels of agreement with statements on immigration if the messenger is affiliated with their own political party, while they will display lower levels of agreement if the message is perceived as coming from an out-group member.

Data analysis, consistent with the first sub-hypothesis, reveals (though modestly) that right-wing respondents exhibited increased levels of agreement when the identity of the messenger was made explicit, compared to responses of Treatment Group 1 where the messages were anonymous. However, the regression models indicated an overall decrease in agreement, suggesting that other political segments (left-leaning individuals) did exhibit lower levels of agreement with messages perceived as coming from out-group members. Among the sample, which included a significant portion of left voters, the majority likely viewed the messengers (Vanacci and Feltri) as out-group figures. This perception may have triggered negative associations with migrants and migration, causing participants to either disregard or reject the statements, regardless of their content.

In summary, the research confirms the general hypothesis, revealing that while right-wing respondents showed slightly increased positive attitudes toward migrants due to right-wing messengers, left-leaning participants may have discounted the statements because they perceived the messengers as non-credible, out-group members. This finding aligns with the broader hypothesis that the identity of the messenger can exert a more substantial influence than the content of the message itself, often overshadowing it. This highlights the critical role of the messenger in the effectiveness of communication strategies, particularly when the messenger's identity contrasts sharply with the audience's social or political affiliations.

The dissertation is structured to provide a comprehensive exploration of the research topic. The first chapter offers an overview of international migration, detailing its main characteristics, prevalent stereotypes, and recent trends, while also discussing the politicization of migration and public opinion in Italy. The second chapter delves into public attitudes toward migration, examining how these attitudes are formed and influenced by various factors. It focuses particularly on the role of messengers in shaping public opinion and reviews the relevant literature on this topic, ultimately leading to the formulation of the research hypothesis and expected outcomes. The third chapter is dedicated to outlining the research methodology, describing the survey questionnaire, sample selection, data collection process, and data analysis methods. The fourth chapter presents the results of the regression models, while the fifth offers

an interpretation and analysis of these findings within the context of the survey and the existing literature.

CHAPTER 1: INTERNATIONAL MIGRATION, POLITICAL NARRATIVES AND PUBLIC ATTITUDES

This chapter provides a comprehensive framework of international migration by examining its evolving dynamics, the political narratives that shape it, and the public attitudes that arise as a result. The chapter is structured into five sections to systematically address these themes.

The first section (*1.1 International Migration*), introduces the fundamental concept of migration, offering a detailed exploration of its definitions and dimensions. The second section (*1.2 International Migration: What is Changing?*), analyzes the shifting trends and patterns in global migration, highlighting recent developments. In the third (*1.3 The Politicization of International Migration and its Key Drivers*), the focus shifts to the growing politicization of migration, identifying the primary factors driving this trend. The fourth section (*1.4 Public Opinion and Migration*) delves into the formation of public opinion on migration, examining the key influences shaping these attitudes. Finally, the last (*1.5 Public Attitudes toward Migration in Italy*) provides a specific analysis of the Italian context, offering insights into how migration is perceived within the country.

1.1 International Migration

International migration lacks a universally accepted definition under international law, and there is no single, comprehensive data source to analyze this complex phenomenon (Brown, S. K., & Bean, F. D., 2005). As a result, collective misconceptions and inaccurate mental images add to this unclear the picture, further blurring the already ambiguous reality.

Indeed, in the European context, a region that witnessed and is still witnessing intense migration flows, the discourse about international migration is often filled with generalized perceptions and categorizations that may not fully capture the diverse reality of international migration. The public often assumes a comprehensive understanding of migration dynamics, which, in reality, translates into an unintentional synecdoche. People tend to use a specific category of migrants to refer to the entire concept, often reducing the whole international migrant population to undocumented, low-skilled labor migrants or asylum seekers. It is unsurprising that when looking up “migration” on Google Images, the most common picture you’ll find is a packed boat in the Mediterranean (Blinder, S., 2015).

People, indeed, rely almost exclusively on these quick strategies or mental images to understand a world where they are bombarded with the most disparate information, especially when sitting through phenomena like international migration. These mental representations serve as shortcuts, allowing us to build impressions, make decisions, and find explanations on a topic, with the minimum cognitive effort. They predominate and present the same rapid response

whenever dealing with that particular topic, such as international migration. However, quite intuitively, whenever we develop ideas within a limited time frame and with little information, we stumble into ineffective shortcuts or biases leading to erroneous results and unfounded misconceptions. Eventually, we tend to hold onto these mental perceptions or misperceptions, often reducing the whole subject to one (either accurate or erroneous) mental image (Flynn, D. J. *et al.*, 2017; Kuklinski, J. H., & Quirk, P. J., 2000).

These widespread misperceptions and general ambiguity coupled with a myriad of differing definitions and approaches, form a complex puzzle. Sometimes piecing it together becomes challenging, making it hard to see the full picture of international migration (Gorodzeisky, A. & Semyonov, M., 2019).

Hence, to accurately grasp what international migration truly entails and solve the puzzle, it is essential to dive back into the basics of international movement, by addressing the quintessential “5 W” questions: What is international migration? Who are the people involved? Where do migrants go? Where do migrants come from? Why does it occur?

These simple questions help bridge the gap between frequent misconceptions and the in-depth insights to be explored in the next chapters.

1.1.1 WHAT is international migration?

As mentioned above, international migration is an umbrella term undefined by international law describing a multifaceted phenomenon encompassing both spatial and temporal dimensions. Pinning down a precise characterization of international migration proves challenging due to the existence of diverse narratives, explanations, motivations, circumstances, and durations.

Firstly, the criteria for defining international migrants vary, encircling different conditions and angles. People may be labeled as migrants by foreign birth, others may consider instead foreign citizenship, or, in some cases, some may encompass also children born in a country but with foreign-national parents. Interestingly, even individuals who relocate within national boundaries are commonly tagged as migrants in everyday language.

In addition, the discussion about “who is considered an international migrant” can occur on different levels, collecting a myriad of different perspectives. Indeed, individuals may be identified as migrants within various stages: under official statistical categorizations, legal classifications, in political discourse, or even at the emotional level (Tsegay, S. M., 2023).

Complicating matters further, refugees often constitute a distinct category. They are usually not included in the ample definitions of international migrants, preferably defined as individuals

outside their country of origin due to feared persecution, conflict, generalized violence, or other circumstances requiring international protection (Tataru, G. F., 2019).

Another critical aspect to consider is that while migration is often delineated by national borders, these borders themselves are remarkably unstable. This instability adds then another level of complexity to the understanding of migration, challenging conventional notions tied to fixed geopolitical boundaries (Haas, H de., 2011; Wickramasinghe, A. A. I. N., & Wimalaratana, W., 2016).

Undoubtedly, it becomes tricky to pinpoint an all-encompassing definition. Still, it could prove beneficial to adopt the United Nations' 1998 definition as a reference, wherein an international migrant is delineated as *“Any person who is outside a State of which he or she is a citizen or national, or, in the case of a stateless person, his or her State of birth or habitual residence”* for more than 3 months (Tataru, G. F., 2019). Other relevant definitions cite *“a person who moves away from his or her place of usual residence, across an international border, temporarily or permanently, and for a variety of reasons”* (IOM, Glossary on migration, 2019), or identify international migration as *“the movement of a person across an international border for more than one year irrespective of the causes, voluntary or involuntary, and the means, regular or irregular, used to migrate”* (EMN Asylum and Migration Glossary, 2022).

Hereinafter, it appears crucial to eventually differentiate international migration from international mobility. While all migrants are movers, not every mover is a migrant, meaning that not all individuals crossing borders change their country of usual residence. International mobility includes, indeed, people crossing borders for various reasons such as recreation, holidays, visits to friends or relatives, business engagements, or medical treatments. Circumstances that do not fall under the international migration macro-group (Tsegay, S. M., 2023).

1.1.2 WHO are the people involved?

As cited above, the discussion about “who are international migrants” often comes together with some common misreading, that needs some clarification.

The first misperception stems from the stereotype of the iconic immigrant boat navigating the Mediterranean crowded with poor, uneducated, irregular migrants. It easily comes to mind whenever thinking about migration, implicitly oversimplifying, and grouping together all migrants into one single category.

This tunnel vision inevitably leads to the overestimation of the numbers of asylum seekers and labor migrants, while minimizing other significant migrant groups such as students, spouses,

and high-skilled workers (Blinder, S. (2015); Pedersen, A., & Hartley, L. K., 2017; Dixon T *et al.*, 2019; Gorodzeisky, A. & Semyonov, M., 2019).

Inaccurate perceptions persist also about immigrants' socioeconomic status and education level, with a tendency to incorrectly deem them poorer and less educated than they actually are (A. *et al.*, 2023).

Lastly, misconceptions affect qualitative aspects of immigration too, with a widespread propensity to assume that international migrants always aim for permanent settlement, which, as demonstrated by various evidence, is not the case (Blinder, S., 2015; Lutz, P., & Bitschnau, M., 2023; Herda, D., 2023).

In fact, grouping migrants into precise categories or, else, pinning the specifics of each diverse category is still very challenging, given the multitude of complex factors at play. Migrants do navigate but across a nuanced interplay of various economic, political, and social influences, making it difficult to accurately define the people involved.

Indeed, while conventional narratives often shut migrants into two separate categories as either "economic migrants" (voluntary) or "asylum-seekers/refugees" (forced), as "documented and regular" or "undocumented, irregular", these dichotomies fail to grasp the nuanced reality of migration. As noted before, international migration, as a multifaceted phenomenon, operates along a continuum rather than within rigid binary classifications. In trying to comprehend who are the individuals involved in the international migration phenomenon while aiming to embrace as many aspects as possible, two primary continuums stand out: *document status* and *level of choice*.

On the one hand, *document status* refers to the legal framework governing the movement of individuals across international borders. Rather than sticking to rigid dichotomies, this spectrum embraces a wide variety of nuances. At one end of the continuum lay regular and documented migrants, individuals legalized by the destination country's regulation and international treaties. However, within the realm of regularity, there are some other shades of the same color. For example, individuals may legally obtain a regular visa but then switch to irregular status by violating entry conditions, such as working when admitted as students (Collyer, M., 2020). Again, consider a scenario in which individuals travel across borders following local conventions and agreements with village officials, but in the absence of proper documentation. While this may not be consistent with authentically documented movement, it does not represent a completely irregular flow. At the other end, the continuum includes a spectrum of status, which defines undocumented immigrants – individuals without proper documentation. One example may be represented by migrants whose documents are valid upon entry but subsequently become irregular staying in the country beyond the designated visa period. Within

this domain, it is also important to distinguish between “undocumented” and “irregular” migration. While undocumented refers to the absence of valid documents such as passports, visas, and identity cards, the status of irregularity stems from a full-documented entry but with a subsequent violation of access conditions (Bakewell, O., 2020).

Simultaneously, the *level of choice* presents a continuum within which each migratory movement unfurls. At one end there is forced migration, encompassing refugees and family migrants, pushed by compelling conditions. At the opposite end lies voluntary migration, a category embracing motivations like study or tourism, and labor migration – with further differentiations in skill sets. However, most people moving globally do not align perfectly with either category. For example, an individual fleeing violence is usually considered a refugee. Still, in some instances, once asylum is granted, refugees might also move again in search of better living conditions, thus blurring the distinction between forced and voluntary migration. Similarly, when people migrate running from difficult living situations in pursuit of greater possibilities, the extent of voluntariness becomes ambiguous (Charron, A., 2020). For instance, a highly skilled student unable to find good job opportunities in his hometown or motherland may feel compelled to move in order to benefit from greater career chances. Migrating towards improved living conditions may not constitute an entirely voluntary movement, as it stems from a lack of suitable options in the homeland (Erdal, M. B., & Oeppen, C., 2020; Bakewell, O., 2021).

In essence, it becomes evident that the categorization of migrants into different rigid classes based on their legal status, their degree of voluntariness, or any other ground, reveals purely simplistic. International migrants exist alongside a continuum, emphasizing the necessity to contemplate the multifaceted nature of migration experiences in order to puzzle out migrants’ identities.

1.1.3 WHERE do international migrants go?

In the modern-day era of worldwide shifts, international migration emerges as a substantial force reshaping societies and politics globally. The traditional classification rigidly distinguishing countries as either migrant senders (countries of emigration) or receivers (immigration countries), is dropping relevance. Instead, most nations and regions now experience both faces of the phenomenon, encountering simultaneously emigration and immigration, with one sequentially taking priority over the alternative.

Another key component of contemporary migration is circular migration, wherein individuals regularly move between different locations in a cyclical manner. This pattern challenges

traditional ideas of permanent settlement, highlighting the dynamic and fluid nature of modern global mobility (Østergaard-Nielsen, E., 2003; Leal, D. F., & Harder, N. L., 2023).

Looking at the actual global landscape, the US, Saudi Arabia, and Germany emerge as host leaders, receiving the highest number of international migrants within their borders. Additionally, when considering the impact of immigration flows on the local citizens in terms of number, the United Arab Emirates, Kuwait, and Singapore arise as the top 3 nations with the highest percentage of global migrants relative to their local inhabitants (see Figure 1) (IOM, 2022).

FIGURE 1: INTERNATIONAL MIGRANT POPULATION AND MIGRANT SHARE OF TOTAL POPULATION IN TOP 25 DESTINATION COUNTRIES (MPI, 2020).

1.1.4 WHERE do international migrants come from?

In contrast to common perceptions, particularly entrenched within the European population, it is noteworthy that the principal countries contributing to the global migrant population are not the least developed or the poorest regions. Remarkably, Europe and Northern America stand out as the main sources of migrants worldwide. Central and Southern Asia follow closely as the second most significant emigrant-origin regions, trailed by Latin America and the Caribbean (see Figure 2).

Interestingly, among the predominant nations contributing to this migratory outflow are economically dynamic middle-income nations, including India, Mexico, and Russia. Moreover,

several European nations, such as Ukraine, Poland, the United Kingdom, Romania, and Germany, host sizable populations of emigrants (Haas, de H., 2019; IOM, 2022).

	Origin	
	Estimate	Share of International Migrant Population (%)
Total International Migrant Population	280,598,105	100%
Europe and Northern America	67,601,621	24%
Central and Southern Asia	51,229,549	18%
Latin America and the Caribbean	42,890,481	15%
Eastern and Southeastern Asia	38,400,740	14%
Northern Africa and Western Asia	37,563,820	13%
Sub-Saharan Africa	28,284,538	10%
Australia and New Zealand	1,404,924	1%
Oceania (excluding Australia and New Zealand)	565,281	0%

FIGURE 2: ORIGINS FOR INTERNATIONAL MIGRANTS BY REGION, 2020 (BATALOVA, J., 2022).

This reality challenges preconceived notions and emphasizes the evolving and fluid dynamics of migration while dispelling the popular myth that poverty and destitution are the exclusive drivers of labor migration. Migration involves significant costs and risks, requiring not only financial resources but also knowledge, aspirations, and social networks. Thus, an apparently paradoxical relationship between socioeconomic development and migration emerges, indicating that rising incomes, educational levels, and access to information are often associated with increased migration. Rather than absolute poverty, the key driver of migration appears to be a certain level of socioeconomic development coupled with relative deprivation in the face of global inequality in development opportunities. This condition provides the population simultaneously with the required *capabilities* to move (financial, networking, etc.) and the *aspirations* to migrate and seek better opportunities elsewhere (Haas, de H., 2021).

However, it is crucial to highlight that this relationship is not unidirectional. As countries experience sustained growth and progressive convergence of income gaps with destination countries, emigration tends to decrease, and immigration increases over time. Alternatively, a declining development level relative to other countries can turn an immigration- into an emigration country, as evidenced by recent trends, such as the case of Argentina (Schewel, K., 2020; Haas, de H., 2020).

1.1.5 WHY do people migrate?

As anticipated, international migration is a puzzling phenomenon forged by a myriad of elements running on different levels. Understanding every single puzzle piece would require a much deeper analysis, but still, to grasp the main drivers guiding global movements, it is worthwhile to look at the key theories studying migrants' motivations from different perspectives.

Micro-level theories aim to explain migration choices at the individual level, as articulated by experts like Borjas (2014) and Stark (1991). These theories emphasize the rational nature of migration decisions, related to cost-benefit analyses, employed to maximize profits (for example via remittances) and limit risks (such as those arising from agricultural failures). More recent *micro-level* theories amplify the field of analysis overcoming mere economic and rational considerations, by pondering cultural factors, personal attitudes, and emotions in the shaping of migration decisions (Haas, de H., 2021). These authors claim that people *decide* to migrate or to stay for a myriad of reasons rising above economic possibilities. For instance, individuals may choose to stay because of their positive attachment to their homeland, or disinterest in alternative destinations, independently from sufficient or insufficient resources. Moreover, scholars posit that some people, such as Afghans for instance, may *choose* to migrate partially on the basis of their profound belief in political discourses surrounding human rights entitlements. Afghans may consider the assistance and support received in their home country, thus assuming similar or even enhanced opportunities in Europe. The presence of foreign financial and physical support, coupled with the public visibility of human rights discourses, is likely to shape individuals' migration decisions. Thereby, the *micro-level* perspective is no longer deemed to be concentrated on mere financial and economic evaluations, but considers further cultural and attitudinal aspects, providing a holistic understanding of the multifaceted nature of individual migration choices (Majidi, N., 2018).

At a secondary degree, *meso-level* theories look at the intricate dynamics of migration, from the perspective of collaborative choices made by individuals, families, friends, and migrant associations within their social networks. According to these studies, migration decisions are substantially impacted by the net of social ties among immigrants and potential migrants, often notwithstanding individual economic conditions (Hammar, T. *et al.* 2021). Some authors consider also the impact of institutions mediating between individual aspiration and final concrete migration decisions or the influence of different countries' normative regulations on migration.

In any case, contrary to common assumptions, migration decisions are very rarely determined by traffickers or enhanced by NGO rescue activities (Cusumano, E., & Villa, M., 2019). Instead,

those entities normally function as further facilitators within the broader social context. Migrant smuggling, in most contexts, arises as a reaction to the heightened militarization of border controls, rather than being the fundamental motive of irregular migration (see Figure 3) (Haas, de H., 2015; Haas, de H., 2020).

FIGURE 4: EUROPE'S RESPONSE TO COUNTERACTING SMUGGLING ACTIVITIES AND ITS CONSEQUENCES (CARLING, J., 2015). INIZIO MODULO

Thirdly, according to *macro-level* theories, migration is perceived as a result of broader economic forces, encompassing factors such as income disparities, job opportunities, demographic changes, and modernization processes. Essentially, this perspective considers migration as an outcome of both pull factors, like economic opportunities and demographic conditions in destination countries and push factors, often associated with labor market dynamics and economic pressures in the homeland. Together, these elements are regarded as playing a role in the intricate and dynamic patterns observed in international migration. Scholars typically draw as an example the significant drop in international movements during the 2007-2008 economic crisis, explained by a lack of incentives (pull factors) in destination countries (Van Hear, N. *et al.* 2020; Haas, de H., 2021).

Contemporary scholars claim that no theory alone would be convincing enough, as no theory alone would successfully encompass the multifaceted nature of migration, where a myriad of different causes, contexts, and backgrounds unfold. Any attempt to pinpoint a single dominant theory could prove useless since international migration is molded by countless factors interconnecting in multiple complex ways.

Thus, in trying to grasp a general understanding of “Why do people migrate?”, scholars identify a range of potential drivers impacting migrants’ choices:

- ❖ *Environmental* factors: the threat of natural disasters, the impact of climate change, or the scarcity of essential resources like food and water can push or sometimes force people to leave their homeland in search of safer locations.
- ❖ *Economic* considerations: the pursuit of better job opportunities, the aspiration for improved economic and living conditions, or the need to escape a struggling local economy can influence migration choices.
- ❖ *Social* factors: higher-quality educational prospects and family ties influence the decision-making process.
- ❖ *Political* conditions: persecution, conflict, or repressive government policies can compel individuals to migrate chasing politically stable or free environments.
- ❖ *Demographic* factors: the density of the population or the prevalence of diseases also affect these decisions.
- ❖ *Personal and household characteristics*, such as age, level of education, wealth, marital status, personal preferences, ethnicity, religion, and language, shape individuals' propensity to migrate. These characteristics can determine both the desirability and feasibility of staying or moving.

Other intervening obstacles and facilitators, which can include anything from immigration policies to the cost of moving, the availability of social support networks, and technological advancements, can either obstruct or enable the migration process (Black, R. *et al.*, 2011).

Beyond these tangible factors, the decision to migrate may be also influenced by *subjective* elements such as personal attitudes and perceptions about origin countries or potential destinations, emotional responses to the idea of moving, and inherent psychological traits (Government Office for Science, 2011; Majidi, N., 2018; Castelli, F. 2018; Haas, de H., 2021). Therefore, a comprehensive understanding of migration requires recognizing the intricate web of influences shaping individuals' decisions to migrate, and acknowledging the interplay of all *micro*, *meso*, and *macro-level* factors (Haas, de H., 2020).

Assembling all the puzzle pieces, a clearer image emerges depicting international migration as a complex phenomenon, marked by constant evolution and fluidity. Hard to define and measure, it is characterized by a variety of narratives, motivations, and durations it encompasses.

It includes everyone (documented, undocumented, or in the middle ground) from workers and students to family migrants and refugees, whose more or less voluntary choice is affected by a myriad of factors like economy, politics, networks, society, and personal conditions. In this ever-evolving landscape countries fluidly exchange roles as sources and destinations of migration underscoring the inherent adaptability of migration to global trends, policies, and societal change.

Hence, it's this dynamic essence of international migration that truly stands out, illustrating its ongoing evolution and responsiveness to the changing world around us. Then, how is international migration changing in the last decades?

1.2 International Migration: What is Changing?

Considering international migration's adaptability and evolving nature, it becomes natural to ask how this phenomenon is changing and what current and future patterns might emerge.

This curiosity, first thing, leads to a central question, encapsulating the core FAQs that define the new millennium. "Are we living in an unprecedented time of migration?"

On the first level of inquiry, an examination of historical data reveals that the proportion of international migrants in the world population did increase during the 1990s. These last decades are characterized indeed, by a significant upsurge, illustrative of the increased global mobility and shifts in migration patterns. However, this is not unique to the late 20th and early 21st centuries. Equivalent periods of extensive migration occurred back in the 19th and early 20th centuries too (Gellwitzki, C. N. L., & Houde, A. M., 2023). Earlier waves were boosted by various global trends, policies, and societal transformations such as the Industrial Revolution, colonial expansions, economic disparities, wars, and political upheavals which instigated many individuals and communities to resettle abroad. These studies highlight the constant and cyclical nature of human mobility rather than its extraordinary features (Haas, de H., 2005; Zapata-Barrero, R., 2023).

Additionally, a second stage of analysis reveals that a century ago, the percentage of international migrants globally was, in fact, identical to the current levels, constantly being around 3%. The absolute number of migrants did rise in recent decades, with more and more people moving globally. Still, it is undeniable that the global population is also growing concurrently, at the same pace. Simultaneously, various forms of mobility, such as tourism, commuting, and business travel, have increased, but still, the share of people changing residence has remained remarkably stable. As a result, the percentage of international migrants over the global population remains invariable. Hence, contrary to common beliefs, globalization is no trigger of an extraordinary surge in international migration numbers. Indeed, the increasing interconnectedness of global societies may enhance people's awareness of other cultures, but this doesn't necessarily translate into an upswing in global flows (Czaika, M., & Haas, de H., 2014).

Hence, there is no compelling evidence of an unprecedented global migration crisis. However, as anticipated, there has been a marked shift in migration patterns, validating the evolving and adaptable features of the migration phenomenon. These evolution trends notably include a rise

in South-to-North migration following post-World War II, decolonization, and Western economic growth. This shift presents, in fact, unprecedented challenges for Western societies as they accommodate culturally and physically increasingly distinct immigrant communities coming from the global South (Zlotnik, H. 1998); Sørensen, N. N., et al. 2002). The heightened visibility of global migration in Western societies has fostered the perception of unparalleled migration levels, often depicted as *floods*. But, indeed, the current dynamics of human mobility are marked by changing directions in migration flows rather than an absolute global surge (Brochmann, G., & Hammar, T., 1999, Herda D., 2021). Europe, for instance, which was not initially expected to become a major immigration-region, and Turkey, traditionally known for sending labor abroad, have both unexpectedly transformed into popular destinations for migrants (Herda, D. 2023; Lutz, P., & Bitschnau, M. 2023).

Looking ahead, the future outlook of migration will be totally different from the current one. In fact, many argue it is worthless to ask whether there will be fewer or more migrants. It could turn out much more relevant to understand the major shifts in migration course. Where will future migrants originate from, and to which destinations will they head to? What are the latest trends and changes in migration patterns?

Here's a glimpse into the major trends likely shaping the current and future dynamics of international migration:

1. **Globalization of Migration:** As anticipated, globalization has not multiplied the number of migrants moving across the world but has rather multiplied the routes, the means, and the styles of migration. Current migrants originate from very diverse economic statuses, social structures, and cultural contexts. Additionally, as migration becomes more globalized, a growing number of countries are touched by international migration. Origin countries are increasingly diversifying, covering a wider spectrum of backgrounds, whilst the preferred destinations for migrants are constantly changing, adapting to dynamic factors such as political stability, economic opportunities, demographic needs, or societal developments.
2. **Differentiation of Migration:** With the amplification and diversification of means, styles, backgrounds, and destinations of migration, coupled with the growing governments' actions to partially restrict international mobility, global migration is witnessing a differentiation process. Currently, many countries are experiencing an increase in the variety of migration types happening simultaneously, including labor migration, family reunification, refugees, cyclical migration, and permanent settlement. In fact, governments' efforts to restrict or manage specific migration types often lead to migrants

simply changing their migration strategies rather than stopping. In the context of Africa-EU migration, for example, as entry policies and visa controls become stricter, migration continues but its nature shifts. There has been a worldwide switch from regular forms of migration towards a rise in undocumented, irregular, smuggled, or asylum-seeking migration.

3. **Feminization of Labor Migration:** Historically dominated by male individuals, labor migration has witnessed a notable feminization since the 1960s. Women now play a predominant role in diverse migration movements, challenging previous categorizations and raising awareness of their increasingly important role. This shift is particularly evident in movements involving for instance Cape Verdeans to Italy, Filipinas to the Middle East, and Thais to Japan (Haas, de H., *et al.* 2019).
4. **Evolution of Migration Policies:** Over the past half-century, policies in most net immigration countries have become more sophisticated and overall, counter to widespread beliefs, less restrictive. This is particularly evident in the creation of free-movement zones like the Schengen Area. However, this liberalization trend has been non-linear and non-uniform across countries, policy areas, and migrant categories. Policies have become more fine-grained, imposing more stringent entry criteria on “unwanted migrants”, whilst facilitating the mobility of “wanted migrants”. Governments incentivize preferred migrants picked based on their skills and the current labor market’s demands, encouraging for example highly qualified ICT workers, engineers, or immigrants who can fill domestic labor shortages in specific sectors such as health services, and agriculture (Massey, D. S., 1999).
5. **Visa Access and Quality of Life:** The availability of migration options is increasingly tied to visa access, reflecting the diplomatic status and international relations of a migrant’s origin country. Nationals from countries with high human development levels, which tend to be also preferred destination countries, enjoy greater visa-free travel options up to around 85% of all other countries worldwide, allowing for greater freedom of movement. On the other hand, those from countries with very low human development face much more restrictive pathways, potentially leading to reliance on irregular migration options, highlighting a stark contrast in global mobility based on geopolitical and economic factors (IOM, 2022).
6. **Symbolism in Immigration Policies:** In recent times, immigration policies have increasingly played symbolic roles, often acting more as “signals of control” to the public or voters in specific migration policy domains, rather than concrete steps towards creating an equitable society. Policymakers, pressured to “do something” to address migration,

employ these policies to demonstrate action. This results in a discourse gap characterized by the frequent mismatch between often stringent and anti-migrant political discourses and the reality of more permissive policy practices (Czaika, M., & de Haas, H., 2013; Chastand, J. B., 2022).

1.3 The Politicization of International Migration and its Key Drivers

Remarkably, one of the most significant transformations characterizing the “new” international migration lies in its profound politicization. The increasing impact of international migration on domestic politics, bilateral and regional relationships, and global national security policies contributes to its growing importance in political discussions. This trend is evident in several areas. Countries are progressively adopting heightened border control measures in response to specific migration events. Additionally, the emergence of nationalist political movements leveraging migration as a focal point, highlights how it is increasingly seen as an economic or cultural challenge. These movements gain support by advocating for policies that restrict migration, aiming to address the perceived threats it poses. This heightened political relevance, coupled with the rise of polarized (political) movements (nationalist on one hand and pro-immigrant on the other), marks the current era as an unprecedented time of politicization of migration (Van der Brug, W. *et al.*, 2015).

Migration has, indeed, boldly made its way into public and political discourse, often monopolizing it and attracting significant attention from the media and the public. Policymakers are under increasing pressure to address, manage, and mitigate the phenomenon as economic stability, cultural identity, and security concerns escalate. Consequently, political and civil movements incrementally align themselves as either pro- or against immigration, significantly polarizing the conversation. Henceforth, international migration has become a complex political issue, affecting the social and economic sphere, and profoundly influencing public attitudes and opinions on migration (Blanton, S. L. & Kegley, C. W., 2017).

But what exactly are the key factors leading to the politicization of migration?

Two main bodies of literature examine the process of issues becoming politicized or remaining outside the realm of political attention.

The first corpus of research centers on *agenda-setting*. These studies suggest that an issue becomes politicized as long as it is perceived as one of the top priority problems on the political agenda, capturing much attention from the media and the public. Several scholars posit that the communications media, through their ability to identify and publicize issues, play a pivotal role in shaping the problems that attract attention from governments and international

organizations, and in directing public opinion towards specific issues (Van der Brug, W. *et al.*, 2015). Indeed, issue salience, in a simplified view, moves from public opinion through the news media, party politics, and eventually to government and policymaking; making it become a political issue requiring solutions in terms of policies (Jones, B. D. & F. R. Baumgartner, 2005; Baumgartner, F. R., *et al.*, 2009a). The *agenda-setting* effect occurs through a cognitive process known as “accessibility”. It implies that the frequency and prominence of mediatic and political coverage significantly influence the accessibility of specific issues within the audience’s memory. When respondents are asked what the most important problem facing the country is, they answer with the most accessible news issue in memory, which is typically the most reproduced and emphasized issue (Dearing, J & Rogers, E, 1988).

However, the relevance of an issue is not solely determined by its accessibility or by measurable factors such as the issue’s width or objective significance. It is also intricately tied to the subjective perceived importance attributed to the issue. For instance, the political and policy response to migration doesn’t depend solely on the actual numbers of migrants but also on how the issue is perceived and described in terms of its impact on national culture, religion, and social cohesion (Kustov, A., 2023).

In essence, individual engagement coupled with media coverage and political instrumentalization of a particular issue, contribute to heightening its political salience and lead thus to its politicization (Miller, J. M., 2017).

The second body of literature posit, instead, that a social problem transitions into the political sphere once it generates significant divergence in viewpoints among political actors. According to this theory, for an issue to be politicized it must create some level of *polarization* within the political arena, essentially becoming a source of conflict. *Polarization* refers to the extent of disagreement or distance between different positions towards certain issues within parliamentary debates. The crux of this theory lies in positional party rivalry. This concept views electoral competition as a strategic game in which parties present different choices to the electorate in terms of different policy proposals, solutions to relevant issues, and opposing ideological stances (Van der Brug, W. *et al.*, 2015). This differentiation not only contributes to the shaping of parties’ political identity but also intends to frame the political debate around some strategic issues, thereby influencing their course into the political discourse and the policy-making process (Brewer, M. D., 2005).

In reality, most contemporary scholars do not align with either theory but generally claim that the politicization of complex issues, like migration, results, from the combined influence of both *polarization* and *salience* (Van der Brug, W. *et al.*, 2015; Gattinara, P. C., & Morales, L., 2017; Stevens, F., & Willems, E., 2024). They argue that as long as a high-salience issue does not elicit any kind of disagreement or conflict in the political arena it remains a mere urgent problem. Vice versa, as an issue is a source of conflict but still does not gain enough attention, it will lie at the back as a latent conflict. Thus, according to them, the politicization process can only be triggered by both conditions simultaneously (see Figure 4).

FIGURE 4: TYPOLOGY OF POLITICS TOWARDS A TOPIC (VAN DER BRUG, W. ET AL., 2015).

The earthquake in L'Aquila, Italy in 2009, for instance, serves as an illustrative example of how an issue be politically and publicly relevant without immediate politicization due to a low level of conflict and polarization. It was instantly placed at the top of the Italian agenda, marking its indisputably high salience and urgency. Yet, in this case, despite the heightened relevance of the earthquake-related problems, there was no disagreement but rather consensus among political actors and the public about the urgent need to address risks, enhance infrastructure seismic resilience, and improve disaster readiness.

In this context, the lack of significant ideological partitioning granted a collaborative and unified attitude, illustrating that high salience alone does not necessarily imply politicization when harmony and general agreement prevail (Brewer, M. D., 2005).

In contrast, certain issues may not enter the political sphere, even if they reach high polarization levels but lack attention and relevance to the public. Consider the litigious debate surrounding policy proposals related to *green* and environmental regulations in the last few years in Italy. Notwithstanding the highly polarized political arena and the heated debates between political parties and the public, climatic concerns and *clean* industries seem to gather poor attention and relevance within the public discourse, due to their limited mediatic visibility or perceived

urgency among the population. The intense polarization and disagreement continue, yet the matter is still not perceived as a priority, whether due to other dominant topics overtaking importance or a lack of media focus. This example outlines once again that, for an issue to become politicized, it simultaneously needs to gain both salience within the political and public agenda and polarized disagreement (Van der Brug, W. *et al.*, 2015; Gattinara, P. C., & Morales, L., 2017).

But how did migration become such a politicized issue?

On the one hand, the topic has undoubtedly gained unprecedented attention, drawing intense scrutiny and debate across various key arenas: within the institutional arena (National and European parliaments), within the intermediary arena (including political parties and civil society organizations), and in public opinion.

To understand this heightened salience of migration-related discourses, first, it is crucial to recognize the multifaceted impact of migrants on host countries. International migration, indeed, holds the potential to reshape various dimensions of host countries' domestic social fabric, actively introducing new cultures, religions, and beliefs. This impact extends beyond the simplistic view of immigrants as passive guests; it fosters complex interactions between newcomers and the native population. For instance, music or literature festivals organized by native civil society groups and the popularity of ethnic restaurants illustrate the tangible co-existence and contribution of migrants to host societies (Buonfino, A., 2004). These visible transformations in the social sphere inevitably foster concerns about economic stability, cultural identity, and security among the population, intensifying public and political attention on the topic and thus, placing the discourse surrounding migration and its management at the top priority list in the political agenda.

As anticipated, this extraordinary surge in public salience does not rely solely upon the width of the phenomenon, or its cognitive accessibility but also on other factors such as public perception and media representation. Despite the smaller volume of undocumented migration flows compared to documented and regular family or labor migration, the former gains disproportionately high political and media attention. Internationally, even though global migration rates have been relatively stable over the past fifty years, the political and mediatic spotlight on migration issues has tenfold increased. This shift is not driven by an actual increase in migration volumes but rather by changes in public opinion and the strategic choices of political parties and candidates. The media and the public opinion have played a pivotal role in bringing migration issues to the forefront of political debates (Jeannet, A.-M., *et al.*, 2021).

Additionally, in several European countries, political parties and candidates have made migration a centerpiece of their electoral campaigns, inevitably dominating public debates, and

leading to numerous self-titled summits dedicated to addressing migration at the regional level. The significance of migration was also underscored in the British referendum, wherein concerns over migration are recognized to have strongly influenced the outcomes of Brexit (Lauwers, N., *et al.*, 2021).

This complex interplay between demographic realities, public opinion, and political agendas has significantly raised the profile of migration issues, leading to an unparalleled relevance of the topic within public and political debates (Alto Analytics, 2019).

On the other hand, simultaneously significant polarization has unfolded within international migration debates, with individuals and groups having strong, often opposing views.

Indeed, contemporary societies wrestle with an array of challenges, encompassing migration, globalization, and shifts in welfare states. These challenges collectively contribute to transforming social cohesion into a contentious domain. Different actors within society advocate for disparate conceptions of social cohesion, with some supporting a vision that reinforces identity and fosters community closeness, while others endorse a more inclusive, non-identity-based social cohesiveness (Van der Brug, W. *et al.*, 2015).

This division is further amplified by grassroots organizations, growing in numbers and influence, and gathering financial and physical support from a broader public through awareness campaigns, and public demonstrations (ICPA, 2018).

These developments compel governments to walk the delicate wire between immigration control and migrant integration, with political parties under pressure to propose effective migration policies. Concurrently, the mass media assumes a pivotal role in strategically shaping the visibility of either xenophobic right-wing actors or pro-migrant movements, strongly influencing public support or opposition to immigration policies (see accessibility bias above) (Van der Brug, W. *et al.*, 2015; Paul, H. L., & Fitzgerald, J., 2021).

In essence, the process of polarization is driven by a combination of societal challenges, advocacy by grassroots organizations, governmental and political responses to migration, and the role of media in shaping public opinion.

Hence, migration has clearly been a hot-button issue, marked by a deep polarization in the political arena, leading to a substantial mobilization of the public either in support of or against migrants.

As learned above, this increasing salience and polarization have made the migration discourse intensely politicized, as evidenced by the analysis conducted by Alto Analytics before the EU elections (2019) on Twitter in Italy. It confirms that immigration emerges as the second most relevant topic, characterized by a highly polarized debate dominated by a small fraction of

users. Specifically, 0.1% of users (almost exclusively right-wing advocates) were responsible for producing 10% of the content, indicating a targeted effort to strategically influence the narrative around migration (Alto Analytics, 2019).

This escalating politicization of the migration discourse collides, indeed, with a notable political shift that characterizes the twenty-first century. European voters are increasingly supporting anti-immigration parties, often categorized as *radical*, *far*, or *populist* right. These parties, typically centralizing their electoral campaigns and political movements on a clear anti-immigration agenda, tap into and amplify public anxieties over the refugee crisis. By employing populist tactics, they claim to voice the collective feelings, frustrations, and desires of the people, gaining significant electoral support and sometimes reaching majorities in governments (see Figure 5).

Notably, their supporters seem to closely align with these anti-immigrant attitudes, with many voters choosing these parties specifically for their opposition towards immigration (Dennison, J., & Geddes, A., 2019; Campo, F., *et al.*, 2021).

Thus, the question arises: Are Europeans becoming more hostile towards immigration?

FIGURE 5: POLLING FOR ANTI-IMMIGRATION PARTIES IN 15 WESTERN EUROPEAN COUNTRIES (DENNISON, J., & GEDDES, A., 2019).

1.4 Public Opinion and Migration

Considering the fast-rising anti-immigration parties’ popularity and support, expectations would predict a parallel increase in anti-immigrant sentiments among the European population. In reality, in recent decades, empirical evidence suggests that attitudes toward immigration have remained stable over the long term (Kustov, A., *et al.*, 2021). Interestingly, contrary to most projections, in the aftermath of the 2015-16 so-called migration crisis, there has not been a corresponding negative shift in attitudes toward immigration. Indeed, there is no empirical evidence indicating a public preference for the “end of asylum”. There is no widespread public support for the concept of “repatriation” (Jeannet, A.-M., *et al.*, 2021).

In truth, some data sources and specific survey questions indicate that attitudes toward immigration, in the last decade, have shown a tendency to become rather more positive in several European countries (see Figure 6) (Heath, A. & Richards, L., 2016; Dennison, J., & Geddes, A., 2019; Scipioni, M., *et al.*, 2019; Banai, A., *et al.* 2021; Dennison, J. Kustov, A., 2023).

FIGURE 6 : NEGATIVE ATTITUDES TO EU AND NON-EU IMMIGRANTS, 2014-2018 (SCIPIONI, M., ET AL., 2019).

Yet, if individuals are not displaying heightened hostility toward immigration, what explains the substantial increase in support for anti-immigration parties over the past decade?

The growing electoral support for anti-immigration parties, associated with the absence of a corresponding rise in anti-immigration sentiment, poses a paradoxical scenario. To resolve this puzzle, it could be useful to shift the focus and go back to the concept of migration's increasing salience. The variation in issue importance could, in fact, serve as the crucial cognitive missing link to understanding the growing support for anti-immigration parties (Krosnick, J. A., *et al.*, 2018; Dennison, J., 2019).

As previously discussed, issue salience, also known as issue attention, refers to how people perceive particular social issues. It represents the political inclinations of the average voter.

In other words, people care about different things, and to understand why they vote a certain way, it is essential to recognize their priorities, weighing specific issues more or less heavily, in the same way as they presumably do in deciding what to vote (Paul, H. L., & Fitzgerald, J., 2021).

High levels of concern about an issue influence individuals' behavior through emotional triggers, resulting in increased and selective information about the issue and parties' positions on it to foster cognitive consonance. Indeed, voters not only tend to support parties with policies congruent to their own, but they also weigh congruence based on the salience of the issues (Helbling, M., 2014). Consequently, in the realm of electoral strategy, parties strive not only to align with public attitudes – which tend to be stable - but also to increase the salience of issues they *own*, strategically capitalizing on these issues when they gain prominence - a phenomenon often described as “wave-riding” (Gattinara, P. C., 2016; Miller, J. M., *et al.*, 2017; Krosnick, J. A., *et al.*, 2018; Dennison, J., & Geddes, A., 2019; Kustov, A., 2023).

Yet, how does salience sway voters towards supporting anti-immigration parties?

As mentioned above, research indicates that individual public salience of issues tends to be relatively stable over time. According to Krosnick *et al.* (2018), the variation in issue salience between individuals is shaped by three factors: self-interest, social identification, and values.

Still, what is far more dynamic and easily influenced by external elements is the *national* salience of issues (Iyengar, S., & Kinder, D. R., 2010). Over time, issue salience at the national level is swayed by shifts in media coverage, by prominent events or problems that capture national attention, including for instance, increasing and highly politicized flows of immigrants (Krosnick, J. A., *et al.*, 2018).

Essentially, during periods when international migration gains very high salience, negative attitudes towards immigration become a key determinant of votes for the *far right*, whereas these attitudes might not have a significant impact on voting when other issues take precedence within the national political debate (Krosnick, J. A., 1990). An illustrative example can be found in the marked decline in the salience of the immigration debate during the COVID-19 pandemic. In theory, a global health crisis like a pandemic could heighten apprehensions regarding outsiders or the potential contribution of migration to the spread of disease. In fact, contrary to expectations, the perceived importance and urgency of the migration discourse significantly diminished. This somewhat unexpected phenomenon can be attributed to the emergence of another prominent issue, likely monopolizing public attention. Consequently, when alternative issues take precedence, individuals may redirect their focus and change their voting preferences according to their actual dominating concern, in this case, the COVID-19 issue, relegating migration to a less pressing and relevant consideration. During and immediately after the pandemic, there was a general drop in the salience placed on migration issues, with most people ranking them below second in terms of issue priority (see Figure 8) (Dennison, J. *et al.*, 2023).

FIGURE 8: IMMIGRATION SALIENCE PRE- AND POST- THE OUTBREAK OF COVID-19.

RESPONSES TO THE QUESTION “WHAT DO YOU THINK ARE THE TWO MOST IMPORTANT ISSUES AFFECTING YOUR COUNTRY?” % OF PEOPLE SAYING IMMIGRATION IS ONE OF THE TWO MOST IMPORTANT ISSUES.

THE VERTICAL LINE REPRESENTS THE EMERGENCE OF COVID-19 (DENNISON, J. ET AL., 2023).

Essentially, there is little evidence of an anti-immigration pandemic spreading across Europe. Attitudes toward migration have, in fact, followed a positive trend over the last decade, considering either immigration from outside or within the EU. Notwithstanding some variations

across countries, there is a general conveyance towards more favorable sentiments on migration (Vidigal, R., & Jerit, J., 2022).

The rise of anti-immigration parties appears to be more a consequence of increased salience of immigration among those individuals with negative predispositions ex-ante. Simply put, certain aspects of immigration possibly perceived as threats to conservative values, such as security, tradition, or conformity, have triggered and increased a pre-existing anti-immigration sentiment, but among a decreasing number of Europeans.

Changing people's political attitudes is likely to be very difficult, but aligning and allying with their worst fears may be less so (Dennison, J. *et al.*, 2023).

While immigration preferences remain relatively stable, their significance to voters proves to be more volatile. Although providing information can effectively persuade even on racialized issues, it seems more challenging for topics that voters consider to be significant (Howe, L. C., & Krosnick, J. A., 2017; Vidigal, R., & Jerit, J., 2022).

An important implication may be that even though anti-immigration preferences are on the decline, events that garner media attention on immigration are more likely to engage those opposing it, placing advocates of immigration at a systematic disadvantage when trying to draw national attention to the issue.

Some scholars deem that a plausible explanation for this phenomenon is that the perceived threat from immigration, whether economic or cultural, is more psychologically powerful and mobilizing than perceived opportunities - an instance of the broader concept of loss aversion in politics (Baumeister, R. F., *et al.* 2001; Alesina, A., & Passarelli, F., 2019; Kustov, A., 2023).

Interestingly, most recent studies show that the individuals prioritizing and placing greater importance on the international migration debate are counterintuitively those with anti-immigrant sentiments (predominantly right voters) rather than those who support immigration (left voters). This imbalance holds significant implications, entailing that public support for immigration is relatively weak compared to a more vigorous and steady opposition, essentially allowing opponents to exert greater political influence on the topic. Some studies outline, for instance, that young people attach greater importance to the issue of climate change than to the issue of migration. They consider both to be either relevant or very relevant issues, although in general migration is of less concern than climate change (Mulholland, E., *et al.*, 2017; Krakow University, 2022).

Kustov (2023) names a systematic asymmetry that consistently disadvantages pro-immigration advocates. Indeed, particularly during high salience periods, even when the majority of the public either supports or is neutral towards pro-immigration reforms, politicians still lack

enough motivation to implement them, as they are not penalized by voters for not doing so. Conversely, they face much greater pressure to enforce anti-immigration policies for stricter influx control.

Some scholars attribute this asymmetry to a common disillusion among pro-immigration advocates that nothing substantial can be changed through traditional advocacy, given immigration's complex and international nature. This attitude leads to a reduced priority and salience placed on immigration issues, even for those closely involved in the subject (Coin, F., 2004). Other authors from the *Mindchangers* European project theorize that young people prefer to engage in actions related to climate change rather than migration mainly because of a higher level of awareness of the former issue; the presence of numerous opportunities for young people to participate in groups, actions, and initiatives that address climate change, and greater familiarity with the types of actions that can be undertaken in climate change advocacy (Mulholland, E., et al., 2017; Krakow University, 2022).

1.5 Public Attitudes Toward Migration in Italy

The analysis of migration attitudes will now proceed with a specific focus on Italy and Italian citizens' attitudes toward newcomers. This in-depth examination will serve as a general theoretical framework for the survey experiment, which will be conducted, indeed, within the Italian territory.

To begin with, the Eurobarometer surveys report a striking difference between Italian perceptions and reality: Italians deem migrants to represent 24% of the total population, yet the actual amount stands at a modest 5.05% (see Figure 8). Furthermore, Italy is often assumed to be a leading European host for refugees, but surprisingly places in the 11th spot of top destinations, not making it to the expected top 10 list (see Figure 9).

Additionally, there emerges a tendency to overestimate the influx of immigrants from Africa. Data reveals that 27.4% of respondents identify North Africa as the primary region of origin, whereas only 12.9% of immigrants actually arrive from this area. The immigrant landscape further develops with half of the resident immigrants originating from Europe (50.2%, including 30.1% from the EU), slightly over a fifth from the African continent and Asia, respectively 21.7% and 20.8%, and a 7.2% share from the Americas (Saso R., 2019).

Stranieri e "nuovi italiani" in Italia

ISPI

FIGURE 8: FOREIGNERS AND "NEW ITALIANS" IN ITALY.

BLUE: DOCUMENTED MIGRANTS

GREY: UNDOCUMENTED MIGRANTS

ORANGE: "NEW ITALIANS". MIGRANTS LIVING IN ITALY FOR 10 YEARS (ISPI ONLINE, 2023).

FIGURE 9: NUMBER OF REFUGEES HOSTED PER CAPITA (EUROSTAT).

These misperceptions and stereotypes spring up in a context of mounting skepticism, exacerbated by the sharp politicization discussed earlier. This tangled framework has caused many Italians to feel disillusioned, ending up blaming the European Union which is believed to have failed to offer the support expected. The frustration then extends to other nations perceived as neglecting Italy in the management of its maritime borders. Italy views the so-called “invasion of immigrants” as a problematic issue, especially in terms of job prospects for native citizens, making it a major public concern (Basile, L., & Borri, R., 2022).

As a result of the rising skepticism and frustration, people tend increasingly to view migration issues through the lens of group identity, spurring a dissociation from *us* to *them*. Most Italians recognize the distinctions between migrants and refugees, yet there is a widespread tendency to simply label them a *non-membership* group, often referred to as *the other*. As cited above, right-wing populists strategically exploit this dynamic by amplifying narratives that paint the out-group as a threat to in-group members.

Additionally, economic instability, rising inequalities, cultural and demographic changes, and the increasing influence of social media as a primary source of information, contribute to creating a fertile environment for anti-immigrant propaganda, often fostering misperceptions

and blurring the real picture (Boeri, T., *et al.*, 2023). Hostility towards immigration further grows as fed by mounting safety concerns, a sensed loss of control over borders, and the government's perceived incapacity to handle the migration phenomenon. The apparent overwhelming situation coupled with the feeling of loneliness while dealing with a crisis, inevitably fuels frustration and a stronger inclination towards drastic measures (Yudkin, D., 2018).

Beneath these sentiments lies an additional fear related to integration. A significant portion of Italians, 44%, disagrees with the idea that immigrants try to integrate into Italian society, reflecting apprehensions about national identity erosion. Additionally, there is unenthusiastic acceptance of Muslim groups, with 40% of respondents expressing concerns about the compatibility of Italian identity with Islam.

Religious identity, particularly rooted in Catholic heritage, plays a significant role in shaping Italians' attitudes towards migrants and refugees. Almost half of the population, identifying as Catholic, feels a responsibility to help newcomers, yet there is a parallel fear of losing Italy's religious identity, with 48% supporting measures to safeguard it from foreign faiths (Bianchi, G. E., 2011).

Aside from these general trends, Italian public opinion on migration presents a deeply multifaceted reality, revealing a country divided into millions of different fractions on the topic. This fragmentation, mirroring Italy's national history and, in some ways, the weight of the diverse regional identities, has been organized by Yudkin, (2018) into seven major segments, reflecting seven macro families of attitudes toward migration.

These segments, range in a continuum from those with more *open* attitudes in favor of migrants and refugees, such as the *Cosmopolitan Italians* and the *Humanitarian Catholics*, to those at the opposite extreme with more *closed* viewpoints, including the *Hostile Nationalists* and the *Defenders of Culture*. In the middle ground, approximately half of the Italian population finds representation in the *Disengaged Moderates*, the *Neglected*, and the *Security Concerned*. (see Figure 11).

Remarkably, unlike other nations, these intermediate groups are divided into two distinct tendencies: one group leans toward being open and more accepting (*Disengaged Moderates*), while the other inclines toward closure and protection (*Neglected and Security Concerned*). They distinguish themselves not only in their overall attitudes towards closure or openness but also in the factors influencing their political choices, the intensity of their positions, and their level of engagement with the issues at hand. Anyhow, despite the overarching polarization and contrary to common expectations, the larger segments, hosting the majority of the population, reside in the middle ground, often referred to as the *movable middle* (Dixon, T., *et al.* 2018).

FIGURE 11: CAKE GRAPH SHOWING THE SEVEN SEGMENTS OF THE ITALIAN POPULATION (IBIDEM).

Yet, what are the main characteristics of these macro-segments partitioning the Italian population?

- ❖ The *Cosmopolitan Italians* represent 12% of the total population. They are mainly students and retirees, whose educational level varies from medium to low. About half of this constituency self-defines as either non-Catholic or non-religious at all. Notably, the proportion of respondents identifying with left-wing or center-left political parties is significantly high (72%). The representatives of this group express hope and optimism in their own future and the Nation's prospects. While globalization and its repercussions are regarded negatively by *Cosmopolitans*, they are still favorable to immigration. Interestingly, they think of migrants as akin to Italians and, compared to all other segments, are the most eager to help them. Overall, this group portrays a progressive and humanitarian outlook, remarking support and sympathy for refugees and migrants.
- ❖ The *Humanitarian Catholics* (16%) constitute the older generation, with the majority being over 65 years old. A considerable 71% of this cohort are practicing Catholics, and 57% place themselves within the center-right or, alternatively the center-left of the political arena, mainly supporting parties like Forza Italia and the Democratic Party. They proclaim an optimistic viewpoint, as they deem the Italian economy to be consistently growing, predicting a similar trajectory in the next years. They are very proud of being Italian, and believe the Italian identity is not threatened by immigration. They display a

strong feeling of responsibility towards refugees, as the core element of Italy's tradition of solidarity. Their faith shapes their values, and they eagerly agree with Pope Francis about the need to welcome refugees.

- ❖ The *Hostile Nationalists* comprise 7% of the population, with a high proportion of middle-aged people fluctuating among lower-middle levels of education. 62% of them are practicing Catholics.

They are overall optimistic about their prospects, nonetheless many deem it difficult, for people like them, to live satisfactorily in Italy. They are more pessimistic about the future of Italian society and economy, as they consider it structured for the exclusive benefit of rich and powerful people. They are proud of the country's history and convinced of the need to protect its religious heritage against outsider faiths. They hold the most negative view of immigration, refugees, and Muslims, and according to them, employers should give priority to Italians over immigrants. *Hostile Nationalists* believe it is necessary to put aside the protection of rights to overcome impending dangers.

- ❖ The *Defenders of Culture* constituting 17% of the population, include mainly middle-aged Italians between 31- and 50-year-olds. This family embraces many workers, living predominantly in North-west Italy. They think Italy needs a strong leader to solve the country's problems.

More than all segments are concerned about the cultural impact of immigration, believing Italian identity to be disappearing. Besides, they think that migrants are unfairly given precedence over Italians in access to subsidies, housing, and public services.

- ❖ The *Disengaged Moderates* representing the largest segment of the population (19%), are predominantly young and well-educated, with a significant presence of individuals aged 18-30. 30% of them don't identify either with the left or with the right of the political spectrum. They are collocated mostly in the northwest, in the south, and on the islands. *Disengaged moderates* are uncertain about their prospects of success and doubtful about the possibility that people like them can really impact politics and society. Overall, disinterested in political parties, they do not have strong opinions and do not participate in debates. They think of Italy as divided, and weak but also welcoming. Despite they are unsure about the effects of immigration, both economically and culturally, they still display warm attitudes towards refugees and Muslims.

- ❖ The *Neglected* constituting 17% of the population, are mainly composed of elderly people, with a significant number being over 65 years old, mostly presenting a low level of

education. The majority live in the north-east of Italy and are inclined to vote for the Lega party. They are pessimistic both for the country's and their own prospects, believing they have suffered more than others from the impact of economic decline and social change. According to them, the structure of the Italian economy favors only the rich and powerful people, making success more difficult for people like them. They feel that immigration is creating divisions in the country and tapping resources: their opposition to "unwanted, voluntary" migrants is stronger than in all other groups. Despite these feelings, they support the right to asylum, claiming that refugees should be welcomed if they accept the Italian culture.

- ❖ The *Security Concerned* group, comprising 12% of the population, consists of individuals aged 31-64, ranging from medium to low levels of education. Approximately 44% identify with center or center-right political parties and live for the most part in the center-south area.

They think optimistically about Italy's future economic environment, believing in the favorable potentials of globalization. However, they are more discouraged when it comes to their own future and quite anxious about their safety in general, especially pertaining to crime and terrorism. They deem immigration too dangerous, firmly believing that Italy must undertake any possible measure to stop terrorism, even if this means ignoring human rights.

Once reviewed the dominant features characterizing the various categories within the public opinion spectrum, it is worthwhile to conclude this broad framework of attitudes by analyzing the major trends that differentiate Italy from other European countries.

Generally, *open values* type Italians look at immigration in a positive way, while *Disengaged Moderates* remain unsure. Conversely, *Neglected*, *Security Concerned*, and *closed values* segments are prone to perceiving negative effects of immigrants.

Interestingly, the ground below these positions varies from one segment to another:

- Uncertain individuals view the international migration discourse through the lens of an Italian cultural war versus migrants, thus spurring hostilities toward immigration.
- The *Security Concerned* group's enmity is rooted in the perception that newcomers may increase the risk of delinquency and terrorism.
- The *Neglected* primary concern lies in economic insecurity and tend to see immigrants as its fundamental source. They are framed as unfair competitors in the job market and illegitimate recipients of Italian public welfare.

d. *Disengaged Moderates* generally include refugees within their social group, showcasing compassion and empathy. Their uncertain and disengaged position is rather anchored in their personal situation and experience.

Furthermore, a unique fact within Italian public opinion contrasting with other European countries is the connection some segments tie between immigration and public health threat. *Hostile Nationalists* (78%) and *Security Concerned* (72%) reflect this kind of concern in their opinions, holding immigrants responsible for the introduction and/or proliferation of some disease.

In addition, part of the *movable middle* of the continuum and its *closed segments*, altogether voice concerns towards newcomers' intention to respect Italian laws and cultural values, doubting their willingness to integrate (with a tendency to confuse integration with assimilation). On the other side of the spectrum, the *open groups* see immigrants as just trying to find their place in society, and *Disengaged Moderates* blame integration struggles on systemic inadequacies. In fact, positive and welcoming attitudes towards immigrants sharply increase among all segments when the newcomers prove their desire to accept and respect Italian culture and traditions.

Generally, all segments generally support the right to asylum, but some are suspicious when refugees are perceived as economic migrants. Italy's administrative capacity to handle asylum applications and integrate immigrants is still doubted by many, especially within the *Neglected* and *Security Concerned*. Anyhow, all segments agree that within the welfare state, unaccompanied minors should hold the priority, with almost everyone repudiating children repatriation.

Remarkably, most Italians worry about growing racist and discriminatory attitudes rooted in the increasing anti-immigration sentiment. Only *Hostile Nationalists* do not have such discomfort concerning the direction national debate is taking.

Lastly, according to various recent research, among the Z generation (the youths born between the late 1990s and 2010s) young women are significantly more progressive and liberal on several topics – such as “race”, migration, sexuality, and gender - face to male peers. This gap, in line with some other nation's trends, reaches as high as 30% (Ricci, M., 2019; Change Research, 2023; Leda Kenny, B. (2024).

Regardless of Italy's unique features, about 50% of the Italian population in the intermediate groups lines up with findings in France, Germany, Holland, and Greece. Similarly, this central

area is characterized by a lack of extreme or radical positions, but still, each segment conserves different prevailing priorities, values, and concerns (Dixon, T., *et al.*, 2018).

In essence, despite the widening polarization of the migration debate, the majority of the population still clings to intermediate positions rather than adopting radical pro- or anti-immigration stances. Most Europeans and Italians are uncertain about many aspects of their own or their country's life and, generally, do not hold strong opinions about the international migration debate, often preferring to stick to the "neither positive nor negative" narrative (Yudkin, D., 2018; Jeannet, A. -M., 2020).

CHAPTER 2: THE MESSENGER EFFECT

This chapter delves into the theoretical foundations of the *Messenger Effect* and its relevance to shaping attitudes toward migration. It aims to bridge existing theories and studies with the research's hypotheses, providing a comprehensive framework for analyzing whether and how different messengers influence public attitudes on immigration.

The chapter is organized into four sections. The first section (*2.1 Theoretical Framework: How Attitudes Are Formed and Transformed*), establishes the theoretical basis for understanding how attitudes are developed and changed. The second section (*2.2 Literature Review: Messenger's Role and Characteristics in the Shaping of Public Attitudes*), reviews existing research on the role and attributes of messengers in shaping public opinion. In the third (*2.3 Research Gap on Messenger Influence in Strategic Communication Regarding Migration*), the focus shifts to identifying gaps in current research and the need for further investigation into how messengers affect strategic communication about migration. Finally, the fourth (*2.4 Hypothesis and Expected Outcomes: Evaluating the Impact of Messengers in Shaping Public Attitudes on Migration*) presents the hypotheses and anticipated results, assessing the influence of messengers on public attitudes toward migration.

2.1 Theoretical Framework: How Attitudes Are Formed and Transformed

Within the migration domain, public opinion is undoubtedly one crucial factor influencing policymaking. People's perceptions, misperceptions, and feelings about migrants and immigration hold the power to shape a country's approach to various national and international policies like border control, repressions, and countermeasures on human trafficking. They further mold the definition and implementation of asylum rules and integration policies, while setting cooperation agreements with third countries to control migrant flows.

Therefore, understanding the formation, functioning, and influences of public attitudes toward migration is essential to grasp a nation's future direction broadly. This knowledge is vital for policymakers, community leaders, and advocates, as they strive to balance the increasing concerns of residents with the rights and needs of migrants, aspiring for policies that are fair and beneficial to all members of society.

Countries and individual citizens vary widely in their views about immigration and immigrants but as revealed in the previous chapter, the current trends of migration attitudes may be resumed as follows:

- ❖ Contrary to popular belief, attitudes towards migration in Europe are not becoming more negative. Rather, they are notably stable, and, in recent years, anti-immigrant sentiments have overall decreased, making room for more positive feelings.
- ❖ Unlike preferences about immigration, what is rather volatile is the perceived importance of the issue of immigration, which has indeed risen sharply across the continent, dominating last national and European election discourses in 2019. In this context, citizens who are most concerned about immigration's legacies are more likely to vote for anti-immigration parties, aligning with their anti-immigration sentiments.
- ❖ What emerges unambiguously is that Europeans everywhere want immigrants who can and are willing to assimilate socially, accepting and respecting national religions and traditions. They prefer professionals and highly qualified (so-called wanted migrants).
- ❖ Lastly Europeans increasingly associate the EU with insufficient control at external borders. Simultaneously, major Southern host countries grapple with persistently critical domestic attitudes towards the hosted displaced populations, increasingly blaming the Union for the perceived poor help offered amid the current "migration crisis" (Eagly, A. H. & Chaiken, S., 1998; Dennison, J., & Dražanová, L., 2018; Dennison, J., & Vrânceanu, A., 2022).

In social sciences, an increasing number of studies on these attitudes are being conducted.

Starting from the groundwork, the American Psychological Association (APA) defines the attitude as "*a relatively enduring and general evaluation of an object, person, group, issue, or concept on a dimension ranging from negative to positive. Attitudes provide summary evaluations of target objects and are often assumed to be derived from specific beliefs, emotions, and past behaviors associated with those objects.*" (APA Dictionary of Psychology, 2018).

These evaluations can be explicit (and conscious), reflecting deliberate thoughts and feelings towards a subject that individuals can easily self-report. Conversely, implicit attitudes operate at a subconscious level. They are automatic and involuntary sentiments to a topic, not immediately or consciously accessible. As such, they include information that people are either unwilling to report or not aware of and therefore unable to report. (Haddock, G. & Maio, G. R., 2004; Sherman, J. W. & Klein, S. A. W., 2021).

The ABC model, a framework in psychology, describes the three main components of attitudes: affective, cognitive, and behavioral. The Affective Component involves a person's feelings and emotions about an object or an issue. This element includes feelings or emotional responses like liking, disliking, love, hate, fear, etc. The Cognitive Component describes, instead, the mental aspects of people's response toward different stimuli, including understanding and interpreting information, based on personal knowledge and beliefs. In other words, it encompasses thoughts and attributes that an individual associates with an object, person, issue, or

situation. Lastly, the Behavioral Component refers to how individuals behave or act toward an object, person, issue, or situation, based on their attitude. It involves people's tendency to behave in a certain way toward the attitude object.

To exemplify, suppose someone holds some concerns towards immigrants (*affective component*). In that case, they might avoid areas or communities where immigrants are known to reside (*behavioral component*), due to their belief that immigrants pose a threat to their own and their family's safety (*cognitive component*).

According to the principle of consistency, there is a general expectation for people's behaviors to be consistent with their attitudes. Nonetheless, in reality, individuals do not always adhere to this principle, sometimes exhibiting seemingly illogical behaviors. Indeed, behaviors are not always a straightforward reflection of the cognitive and affective components. For example, someone might express strong support for immigration, recognizing the economic benefits and cultural enrichment it brings to their country. Yet, they may simultaneously resist the idea of immigrants moving into their neighborhood or their children attending the same school as immigrant children, due to unfounded fears or ingrained biases. This discrepancy would then likely bring a mismatch between the cognitive components and the actual behaviors toward immigrants. (Rosenberg, M. J. *et al.* 1960; Eagly, A., & Chaiken, S., 1998).

In sum, attitudes are cognitive schemas that provide a structure to organize complex or ambiguous information, guiding particular evaluations or behaviors (Bohner, G.; Wanke, M., 2011). More specifically, Daniel Katz writes that attitudes serve people's inner psychological needs: expressive or symbolic functions (affirming values), maintaining social identity, and regulating emotions. According to the Utilitarian function, attitudes are formed based on the perceived rewards or punishments associated with a specific action or belief. For instance, a community member may advocate for more open immigration policies after witnessing how the influx of skilled immigrants has led to job creation and innovation within the local economy. This individual's support for immigration is reinforced by the tangible benefits of economic growth and diversity, showcasing a positive attitude towards immigration that aligns with their self-interest in fostering a prosperous community (Katz, D., 1960). Secondly, the knowledge function, closely tied to the cognitive component of attitudes, organizes and interprets new information. People achieve this goal by making things fit together and make sense, in order to maintain a sense of stability and meaning within their worldview. For example, an individual believes that migrants contribute to cultural diversity and enrich society. Upon learning about a multicultural festival organized by migrants that was well-received by the community, he or she interprets this as further proof of the positive impact of migration, reinforcing their supportive attitude towards migrants (Fabrigar, L. R. *et al.*, 2006). Thirdly, the Ego-defensive need acts in order to

protect self-esteem. When individuals face situations that might challenge their self-esteem or force them to confront uncomfortable truths about themselves, they may adopt certain attitudes or beliefs that help to mitigate this threat (including denial, repression, projection, and rationalization). This theory posits that when people feel threatened by their circumstances or self-perception, they may seek out comparisons that make them feel better about their situation. For example, a person who fears that they might not be competitive in the job market, to feel some relief about his or her own situation, he or she may project this fear onto migrants, accusing them of being the cause of job scarcity, even when the economy might be in fact suffering from broader issues (Hewstone, M., 2003; Graham, J., *et al.* 2013). Lastly, the Value-expressive function serves the need to establish identity and social approval. It allows individuals to communicate who they are and what they stand for through their attitudes towards various issues. Attitudes formed through the value-expressive function are deeply rooted in people's self-concept and moral principles, often leading to strong and emotionally charged positions on issues. An individual who places a high value on compassion and empathy might express strong support for open immigration policies, refugee assistance, and safeguarding of everyone's human rights, seeing these positions as reflections of their humanitarian beliefs (Katz, D., 1960). The author spotlights that these functions embody the key elements to ponder when trying to change attitudes. Indeed, according to the study, the communication should be strategically targeted to the specific need the attitude addresses to be truly effective (see paragraphs below) (Bohner, G., & Wanke, M., 2011).

2.1.1 Factors influencing the formation and transformation of attitudes in the context of migration

After breaking down the components and functions of attitudes, it is crucial to examine the factors that influence the formation and transformation of attitudes, particularly in the context of migration. The main existing theoretical frameworks for the development of attitudes have been categorized as follows:

Influence of Media and Politics (*Framing Theory*): Numerous studies have shown that media plays a pivotal role in shaping perceptions of migration through the framing of migration stories, the portrayal of migrants, and the dissemination of information or misinformation. Indeed, there is evidence that negative stories provoke a threat perception, whilst stories emphasizing humanitarian plight led to increased support for immigrants and perhaps more permissive policies. Furthermore, the impact of *social* media and selective exposure to media content can either amplify negative stereotypes or foster empathy and support. In fact, research has found that the impact of media on people's attitudes lessens when an issue starts to matter more to them. As people become more familiar and concerned with a topic, their opinions on it tend to

solidify. At this point, these attitudes become deeply embedded in the individual's belief system, making them less susceptible to the shaping of media influence. Essentially, the more salient and personally relevant an issue becomes, the less likely it is that media coverage will sway an individual's opinion on it. (Entman, R. M., 1993; Suro, R., 2005). Moreover, other studies deem political discourse and the positions of political parties on migration to be significantly affecting public attitudes. As highlighted in the first chapter, populist movements often leverage migration issues to gain support, framing migrants as a threat to societal well-being. Conversely, policies promoting integration and the positive contributions of migrants can alternatively influence public perceptions positively (Hainmueller, J., & Hiscox, M. J., 2007). In essence, in the context of migration, the *Framing Theory* thus examines how the media, politicians, and other actors present information about migration and migrants. Frames that emphasize threat, competition, or illegality can exacerbate negative attitudes, while those highlighting humanitarian issues, contributions of migrants, and shared values can promote positive sentiments (Entman, R. M., 1993).

Economic Competition effect: According to this group of explanations, public opinions are often shaped by the perceived economic impacts of migration, including job competition, wage depression, and the strain or contributions to public welfare systems. The "labor market competition" hypothesis suggests that locals may fear losing jobs to migrants willing to work for lower wages. Pessimism about the national economy along with actual national economic recessions and rising unemployment rates increases negative sentiments and preference for more high-skilled labor migrants (see segments of the Italian population pp. 13). Numerous scholars found that higher unemployment rates in European countries were related to lower anti-immigrant preferences at the individual level (Rustenbach, E., 2010; Markaki, Y., & Longhi, S., 2013). On the other hand, research points out that economic considerations play a significant role in fostering positive attitudes towards migrants too. Specifically, these positive perceptions are often tied to the practical benefits that migrants bring to a country. For example, migrants are acknowledged for filling gaps in the labor market, for bringing fresh ideas and perspectives, or for their support in sustaining the workforce and contributing to social security systems in countries with an aging population (Borjas, G. J., 1994). Either way, evidence shows that personal economic circumstances (being rich versus being poor) do not matter, as attitudes are rather shaped by concerns about the country or the community as a whole, and less by self-interested concerns about personal economic situations (Dustmann, C., & Frattini, T., 2014).

Other authors further consider historical, demographic, cultural, and social factors.

Historical factors: scholars deem historical relations between countries, including colonial ties and past migrations, to potentially influence contemporary attitudes toward migrants. Additionally, historical experiences of migration and integration are believed to further mold societal norms and policies toward new migrants (Castles, S., & Miller, M. J., 2009).

Impact of demographic characteristics: demographic traits of both the native population and migrants, such as age, education level, and urban versus rural residence, are considered to be influencing perceptions of migration. Younger, more educated, and urban populations tend to have more positive attitudes towards migration. On the other hand, demographic factors such as the education and skill levels of incoming migrants play a significant role too in shaping public perception. Highly educated and skilled migrants are typically classified as “wanted migrants”, eliciting far more positive sentiments compared to those with lower education and skill levels. Additionally, when considering the demography of the incoming population in terms of quantity, it has been proven that the number of migrants *per se* does not have any influence on migration attitudes. It is rather the *understanding* of the number of immigrant inflows that plays the most determinant role in the shaping of both attitudes and salience of the migration discourse (see previous chapter) (Hainmueller, J., & Hiscox, M. J., 2010).

Social and cultural factors: social roles, relating to how people are expected to behave in a particular role or context, and social norms, involving society’s rules for what behaviors are considered appropriate, can have a strong influence on attitudes. Indeed, cultural and social factors, including ideologies and values, concerns over national identity, cultural preservation, and the ability of migrants to integrate into host societies are demonstrated to significantly impact public attitudes on migration (see segments in the first chapter) (Allport, G. W., 1954; Hainmueller, J., & Hopkins, D. J., 2014). Some scholars concluded that “*not fitting in culturally, evokes significantly more opposition to immigration than not fitting in economically, while fitting in culturally promotes significantly more support for it than fitting in economically*” (Sniderman, P. M., *et al.* 2004).

Early life socialization effects (Social Identity Theory): According to this perspective, certain types of early life socialization processes can lead to latent political values, which then can be activated by political exposure and events. Peer group, family, area of origin, and education (as the level of education reached and how many years spent in education) are proven to be powerful predictors of any kind of immigration attitude. Some studies also demonstrate that a person’s formative political climate - or, in other words, the political zeitgeist during their youth - explains their attitudes towards immigration later in life. The exposure to varying levels of certain political principles in the political climate during a person’s youth, for instance, either

equality or tradition, has respectively pro- or anti-immigration effects on his or her attitudes in adulthood (Jeannet, A. M., & Dražanová, L. 2023). Indeed, according to *Social Identity Theory*, individuals derive part of their identity from the social groups to which they belong, leading to in-group favoritism and out-group prejudice. Attitudes towards migrants can change through processes that redefine in-group boundaries or promote identification with a larger group that includes both migrants and natives (Tajfel, H., & Turner, J.C., 1979). These early life socialization effects, contrary to later life effects - like jobs, contact with immigrants, media, and political cues - are considered to have more long-lasting impacts (Jeannet, A. M., & Dražanová, L., 2023).

Psychological factors: psychological explanations for attitudes toward immigration often highlight the role of individual differences, such as personality traits, values, and personal identity. These elements are claimed to be the strongest predictors of an individual's stance on immigration. The value of universalism, for example, emphasizes tolerance and protection of all people's rights leading toward pro-immigrant positions; whilst the desire for conformity, tradition, and security focuses rather on maintaining the community safe and stable, thus viewing immigrants negatively and as a threat (Graham, J., *et al.* 2013). Again, people who are more open to new experiences might be more welcoming of different cultures and thus hold more positive views on immigration. Conversely, those who identify strongly with their national or cultural group may feel threatened by outsiders and therefore have more negative attitudes toward immigrants (Dennison, J., & Dražanová, L., 2018). Some research further explores the impact of other psychological processes on migration attitudes, such as the *Mere-Exposure Effect*. They posit that the constant and protracted exposure to the "attitude objects" may affect how a person forms his or her opinion. Zajonc showed that people were more likely to have a positive attitude on topics or things when they were exposed to them frequently than if they were not. Mere repeated exposure of the individual to a stimulus thus proves to be a sufficient condition for the enhancement of his attitude toward it (Zajonc, R. B., 1968; Pettigrew, T. F., & Tropp, L. R., 2006).

Biological factors (*Consistency Theory*): some authors argue that although attitudes constitute some function of social forces, they also represent neurological systems and biological processes. Once instantiated, they would take on a life of their own and update the cognitive, emotive, psychological, and neurobiological processes humans use to self-select into environments, and perceive, view, and evaluate their social world. In this view, according to *Consistency Theory*, it is not that an individual is born with a fixed attitudinal disposition, but rather all those elements of the individual's psychological architecture, including perception, emotion, cogni-

tion, reasoning, affect, affiliation, and countless other attentional categories, are to varying degrees a function of inherited and developed biological mechanisms. These mechanisms play an important role in the probabilities of self-selecting, experiencing, interpreting, and responding to social experiences (Hatemi, P. K., & McDermott, R., 2016).

These studies and theories aim to explain how people's attitudes toward migration are formed and shaped by diverse factors. To fully understand attitudes' complexity, the analysis will continue by exploring the aspects that potentially influence the transformation and change of public sentiments towards migration.

2.1.2 Theoretical perspectives on attitude change

In the classical definitions an attitude, once formed is rather persistent, while in more contemporary conceptualizations, attitudes are found to be varying depending upon new experiences, different situations, moods, or information, and several other factors (Bohner, G. & Wanke, M., 2011). Hence, according to most recent research, attitudes are not invariably fixed entities but may be subjected to change during an individual's lifetime.

To understand how and why attitudes change, several theories have been proposed.

Firstly, the Learning Theory contributes to the scholarly discussion on the mechanisms of attitude change. Accordingly, processes like classical conditioning, operant conditioning, and observational learning can be used to generate attitude switching. The first one creates positive emotional reactions to an object, person, or event by associating positive feelings with the target object. Imagine a series of social media campaigns or television advertisements showcasing heartwarming stories of immigrants. Each story highlights migrants from various backgrounds contributing positively to their communities - be it a doctor working tirelessly during a health crisis, a young immigrant student winning a national science fair, or a family of immigrants starting a successful local business that becomes beloved in the neighborhood. The repeated exposure to these positive narratives and emotions may gradually influence public attitudes, making people more receptive and supportive of immigration policies and cultural diversity. This approach leverages the principle of classical conditioning by pairing the concept of immigration (which may be neutral or even negative to some at the outset) with positive emotions and outcomes, thereby fostering more positive attitudes towards immigrants and the idea of welcoming them into communities. Further, operant conditioning can be used to strengthen desirable attitudes and weaken undesirable ones. Imagine a young man who initially views immigration skeptically, echoing sentiments he's heard in his community. However, after volunteering at a local center helping immigrants, he receives heartfelt thanks and sees the direct

positive impact of her work. This appreciation acts as positive reinforcement, gradually changing his perspective. Observing immigrants' contributions and resilience, coupled with the community's positive feedback on his efforts, the boy's attitude shifts to a supportive stance on immigration. Lastly, observational learning develops as individuals learn and adopt behaviors or attitudes by watching others, particularly those they admire or consider as role models. This process is especially powerful when the observed individuals are authority figures or important people to the observer. This could be a child observing a parent, a student watching a teacher, or a fan imitating a public figure (Bowleg L., 2009; Chaiklin, H., 2011).

In the second place, the Compliance Theory refers to a change in behavior based on consequences, such as an individual's hopes to gain rewards or avoid punishment from another group or person. The individual does not necessarily experience changes in beliefs or evaluations of an attitude object but rather is influenced by the social outcomes of adopting a behavior change (Kelman, H.C., 1958).

Third, the Internalization Theory refers to the change in beliefs when one finds the content of the attitude to be intrinsically rewarding. Through exposure to new information, someone might change their stance on social or political issues because the new perspective aligns with their underlying values about justice, equality, or freedom. Internalization represents the most profound level of attitude change because it integrates new information or behaviors into the individual's pre-existing values and belief system. However, as a consequence of the *Cognitive Dissonance* and *Confirmation Bias* processes, Internalization theory may incur some path distortions. According to the above-mentioned theories, people tend to self-expose or to pay more attention to information consistent with their value system and their beliefs in order to reduce psychological discomfort. Indeed, the latter motivates people to reduce the dissonance between contrasting beliefs by changing either attitudes or behaviors, to make them more consistent with each other. These findings suggest that individuals tend to ignore information that conflicts with their existing beliefs and selectively interpret new data in a way that supports their established views of the world. For instance, someone might maintain that the number of immigrants entering the country is "still too high", even if the actual figures and the new information presented don't support this claim. These behaviors create a self-sustaining loop where beliefs are continuously reinforced, making it challenging to change deeply held attitudes or behaviors (Deci, E.L., & Ryan, R.M., 1985).

As anticipated above, the fourth theory refers to the attitudes' functions and needs. Some scholars suggest that for attitudes to change (e.g., via persuasion), appeals must be made to the function(s) that a particular attitude serves for the individual. For instance, the ego-defensive function can play a role in shifting the racially biased views of someone who believes they are

open-minded and tolerant. By targeting and reinforcing their self-perception as tolerant and open-minded, it is possible to encourage changes in their prejudicial attitudes so that these views align more closely with their self-image (Lapinski, M. K.; Boster, F. J., 2001).

In the fifth place, the Elaboration Likelihood Model outlines that people can change their attitudes through two primary routes. The first entails that individuals may become motivated to actively engage with and contemplate the mere content of the message, which can subsequently lead to a change in their attitudes. According to the second path, people might be influenced by the characteristics of the speaker, leading to a temporary or surface shift in attitude. The first central route involves a high level of cognitive engagement, where the audience carefully and thoughtfully considers the arguments and evidence presented in a persuasive message. This route is more likely to be followed when the individual is motivated and has the ability to process the message. For instance, when the topic is of personal relevance or when the individual has a high need for cognition. On the other hand, the peripheral route involves a lower level of cognitive engagement, where persuasion is based on superficial cues rather than the strength of the arguments. These cues can include the attractiveness or credibility of the speaker, emotional appeals, or the number of arguments presented rather than their quality. This route is more likely to be followed when the individual is either not motivated to process the message deeply or lacks the ability to do so. (Petty, R.E., & Cacioppo, J.T., 1986; Petty, R.E., & Wegener, D.T., 1999).

On the sixth level, Identification Theory explains individuals' change of beliefs in order to be similar to someone they admire or like. In this case, in line with the observational learning cited before, the individual adopts the new attitude, not due to the specific content of the attitude object, but because it is associated with the desired relationship. This concept is crucial in understanding how social influence works, especially in the domains of family dynamics, peer influence, and even media effects. Often, children's attitudes on *race* or their political party affiliations are adopted from their parents' attitudes and beliefs, not through a detailed understanding of these positions but because they see them as integral to their relationship with their parents. Or else, adolescents might adopt certain fashion trends, slang, or even attitudes toward migrants based on the preferences of their peer group, driven by a desire to fit in or be accepted. Again, individuals might embrace certain beliefs, lifestyle choices, or attitudes because they are associated with celebrities or public figures they admire, even in the absence of a direct relationship (Bandura, A., 1977). Unlike processes that involve careful consideration of infor-

mation, identification involves adopting attitudes or behaviors primarily because they are associated with a significant or admired other, rather than due to the intrinsic merits of the attitudes or behaviors themselves (Tajfel, H., & Turner, J.C. 1979).

In essence, public attitudes toward migration are influenced by a complex array of psychological, biological, social, and economic factors. This section explored the multifaceted nature of these attitudes and various theories that explain how they are formed and evolve. Recent research suggests that these attitudes are indeed dynamic, responding to influences such as media portrayals, personal experiences, new information, and reactions to different messengers. Scientifically, understanding what strategic communication works for changing opinions, perceptions, and the popularity of narratives on migration, immediately elicits questions of causality and lends support to or undermines various and, sometimes, competing social scientific theories of how attitudes are formed and, more broadly, why humans vary in what they think and believe, as outlined in the previous paragraph (Hainmueller, J., & Hopkins, D. J., 2014).

Specifically, this paragraph has delved into the key theories related to changes in attitudes and identifies several factors that can drive these changes. These factors include the expected social benefits that come from changing one's behavior, the specific content of the message - particularly if it is seen as beneficial or aligns with personal values - and the various functions that attitudes serve. Additionally, also the credibility and characteristics of those who deliver these messages appear to significantly impact the possibility of influencing or modifying people's behaviors. These elements collectively elucidate the mechanisms by which attitudes toward specific issues such as migration may change and evolve.

2.2 Literature Review: Messenger's Role and Characteristics in the Shaping of Public Attitudes

Since migration has stepped into the political arena, becoming one of the most salient and relevant issues, influencing public attitudes towards it has become a crucial strategy. At one pole, left-wing parties typically promote policies and practices that support immigration, including local integration efforts to national immigration policies, striving to cultivate positive or at least neutral feelings, to foster social cohesion and prevent conflicts. On the other pole, right-wing parties often outline security and cultural concerns related to migration issues, allying with public fear and depicting migrants as a potential threat.

In this polarized context, strategic communication consists of carefully planned messages and campaigns aimed at multiple goals, including informing, publicizing, gathering information, or shaping public opinion and attitudes toward migrants and immigration. A significant contemporary challenge for numerous international organizations, governments, and non-governmental organizations is using

strategic communication to counteract polarizing, misleading, and inflammatory narratives that can destabilize legal and rights-based migration systems, thus amplifying the potential costs and diminishing the benefits of migration (Dennison, J., & Dražanová, L., 2018). Drawing on previously discussed theories, numerous strategies and communication campaigns about migration have been developed and implemented. Academic research is still in the process of defining and scientifically proving which communication strategies are most effective at positively influencing public attitudes toward migration, trying to grasp the critical factors of message effectiveness.

Within the realm of NGOs, particular emphasis is placed on the role of the messenger, whose influence is broadly acknowledged. Accordingly, theories such as Identification Theory, Elaboration Likelihood Model, and Learning Theory provide a framework for analyzing the effectiveness of messengers. As many grassroots and civil organizations claim, a well-crafted message may fall flat if not delivered by a credible and relatable figure. Thus, the messenger turns out to be as important as the message. Practitioners and researchers begin to agree that communicating strategically means carefully selecting authentic, trusted, and relatable messengers who can speak to the target audience in their own words and language. They claim that a messenger's credibility, relatability, and authority each play a crucial role in how their message is received and can significantly influence public attitudes and behaviors toward migration. The strategic selection of messengers, therefore, is paramount in efforts to change or shape public opinion on this complex issue (Dennison, J., 2020).

This section aims, thus, to line up and intersect the existing literature surrounding the different messengers' influence and characteristics and the up-to-date studies on successful strategic messaging strategies, spotting the potential gaps in the research.

One first set of studies focuses on the main characteristics that make messengers either effective or ineffective in shaping public attitudes. Several scholars deem the influence of the messenger to be significantly shaped by three key attributes: credibility, relatability, and authority. These attributes affect how messages are received by the public, which in turn can alter attitudes and behaviors towards migrants (Hovland, C. I. *et al.* 1953; Mills, J., & Aronson, E., 1965; Miller, G. R., & Burgoon, M., 1978).

Firsthand, credibility appears to be rooted in the messenger's trustworthiness and expertise. Imagine an individual reading about the economic impacts of migration. Suppose this person believes the information comes from a respected academic institution or a well-regarded international organization specializing in migration studies. In that case, they may be more inclined to trust and be persuaded by the findings. The perceived expertise and trustworthiness of these sources lend credibility to the data presented, influencing the reader to accept the positive role of migrants in economic growth. Conversely, if the same information appears to come from a general news blog or a less specialized media

outlet, the reader may question the accuracy and depth of the analysis. The lack of recognition or established trust can lead the audience to either dismiss the message or not engage with it deeply. In this scenario, the credibility of the source directly impacts how the message on migration is received and trusted. Some psychologists have further debated whether this is a long-lasting effect and Hovland and Weiss (1951) found the effect of telling people that a message came from a credible source disappeared after several weeks (the so-called sleeper effect). However, if people are informed of the source of a message before hearing it, there is proved to be less likelihood of a sleeper effect than if they are told a message and then told its source (Pornpitakpan, C., 2004).

Relatability pertains instead to the audience's ability to see themselves in the messenger or their message, seeing them as similar or likable in some way. The Social Identity Theory provides the theoretical framework for understanding this. Developed by Henri Tajfel and John Turner, SIT suggests that people categorize themselves and others into various social groups (such as nationality, ethnicity, or religion). These categories influence their self-image and behavior towards members of other groups. Messengers who can bridge these categorizations by highlighting shared identities or experiences can reduce perceived differences. This connection is based on the concept of "in-groups" (us) and "out-groups" (them), where messages from in-group members are more favorably received due to perceived similarity and shared identity. For example, a Catholic priest could be a powerful and relatable messenger, particularly for audiences in communities where the church plays a significant role in daily life and cultural identity. As spiritual guidance, religious figures oftentimes hold a position of ethical authority and expertise. Their role typically involves lecturing about kindness, thoughtfulness, and the intrinsic Christian duty to welcome people in need, consequently putting migrants under a positive moral frame, which can easily reverberate with religious people. Their longstanding nearness and reliable engagement in neighborhood issues, often make religious leaders trusted and recognizable figures, holding a great influence over community members' attitudes on critical ethical discourses like migration. (Tajfel, H., & Turner, J. C., 2004; Verschueren, J., 2008; Tufte, T., 2017). Authority further entails the messenger's position and perceived legitimacy. It stems from its power and conferred entitlement to be respected and listened to, hence directly influencing the audience's obedience and compliance. In his 1963 seminal work, Milgram found evidence of the powerful influence of authority on human behavior and the tendency for individuals to comply with instructions deployed by who they perceive to be legitimate authority figures, even when these commands entail causing harm to other people. Indeed, despite the discomfort and ethical concerns, many participants in the experiment continued to administer electrical shocks when asked to do so by the authorities. Socialization processes considerably contribute to individuals' tendency to adhere to rules and obey authority, such as instructors, and police officers. From early childhood, societal norms and cultural

education instill a sense of respect for authorities, fostering a general inclination to comply with directives even in the absence of explicit coercion. Within the realm of strategic communication, authority refers thus to the messenger's social position, institutional role, or specialized knowledge. For instance, policymakers or law enforcement authorities often wield a certain degree of authority, lending credibility and influence on the message they deliver (Milgram, S., 1963; Meyer, P., 1988). As mentioned above, the effectiveness of authority in communication depends on the audience's perception of the messenger's legitimacy and power rather than on their real authority. According to French and Raven (1959), there are different bases of power, including expert power, and legitimate power. Expert power is derived from having superior knowledge or expertise in the subject matter, which can make communications more persuasive. Legitimate power, however, comes from the formal authority to control and use resources based on one's position in an organization or society (French & Raven, 1959).

In sum, the above-cited scholars have outlined three key characteristics essential for messengers to effectively communicate about migration: credibility, relatability, and authority. Hovland, Janis, and Kelley's (1953) work on communication and persuasion underscores the crucial role these factors play in influencing how messages are received and acted upon. This research underscores how different types of messengers - such as politicians, figures, and community leaders - can impact the effectiveness of their communication based on these attributes.

Building on this foundation, some scholars have delved deeper into exploring different categories of messengers.

According to some research, media figures, including journalists and television hosts, are among the most effective message deliverers, playing a pivotal role in framing the migration debate. Their influence is tied to their ability to reach wide audiences and shape the narrative around migration issues. Entman's (2007) framing theory illustrates how media can influence public perception by highlighting certain aspects of migration while omitting others, thus guiding the audience's understanding and attitudes.

Additionally, community leaders, such as religious figures and local activists, have a unique capacity to influence through their close connections and trust within communities, based on their potential relatability, authority, and credibility attributes. They are indeed, simultaneously "in-group" members, perceived as powerful and legitimate within the community and trustworthy for these very reasons. Hence, as outlined in the previous paragraph, they often serve as bridges between migrants and host communities, facilitating understanding and integration (Strawser, C., 2021).

Migrants can be powerful messengers as well, sharing personal stories that humanize the migration experience and counteract stereotypes, making the whole message more relatable. The credibility and relatability of their firsthand accounts can challenge misconceptions and foster empathy among the

host population. Collett and Petrovic's (2014) research on migrant narratives emphasizes the impact of personal stories in changing attitudes, highlighting the importance of giving migrants a platform to share their experiences (Tajfel, H., & Turner, J. C., 2004; Verschuere, J., 2008; Tufte, T., 2017).

Lastly, politicians wield considerable influence over public opinion on migration too. They ply authority (actual and oftentimes perceived) and credibility. These attributes are oftentimes unconditionally supported by their in-group members, such as party loyalists who view them as reliable and knowledgeable figures. This partisan backing significantly amplifies the impact of their statements, profoundly shaping public attitudes. Their statements can sway public attitudes significantly, as seen in studies like Eshbaugh-Soha's (2010) analysis of presidential speeches in the United States, which shows that presidential rhetoric on immigration did strongly shape public opinion and policy agenda. Additionally, as presented in the previous chapter, an analysis conducted by Alto Analytics before the EU elections (2019) on Twitter in Italy, evidenced similar results. 0.1% of users (almost exclusively right-wing politicians) were responsible for producing 10% of the content, highlighting their significant role in molding the migration narrative.

A third group of studies further explores the mechanisms and theories explaining why messengers are either effective or ineffective in shaping public attitudes toward migration.

On the first floor, Druckman (2001) and Lupia (1994) scientifically prove that when a political figure endorses a message, the endorsement can significantly affect how the message is received by the public, depending on the audience's prior attitudes toward the figure. Intuitively, supporters of the politician might be more receptive to the message, while detractors might discount the message or react against it due, focusing on its source derogation rather than on the very message content.

In line with the previous scholars, *Social Identity Theory* further demonstrates that messages from in-group members (e.g., a politician from the same political party as the audience) are factually more persuasive than messages from out-group members. The *In-group Bias* can be amplified or mitigated depending on the specific context and how strongly the audience identifies with the group (Turner, J. C., et al. 1979). Moreover, *Social Norms theory* posits that people's behavior is influenced by their perceptions of what is normal or acceptable within their social group. Influential messengers, such as celebrities, politicians, or social media influencers, can set or change social norms and standards around migration by publicly voicing their opinions, thereby shaping public attitudes.

Some other studies further investigate the so-called *Partisan Cueing Effect*, namely how the political affiliation of the source (e.g., a known politician, or a famous activist) influences acceptance of the message, showing that individuals are more likely to agree with statements if they believe these statements come from a politician or party with which they identify (Nicholson, S. P. , 2011; Brader, T., et al. 2020)

In addition, the *Halo Effect* is identified as a cognitive bias where our overall impression of a person influences how we feel and think about their character and capabilities in other areas. This phenomenon helps further explain why certain messengers might be more or less effective: if we have a favorable overall impression of a person, we are likely to view their capabilities and messages more positively, and vice versa. This psychological mechanism means that if we perceive someone positively in one aspect, we are likely to have a favorable view of them in other aspects, even if unrelated. For example, if a Nobel Prize-winning economist argues that migration has positive effects on the economy, their renowned expertise and positive reputation in economics create a *halo* that extends to their statements about migration. People who respect this economist for his or her economic insights might be more inclined to accept his or her views on migration, even if they previously held no strong opinions or were skeptical about the economic contributions of migrants (Nisbett, R. E., Wilson T. D., 1977; Dean J., 2007).

Furthermore, Ray's (2003) study focuses on the emotional connection between the audience and the message deliverer. Messengers who can evoke strong emotions - whether through charisma, personal stories, or expressive delivery - are proven to impact public attitudes toward migration more profoundly.

Lastly, several authors (Kassin, S. M., 1983; Marks, J. & Martin S., 2019) found evidence of the *Messenger Effect*: a cognitive bias that influences how people assess the validity or relevance of information, focusing more on its source rather than the content itself. Often, the individual delivering the information significantly impacts how the audience perceives and interprets the message. When confronted with difficult, complex questions, people usually do not have access to all the information they need to reach a thoughtful conclusion. So, to fill in the gaps, they include any judgment about the messenger in their analysis. This process is rooted in our natural tendency to simplify decision-making by relying on heuristic cues rather than engaging in a detailed analysis of the information itself. If a messenger is perceived as trustworthy, knowledgeable, or similar to them, individuals are more likely to accept their message without rigorous scrutiny. For example, some people may trust social media posts shared by friends, family, or influencers whom users follow and interact with regularly, even if the content contradicts the leading opinions among experts. The relational bond, even if just digital, can create a sense of credibility that might not be warranted based on the content alone. Again, public figures, due to their visibility and established credibility in certain domains, wield significant influence over public opinion. When such figures share information, their followers might accept the information as valid also due to the Halo Effect above-cited, where the positive attributes of the figure (such as charisma, success, or authority) spill over into perceptions of the truthfulness or importance of the information shared.

Over the past several decades, a wealth of research has explored the pivotal role of the messenger in communication across various fields. Numerous scholars have examined what makes a messenger effective in conveying messages, pinpointing essential qualities such as credibility, relatability, and authority (Hovland, C. I., & Weiss, W., 1951; Hovland, C. I. *et al.*, 1953; French, J. R., & Raven, B., 1959; Hovland, J., 1962; Milgram, S., 1963; Mills, J., & Aronson, E., 1965; Miller, G. R. & Burgoon, M., 1978; Meyer, P., 1988; Pornpitakpan, C. 2004; Tajfel, H., & Turner, J. C., 2004; Verschueren, J., 2008; Tufte, T., 2017). Additionally, other researchers have focused on the impact of different types of messengers, such as media figures, community leaders, migrants, and politicians, in shaping discussions about migration. Notable contributions in this area include studies by Entman, R. M., 2007; Eshbaugh-Soha, M., 2010; Collett, E., & Petrovic, M., 2014; Strawser, C., 2021, which collectively highlight how these varied messengers influence public perception. A third strand of research delves into the underlying mechanisms that make messengers either effective or ineffective. This includes theories from Social Identity Theory, In-group Bias, Social Norms Theory, Partisan Cueing, and the Halo and Messenger Effects (Richard E. N., Timothy D. W., 1977; Turner, J. C., *et al.*, 1979; Kassin, S. M., 1983; Lupia, A., 1994; Druckman, J. N., 2001; Ray, L., 2003; Jeremy D., 2007; Nicholson, S. P., 2011; Marks, J., & Martin S., 2019; Brader, T., *et al.*, 2020).

Collectively, these studies underscore a critical consensus: the messenger is just as vital as the message itself in strategic communication. This extensive body of research reaffirms the substantial impact and importance of the messenger in effectively shaping public discourse.

2.3 Research Gap on Messenger Influence in Strategic Communication Regarding Migration

Despite extensive research on the characteristics of messengers and their role in shaping public opinion, there remains a notable gap in practical research within strategic communication research. Specifically, very few studies have empirically tested whether the messenger truly makes a significant difference in real-world scenarios, such as migration campaigns.

Dennison's 2022 paper, the latest comprehensive review, analyzed 68 recent experimental social scientific studies that test the effects of different communication interventions on various forms of public attitudes to immigration. In fact, within this extensive body of research, only three experiments specifically investigated the effects of different messengers on these attitudes. In the first study by Donnelly *et al.* (2020), the authors empirically examined how public opinion shifts when different types of messengers – namely politicians, business leaders, and unions – deliver messages about migration. These messages further varied in content, focusing on different aspects such as skills, culture, or gen-

eral themes. The study mainly analyzed the impact of various types of messages on different demographic groups, categorized by age, education, and country. Specifically, regarding the messenger effect, it points out that there are no actual differences in the effects of pro-immigration messaging when delivered by politicians, unions, or businesses in Canada, Germany, and the UK.

Relatedly, Margolis (2018) further tested how religious messengers influence public opinion on migration, specifically focusing on scenarios where pro-immigrant religious leaders' positions contradict the existing conservatory preferences and norms of their group members. The results showed that a radio message with religious content from a pro-immigration American evangelical organization had a demobilizing effect on evangelical listeners, who opposed immigration. This message featured two pastors urging listeners to support immigration solutions based on Christian values. In contrast, an identical secular version, with no religious references, did not have the same impact.

The last study mentioned in the review, by Wright and Citrin (2011), concentrated on how different types of protests by the same immigrant group affect U.S. public opinion and policy attitudes toward migration. It revealed that in the US hostility to immigration protesters decreases when they are shown waving U.S. flags as opposed to Mexican ones. However, this change in perception did not translate into more moderate policy attitudes on immigration.

Hence, although theoretical research extensively discusses the qualities of messengers and their potential influence on public opinion, there is only a limited number of empirical studies that test these theories in practical situations, particularly in communication campaigns related to immigration. As shown by the most recent review above-cited, very little research examined actual communication efforts led by various types of messengers to see if and how they effectively change or influence public attitudes toward migration issues.

In fact, in the limited realm of "messenger research", these few cited studies did not even directly examine the specific impact of different messengers. Instead, they focused on various elements and specific aspects such as the content of the message, the target audience, and their relationships; or the impact of religious in-group biases on attitudes towards pro-immigration messages that challenge group norms; or else shifts in public perceptions based on the degree of migrants' integration. None of these studies have specifically tested hypotheses regarding the differential impact of various messengers on the same target population, questioning whether different messengers could effectively influence public attitudes toward migration or determining whether the type of messenger is critical in either changing or reinforcing public opinions (Dennison, J., 2020; Dennison, J., 2022).

This gap in empirical research limits our understanding of how significant the role of the messenger truly is in affecting public opinions and behaviors within specific campaigns. Advancing this area of research could provide valuable insights into crafting more effective communication strategies, particularly for issues as complex and multifaced as migration.

2.4 Hypothesis and Expected Outcomes. Evaluating the Impact of Messengers in Shaping Public Attitudes on Migration

Drawing from the extensive academic literature reviewed above, it is widely agreed that the messenger behind a strategic communication campaign does influence the audience's attitudes and opinions. In fact, the messenger appears to carry as much weight as the message itself. Several studies and theories such as Social Identity Theory, In-group Bias, Social Norms Theory, Partisan Cueing, and Halo and Messenger Effects highlight the key role of this figure in shaping public debate.

Still, within the migration discourse, experimental research reveals a substantial gap in the understanding of the messenger effects. Indeed, while many studies have explored different communication strategies aimed at fostering positive attitudes toward migration - including correcting information, appealing to emotions or self-interest, emphasizing common ground or diversity, and using various descriptions of migrants - there remains a lack of focus on the effects of specific messengers, despite their significance in NGO and academic circles.

Hence, this research seeks to address this gap by investigating whether the identity of a messenger, when made explicit, influences attitudes toward migration. Specifically, the experiment aims to answer questions such as: Is the role of messengers influential in the shaping of opinions and attitudes? To what extent do individuals delivering a message contribute to the process?

In detail, the survey will present written statements and messages attributed to well-known politicians or public figures, explicitly naming them, which contradict their typical stances on migration. By assessing the coherence between respondents' stated positions on migration and their reactions to either the messenger or the message content, this approach intends to test the following hypotheses:

H1: The identity of the messenger influences the agreement levels of respondents on statements regarding immigration.

This hypothesis assumes that knowing who makes a statement (i.e., the messenger) can significantly alter a respondent's agreement or disagreement with the content of the stance. According to Entman's (2007) framing theory, media figures, including journalists and television hosts, are among the most effective message deliverers, playing a pivotal role in framing the migration debate. Their ability to shape public attitudes is often contingent on their perceived trustworthiness and relevance to their public, along with their capacity to reach wide audiences. When a messenger is perceived as trustworthy, knowledgeable, or similar to the audience, individuals are more likely to accept their message without rigorous scrutiny.

Similarly, politicians wield considerable influence over public opinion on migration deriving authority and credibility from their positions. This credibility is often unconditionally supported

by their party loyalists, who perceive these politicians as reliable and knowledgeable, thus predisposing them to agree with the politicians' statements on migration. Furthermore, supporters of a politician are more likely to be receptive to messages that align with their views, while detractors might discount or react against these messages, focusing on the source rather than the content (Verschueren, J., 2008; Nicholson, S. P., 2011; Collett, E., & Petrovic, M., 2014; Tufte, T., 2017; Marks, J., & Martin S., 2019; Brader, T., *et al.*, 2020; Strawser, C., 2021).

Further emphasizing the role of messengers, an analysis by Alto Analytics before the 2019 EU elections on Twitter in Italy showed that a tiny fraction of users, predominantly right-wing politicians, produced a significant portion of the content. This indicates that influential figures can disproportionately shape the public discourse on migration.

Sub-H2: Respondents will exhibit higher levels of agreement with statements on immigration if the messenger is affiliated with their own political party.

Sub-H3: Simultaneously, participants will show lower levels of agreement with messages that are perceived as coming from an out-group member.

These hypotheses, built upon theories such as Partisan Cueing, Social Identity, Halo, and Messenger effect, aim to understand how individuals' allegiance to political parties and related public figures, can shape their attitude towards different messages on migration. They assess whether people's agreements with various migration stances depend on how closely the messenger aligns with their own political identity.

In other words, the research evaluates whether party alignment serves as a cue that shapes public attitudes toward migration, with respondents focusing more on the source rather than the message itself (Dean J., 2007; Nicholson, S. P., 2011; Marks, J. & Martin S., 2019; Brader, T., *et al.* 2020). Due to the influence of social identity dynamics, individuals identify with their in-group, which can lead to bias against out-group messengers, affecting how their messages are received, regardless of their content (Turner, J. C., *et al.* 1979).

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlines the methodology employed in the study, detailing the research design and procedures used to gather and analyze data on migration attitudes. The aim is to provide a clear and systematic account of the methods used to ensure the validity and reliability of the research findings.

The chapter is structured into four sections. The first section (*3.1 Research Design, Sample Selection, and Data Collection Methods*) describes the overall research framework, including how participants were chosen and the methods used to collect data. The second section (*3.2 Description of the Survey Questionnaire*), offers a detailed account of the survey instrument used to gather information, including its design and content. In the third, (*3.3 Data Collection Process, Statistical Weights, Ethical Considerations, and Informed Consent Procedures*), the focus shifts to the practical aspects of data collection, addressing how the data was gathered, the application of statistical weights, and the ethical considerations involved, including informed consent. Finally, the fourth (*3.4 Data Analysis Methods*) explains the techniques and procedures used to analyze the collected data, ensuring a rigorous evaluation of the research questions.

3.1 Methodology: Research Design and Sample Selection

The research focuses on evaluating the effects and impact of the messenger — the individual who conveys messages and leads informational campaigns — on Italian public attitudes regarding migration. It specifically assesses whether the identity of a messenger, when made explicit, influences people’s agreement or disagreement with the message presented. By identifying the impact of different messengers, the research seeks to contribute to a deeper understanding of the mechanisms behind attitude formation and change in the context of migration debates.

To that end, a survey experiment has been conducted. This section will detail the research design, including the specific experimental design selected. It will further cover the sample selection process and the sampling method used.

3.1.1 Research Design

The study employs a Randomized Control Trial (RCT) to eventually investigate the impact of different messengers on public attitudes to migration. This experimental design was chosen for its strong ability to minimize bias and firmly establish causality, hence ensuring that any differences in responses can be directly attributed to the variations in the messenger’s identity. In this type of research, participants are randomly assigned to the groups, thereby generating three equivalent and comparable samples at the start of the experiment. This reduces otherwise

uncontrollable external factors that could affect the study's outcomes and increases the reliability and scientific validity of the research.

Additionally, RCT experiments employ *blinding strategies*, meaning participants do not know whether they are part of a treatment or a control group, further diminishing biases.

Essentially, this methodology envisages the splitting of the sample into two (or more) different groups: the treatment(s) and control groups. The former group of participants receives the intervention(s); whilst the latter either receives no intervention, a placebo, or a standard treatment, serving as a baseline to confront the effects of the treatment. In this specific case study, the sample is randomly assigned to three different groups, namely two Treatments and a Control Group.

At the first level, respondents of the Control Group are asked general questions about their attitudes on migration, immigrants, and the current political landscape. This first setup builds a baseline to assess participants' overall pro or anti-immigration sentiments and political affiliations. Due to the random assignment, it is possible to project the results of the control group onto the entire sample (e.g., if 40% of the control group holds anti-immigrant sentiments, then approximately 40% of the whole sample would be expected to identify as anti-immigrant). In Treatment Group 1, respondents are exposed to positive (or pro-) migration messages from an anonymous source. In Treatment Group 2, participants receive identical positive messages but from different identifiable and well-known messengers who typically identify with anti-immigrant and right-wing positions). This dual-treatment setup allows for an examination of the effects of positive messages on migration attitudes, further providing a primary parameter to measure the influence of the messenger's identity.

Indeed, the RCT design enables the direct establishment of a cause-effect relationship between the intervention and the outcomes. Specifically, by manipulating the independent variables, namely the types of messages and the messenger's identity - made explicit in Treatment 2 and omitted in Treatment 1 - and observing the effect on the dependent variable (attitudes towards migration), the design effectively isolates the influence of both dependent variable from other potential factors. In particular, the comparison between Control and Treatment 1, between Control and Treatment 2, and between Treatment 1 and Treatment 2, allows to precisely extrapolate the effects of pro-immigrant messages, the effect of both pro-immigration messages and messengers' identity combined, and the impact of messengers' identity alone, respectively. This approach, thus, ensures that any differences observed between the three groups are attributable directly to the interventions being tested.

Hence, the advantages of using a Randomized Control Trial include its ability to easily establish causality, by testing cause-effect relationships between intervention and outcomes. As

mentioned above, this methodological accuracy is achieved through randomization and blinding, which help minimize potential bias and environmental variability. It provides, indeed, a controlled environment where messengers deliver messages to randomly assigned groups ensuring that all participants are subject to the same conditions except for the variable under study. This experimental setup aligns perfectly with the research's objective to accurately assess how different messengers influence public attitudes toward migration, providing clear, actionable insights that could inform policy and communication strategies (Duflo, E., *et al.*, 2007; Glennerster, R., & Takavarasha, K., 2014; Spieth, P. M., *et al.*, 2016; Tjaden, J., & Dunsch, F. A., 2021; Gazeaud, J. *et al.*, 2023).

3.1.2 The choice of Italy as a case study

As previously mentioned, the broader population from which the sample is drawn consists of all people currently residing in Italy. This population is particularly relevant to the research due to Italy's unique migration history and its impact on contemporary society. Historically, Italy saw significant emigration, with over 30 million Italians leaving the country between the mid-nineteenth and mid-twentieth centuries. However, this trend started to reverse in the early 1970s, leading to a period of positive net migration (Castellazzi, 2010).

In recent decades, international migration has profoundly reshaped various dimensions of Italy's social fabric, introducing new cultures, religions, and beliefs. These transformations have inevitably raised concerns about economic stability, cultural identity, and security among the population, intensifying both public and political attention on the topic. Notably, the Eurobarometer survey highlights a perceptual gap where Italians significantly overestimate the proportion of migrants in the population compared to the actual figure (see previous chapters) (Eurobarometer, 2021). This heightened focus has not necessarily been driven by an increase in migration volumes but rather by shifts in public opinion and the strategic choices of political actors. Political parties and candidates, particularly in the last few decades, have made migration the theme of their electoral campaigns, significantly influencing public debates and policymaking (Jeannet, A.-M., *et al.*, 2021; Lauwers, N., *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, the migration discourse has become increasingly polarized, with a noticeable political shift towards supporting anti-immigration parties, often categorized as *radical*, *far*, or *populist* right. These parties, tap into and amplify public anxieties over the so-called "invasion of migrants", thereby further politicizing the debate (Dennison, J., & Geddes, A., 2019; Campo, F., *et al.*, 2021).

Given this context, Italian public opinion on migration presents a deeply fragmented reality, mirroring the country's national history and diverse regional identities. Indeed, Italy's

demographic diversity and experiences with migration vary significantly by region; for example, northern Italy has a higher concentration of economic migrants, while southern regions are more affected by refugee arrivals. Furthermore, as a frontline state in the European migration crisis, Italy's legal and policy frameworks are particularly relevant to migration debates. The government's policies and legal decisions directly impact migrants and the public's perception of them (Basile, L., & Borri, R., 2022).

For these reasons, the Italian population provides a critical context for studying the influence of messengers on public attitudes toward migration, shaped by historical, political, geographic, and social diversity.

3.1.3 Exploring the Rationale Behind the Sample Selection

The specific strategy employed to select the survey's respondents was convenience sampling. This method was chosen primarily for its simplicity and cost-effectiveness, essential considerations since the study received no financial support. According to this approach, respondents are selected based on their availability and willingness to participate. This selection method can expose the research to bias (e.g. self-selection) and affect its findings' generalizability, due to its potential lack of accurate representativeness of the population considered.

Despite these limitations, the specific setup of this study is designed to minimize such risks. Firstly, to address potential demographic imbalances in the sample, the questionnaire includes questions about age, gender, origin, education, and economic status. Statistical weights will be applied during the analysis to align the sample more closely to the broader population.

Another potential bias from convenience sampling is the overrepresentation of left-leaning and pro-immigrant people, who might be more inclined to participate in such studies. The study's design approach aims to neutralize any biases that might arise from the political or ideological composition of the sample. Specifically, a Control Group assesses participants' pro- or anti-immigration sentiments and political leanings. This baseline analysis captures the initial attitudes of the sample, precisely the percentage of pro- and anti-immigration responses. By comparing these baseline percentages with those of Treatment Groups 1 and 2, the study can understand the effects of the dependent variables, regardless of the respondents' political leanings. Thus, whether the majority of respondents identify with the right or the left, the comparative analysis should validate the reliability of the results across political spectra.

The questionnaire was administered online, using tools like social networks, WhatsApp's broadcasts, and survey platforms such as SurveyCircle.com.

The Allocate Monster software by Fergusson (2016) was used to randomly assign participants to the different groups. By inserting the three Google Forms links, it generates a single link that, once clicked, equally and blindly randomizes participants into the various groups.

To the survey's end, it was not necessary to collect sensitive data such as email addresses or phone numbers. However, before completing the survey, each participant was advised to view the privacy policy and was asked to explicitly consent to the processing of their data in accordance with EU Regulation 2016/679, articles 13-14.

3.1.4 Sample Size

Due to limited funds and time, the study was mostly designed as a preliminary exploration for future research. Accordingly, rather than having a predetermined sample size, the goal was to collect as much data as possible within two months, resulting in a sample of 521 respondents.

As previously mentioned, since the sample does not accurately reflect the target population, it becomes essential to use survey data weighing to adjust the survey. In detail, different weights are assigned to different responses based on key characteristics like age, gender, geographical origin, etc., to ensure that the sample perfectly represents the larger population. This procedure minimizes bias and increases the survey results' reliability and validity.

After collecting the data, "demographic graphs" were created, to show the distribution of responses across each demographic group. An expected distribution table was also made to illustrate how the distribution of survey responses would appear if the sample were completely representative of the population (according to ISTAT data). This table is then compared to the actual demographic dataset, serving as a benchmark to notice any significant discrepancies that could suggest bias in the survey sample.

With the reference population (Italian Population) set, the weighting factor for each demographic group is calculated by dividing the expected percentage by the actual percentage. Each data point is then multiplied by its corresponding weighting factor, adjusting the data for a better representation of the target population (Ridgeway, G., et al., 2022).

3.2 Description of the Survey Questionnaire

As described above, the research envisages three different groups, presenting three different questionnaires.

3.2.1 Demographic section

All three surveys shared a common first section that covered sociodemographic information including questions on age, gender, origin, education, and economic status. This section is

crucial for assessing the general characteristics of the sample population and identifying any potential biases resulting from self-selection. By capturing detailed sociodemographic data, the study could address imbalances in the sample. This data allowed the application of statistical weights during analysis, ensuring that the sample more accurately represented the broader population.

Furthermore, this initial section provided a foundation for understanding the overall composition of the participants, facilitating a more nuanced analysis of the effects of the treatments. By comparing the sociodemographic profiles across the control and treatment groups, researchers could ensure that any observed differences in attitudes or responses were due to the interventions rather than pre-existing demographic disparities.

Specifically, participants were asked to indicate:

1. Their age. (*18 or less; 19-24; 25-34; 35-44; 45-54; 55-64; 65 or more*)
2. Their gender (*man, woman, or other*).
3. Their education, in terms of the highest educational qualification obtained. (*No qualification, elementary license, middle school license, high school/technical/professional diploma, bachelor's degree, master's degree, and Master/Doctorate*).
4. Their main occupation (*Student, Student-worker, Self-employed, Employee, Retired and Unemployed*).
5. Their geographical origin. (*north, center, south of Italy*)
6. A self-assessment of the economic status in terms of well-being (*insufficient, precarious, more than sufficient, wealthy, and well-off*).

(Quintelier, E., & Hooghe, M., 2013).

3.2.2 Section on Attitudes toward Migration and Political views

Again, all three questionnaires shared a common final section that inquired about personal attitudes and perceptions regarding immigrants, as well as participants' political views. This main section provides insights into people's political positions, voting behaviors, and interest in Italian politics. It helps determine the extent to which respondents' ideals might be influenced by a political message, a political figure, or a combination of both. Understanding the political orientation helps identify correlations between political beliefs and attitudes towards migration. It also helps in cross-referencing their political stance with their actual voting patterns. Measuring interest in politics is crucial for understanding respondents' political awareness and

engagement level. It allows to determine how closely respondents follow political developments, which can influence their opinions on policy issues.

Additionally, this section included questions about participants' migration policy preferences, the importance they attribute to migration issues, and their views on the economic impact of migration and the duty of assistance. This information allows to catch people's general attitudes toward migrants and migration and to assess whether the treatments have influenced these attitudes.

In detail, participants were asked to answer about:

1. Political Orientation on a scale from 0 to 10, where 0 represents *extreme right-wing* and 10 represents *extreme left-wing* (Dillman *et al.*, 2014).
2. Voting Behavior in the last political elections in 2022 (*Fratelli d'Italia, Partito Democratico, Lega per Salvini Premier, Movimento cinque stelle, Forza Italia, Italia Viva, Azione, Altro, Nessuno*)
3. Interest in Italian Politics (*I do not follow Italian politics at all, I follow Italian politics only occasionally, I follow Italian politics moderately, I follow Italian politics quite attentively, I follow Italian politics very attentively*).
4. Migration Policy Preferences (*Border control, Integration, Humanitarian aid, Repatriation policies, Other*) (Ceobanu, A. M., & Escandell, X., 2010; Blitz, B., 2017)
5. Perception of migrants' contribution to Italian society (*Very positive, Positive, Neutral, Negative, very negative*). (Pratto F., *et al.* 1994).
6. Importance of Migration Issue (*I do not consider the issue of migration important at all, I consider the issue of migration to be of little importance, I consider the issue of migration to be moderately important, I consider the issue of migration to be quite important, I consider the issue of migration to be very important*).
7. Economic Impact of Immigration: Participants rate their agreement with the statement "*Immigrants can contribute to Italy's economic growth*" on a five-point scale from *Strongly disagree* to *Strongly agree*.
8. National Duty to Assist Migrants: Respondents evaluate their agreement with the notion that "*Assisting migrants is a national duty*," using the same five-point scale.

This section was primarily inspired by the recent Positive and Negative Perception of Immigrants Scale (PANPIS), developed to assess both positive and negative attitudes toward immigrants (Panno *et al.*, 2023). The validity and psychometric reliability of PANPIS were demonstrated through two studies involving a total of 956 participants. These results indicate that scale represents a robust measure, distinguished by its ability to simultaneously investigate prejudice and capture both positive and negative attitudes towards immigrants. Another

significant source was the Eurobarometer, which provided additional insights into public opinion and attitudes inquiries within the conceptual sphere of migration (Maria P. E., 2017).

3.2.3 Control group

As stated above, the Control Group's aim is to provide an unbiased baseline for comparing the two treatments, allowing for an accurate comprehension of the latter's impacts. To this end, respondents are questioned about their political positions and general views on migration. This helps to grasp the broader population's attitudes on the topic before any treatment or influence is applied. Participants were questioned following this schema:

Section 1: Socio-Demographic

Section 2: Attitudes on Migration and Political Views

3.2.3 Treatment 1

This group of respondents is presented with two pro-migration messages (independent variable 1) from an anonymous source: one highlighting the positive impact of migration on the Italian economy, and the other emphasizing the national duty to assist migrants. They are placed in between the socio-demographic section and the general assessment of respondents' attitudes on migration and political stances. This setup aims to investigate the extent to which respondents' attitudes can be influenced by general positive messages on migration. The process follows the schema outlined below:

Section 1: Socio-Demographic

Section 2: Treatment 1

Article from 01-16-2016: *"Immigration in Italy is a controversial topic, but it is worth examining its economic impact. Migrants can act as a growth engine for economic development, filling labor shortages or stimulating innovation and productivity in key sectors."*

Book published in 2023: *"Preserving our identity is fundamental; however, welcoming those seeking refuge represents an innate duty of our nation. Assisting people fleeing armed conflicts, persecution, or poverty cannot be reduced to a mere act of generosity but must be recognized as an essential ethical and moral obligation."*

Section 3: Attitudes on Migration and Political Views

3.2.4 Treatment 2

Participants randomly assigned to this group are exposed to the same positive messages about migration as in Treatment 1, but with a key difference: the source and messengers delivering these messages are explicitly identified (independent variable 2). This approach further

analyzes the impact of pro-migrant messages when combined with well-known figures from the Italian public arena.

The distinctive feature of this questionnaire is the choice of messengers. The public figures presented typically align with right-wing and anti-immigration sentiments, contrasting with the positive messages they convey. This contrast aimed to determine, in particular, whether right-wing, typically anti-immigrant voters might be influenced by positive messages when delivered by figures they trust and identify with.

The third questionnaire's outline was:

Section 1: Socio-Demographic

Section 2: Treatment 2

Vittorio Feltri, an Italian journalist, wrote in an article for “Libero” on January 16, 2016:

“Immigration in Italy is a controversial topic, but it is worth examining its economic impact. Migrants can act as a growth engine for economic development, filling labor shortages or stimulating innovation and productivity in key sectors.”

In his 2023 book “Il Mondo al Contrario,” Roberto Vannacci, a writer and general in the

Italian army, argues: *“Preserving our identity is fundamental; however, welcoming those seeking refuge represents an innate duty of our nation. Assisting people fleeing armed conflicts, persecution, or poverty cannot be reduced to a mere act of generosity but must be recognized as an essential ethical and moral obligation.”*

Section 3: Attitudes on Migration and Political Views

(Davis, M.H., 1980; Leach C. W. *et al.*, 2008; Dillman D. A., *et al.*, 2014).

Since both treatments were short and easy to read, there was no need to introduce attention-check or exclusion criteria in the questionnaires. They took just 4 minutes to complete, minimizing the likelihood that participants would be non-compliant or fail to thoroughly read the treatments and questions.

3.3 Data Collection Process

3.3.1 Data Collection Tools

As aforementioned, the online survey was the sole data collection tool used in this research. This instrument was adopted for its many advantages, particularly regarding reach, efficiency, and data management.

Online surveys offer the possibility for a wide distribution without any (or very few) financial burdens. Indeed, technological tools eliminate the need for sheets, other equipment, physical

printing and deployment, significantly reducing the expenses related to traditional and face-to-face data collection methods.

Additionally, the online survey rises above geographical space and limitations, enabling rapid and costless data collection from a wide and heterogeneous audience. Indeed, employing platforms like WhatsApp, Instagram, Facebook, and SurveyCircle, the questionnaire successfully reached a substantial number of respondents from southern Italy – an area that is located far away both geographically, since my main residence site is in Turin, and emotionally, being quite outside my personal networks. This comprehensive reach increased the representativeness and, consequently, generalizability of the findings.

Online surveys also yield significant advantages in terms of convenience and anonymity. These conditions likely make participants feel at ease, allowing them to complete the survey at any moment and at their own pace, which, in turn, results in more thoughtful and reflective answers. The confidence of complete anonymity - considering that the survey did not collect personal information such as emails, names, or phone numbers - supposedly enhances answers' honesty and accuracy, especially regarding salient, polarized, and, thus, sensitive topics like migration attitudes.

From the data management viewpoint, online surveys simplify and automatize the data collection process. Platforms like Google Forms, systemically collect and save responses in a digital format, reducing the risk of data entry errors, whilst facilitating easy data manipulation through statistical software. This capability saves time, allowing for immediate access to data insights and real-time data monitoring.

A small pilot test was also efficiently carried out using online tools, allowing for very rapid preliminary testing and quick adjustments before the final delivery (Tang, J., *et al.*, 2022).

Overall, online surveys leverage technological progress and advantages to provide efficient and flexible data collection, making it possible to conduct valid research even with limited funds.

3.3.2 Procedure

The definitive questionnaire was preceded by a small pilot test, lasting one week and involving around 10 people. This preliminary process was carried out to detect any possible unclear or ambiguous questions, focusing particularly on the third section investigating attitudes towards migration. The pilot sample was chosen for its representativeness of the research population based on the most relevant demographic indicators.

Demographic Breakdown of the Pilot Sample:

- **Age Distribution:**

- <18 years old: 1 participant
 - 19-24 years old: 2 participants
 - 25-34 years old: 1 participant
 - 35-44 years old: 1 participant
 - 45-54 years old: 1 participant
 - 55-64 years old: 2 participants
 - 65 years old: 2 participants.
- **Gender:**
 - Male: 4 respondents
 - Female: 5 respondents
 - Other: 1 respondent
 - **Education level:**
 - No educational qualification: 1 person
 - Elementary license: 1 person
 - Middle school license: 2 people
 - Professional diploma: 2 people
 - Bachelor's degree: 2 people
 - Master's doctorate: 1 people

The pilot sample was invited to complete all three surveys and, subsequently, provide feedback on the meaning and clarity of each question and their understanding of the treatments. This pilot testing helped improve the questions' clarity and effectiveness, thereby enhancing the research's validity and reliability (Pearson, N., *et al.*, 2020).

After correcting some unclear questions, the final questionnaire was deployed by the end of May 2024 for approximately two months. It was distributed in person to friends and family and further spread via WhatsApp broadcasts, Instagram stories, and Facebook groups. One particularly effective platform was SurveyCycle, which attracted nearly half respondents. On SurveyCycle individuals, enterprises, and students upload their surveys and receive a score

based on the number of questionnaires they complete. A higher rating results in higher scores for everyone who completes your questionnaire. In addition, several security measures are in place on the website to prevent cheating. For instance, it invalidates too quick responses, requires GPS activation to ensure respondents are within the target geographical area, requests IDs or other documents to confirm participants' alignment with the target group, and so on.

By the end of July 2024, the questionnaire was closed to allow for the analysis of the results.

3.3.3 Ethical considerations

During the data collection process, several ethical considerations and measures were taken to ensure the research's integrity, ethics, and credibility.

Firstly, participants were provided with specific information about the study. The first section of the survey included details such as the research's purposes, procedures, and intentions. Respondents were also informed about the data usage, assuring their data would be reported just in aggregate format, preventing any possibility of identifiable information. The text also gave my contact information in case anyone had concerns or questions. At the end of the introductory section, people were asked to explicitly consent to the processing of their data in accordance with EU Regulation 2016/679, articles 13-14.

Given that the survey included sections inquiring about attitudes toward migration, which can be sometimes regarded as a sensitive topic, additional care was taken to make sure questions were phrased neutrally and respectfully. Additionally, to ensure the voluntary nature of participation, respondents were informed that, if uncomfortable, they could withdraw from the study at any time without consequences.

As above-mentioned, the survey did not collect any personal identifiers like phone numbers, emails, or names, to guarantee anyone's complete anonymity.

Finally, all data was securely stored, with access authorized only to me.

3.4 Data Analysis Methods

The objective of the research is to evaluate the effects and impact of the messenger — the individual who conveys messages and leads informational campaigns — on Italian public opinion regarding migration. It specifically assesses whether the identity of a messenger, when made explicit, influences people's agreement or disagreement with the message presented.

To this end, 3 different regression models are set up, each comparing migration attitudes of different groups' respondents. The first analysis compares answers from Control and Treatment 1 groups to extrapolate the effects of pro-immigrant messages; the second model matches

results from Control and Treatment 2 groups, examining the effect of both pro-immigration messages and messengers' identity combined; the third and central assessment confronts Treatment 1 and Treatment 2 responses in order to grasp the impact of messengers' identity alone.

Within these models, People's attitudes towards migration represent the Dependent Variable (DV), whose variability is tested upon 3 Independent Variables (IVs), namely no treatment, Treatment 1 and Treatment 2.

3.4.2 Data Coding

To aptly analyze the questionnaires' data, the categorical variables were converted into the following numerical codes:

Dependent Variables:

- No Treatment = 0
- Treatment 1 = 1
- Treatment 2 = 0

Independent Variables:

Attitudes towards Migration:

- Strongly anti-immigrant = 1
- Anti-immigrant = 2
- Neutral = 3
- Pro-immigrant = 4
- Strongly pro-immigrant = 5

3.4.1 Model

As previously mentioned, the chosen model for analyzing this study's data is Simple Linear Regression, which is particularly efficient in predicting the value of a dependent variable based on an independent variable. This model was selected for its simplicity and interpretability: Linear Regression models are relatively straightforward and provide an easy-to-interpret mathematical formula to generate predictions.

The results are based on the following formulas.

1. **Attitude = β_0 + $\beta_0 \cdot \text{Treatment0}$ + ϵ**
2. **Attitude = β_0 + $\beta_1 \cdot \text{Treatment1}$ + ϵ**
3. **Attitude = β_0 + $\beta_2 \cdot \text{Treatment2}$ + ϵ**

Where:

- ❖ Attitude is the dependent variable, representing people's attitudes toward migration.
- ❖ β_0 is the Intercept of the model. It is the "No Treatment" coefficient, representing migration attitudes without any Treatment.
- ❖ B_1 is the "Treatment 1" coefficient. This measures the average migration attitude of people who received Treatment 1 compared to individuals who received no Treatment.
- ❖ B_2 is the "Treatment 2" coefficient. This measures the average migration attitude of people who received Treatment 2 compared to individuals who received no Treatment.
- ❖ Treatment is the Independent Variable indicating which treatment the individual received. No treatment is coded as 1, Treatment 1 as 2, and Treatment 2 as 3.
- ❖ ϵ is the error term representing the accuracy of the coefficients' predictions.

After collecting the surveys, the data for the Dependent and Independent Variables were input into Excel to calculate intercepts, coefficients, and errors.

Excel also calculates the following statistical measures:

- ❖ T-statistic (hypothesis test statistic), measuring the extent of the deviation of the observed difference (between the Treatments and no Treatment) from the expected result if there was no actual effect, considering the data variability (error term). It determines if the difference is relevant or possibly accidental.
- ❖ P-value (or significance observed level) represents a probability score indicating how likely it is to obtain the observed result if the null hypothesis is true. If the value is less than 0.05, it suggests that the probability of obtaining the observed results by chance alone was less than 5%, meaning that the Treatment produced a real effect.
- ❖ Confidential Interval (CI), the range of values expected to contain the estimated parameter. A narrower interval indicates more precise estimates (from 95 to 99%).

These calculations help determine the relationship between treatments and migration attitudes, allowing to assess the impact of each treatment on people's attitudes toward migration (Morris, J. D., & Lieberman, M. (2020); Outrman J. G., *et al.*, 2021; Al-Khaiat, S. S., *et al.*, 2022).

Before running the regression model, it is crucial for the research's validity, to check if some basic assumptions are met.

First, the linearity of the relationship between Independent Variables and Dependent Variables must be verified. This means that if the IVs change, the DVs should change consistently, making the ratio of change uniform, forming a straight-line pattern when plotted on a graph.

Second, Homoscedasticity, or Homogeneity of variance, requires that the spread (variance) of the prediction errors (residuals) is the same across all Independent Variables. This assumption

is checked by creating a scatter plot of the residuals versus the predicted values: if the variables are homoscedastic the points would appear randomly scattered (Đalić, I., & Terzić, S., 2021). Third, the normality assumption is necessary to estimate standard errors unbiasedly, hence confidence intervals and P-values. It refers to whether the data collected (DVs) follows a “normal distribution”. This assumption is verified by creating a histogram. If it resembles a bell-shaped curve, the data may be normally distributed, since most survey responses are supposed to cluster around the center (like the peak of the bell) and fewer responses are likely at the extremes (tails) of the curve (Alita, D., *et al*, 2021).

Lastly, Multicollinearity occurs when two or more independent variables are strongly correlated, making it challenging to isolate their individual effects on the dependent variable. This is assessed by examining the correlation coefficient between two variables: if it is close to +1.0 or -1.0, they are considered perfectly collinear (Shrestha, N., 2020).

By ensuring these assumptions are met, it is possible to confidently assess the impact of each treatment on people’s attitudes toward migration.

CHAPTER 4: FINDINGS

This chapter presents and interprets the research findings, offering a comprehensive analysis of the data collected and its implications. The goal is to provide a detailed examination of the results and to discuss their significance in relation to the research questions.

The chapter is organized into four sections. The first section (*4.1 Presentation and Analysis of the Baseline Data and the Key Patterns*) introduces the initial data and highlights the significant patterns observed, while the second (*4.2 Presentation of the Main Findings: Regression Models*) focuses on the primary results derived from regression analyses, presenting a detailed account of the statistical outcomes.

4.1 Presentation and Analysis of the Baseline Data and the Key Patterns

4.1.1 Baseline Data of the Control Group

As previously illustrated in the former chapter, participants assigned to the Control Group are asked to answer some general questions about their attitudes on migration, immigrants, and political orientation. This type of questionnaire setup was designed to provide a baseline for assessing respondents' broader pro/anti-immigration preferences and political leanings. Due to the random assignment of participants, it is then possible to generalize and project the results from the Control Group onto their entire sample. If, for instance, 30% of the Control Group holds anti-immigrant sentiment, it can be inferred that approximately about 30% of the whole sample shares this belief.

Within his final chapter, the first part is intended to provide insights into the political and migration-related preferences of the Control Group's respondents. The results presented below will effectively serve as a threshold, upon which the Regression model's findings will be interpreted, allowing the analysis of any shifts resulting from the Treatments' impact.

Control Group's Political Orientation:

Political orientation	Count	Percentage
Extreme right	6	3.5%
Strong right	3	1.7%
Right	11	6.5%
Moderate right	15	8.9%
Slightly right	6	3.5%
Neutral	20	11.8%

Slightly left	12	7.1%
Moderate left	27	16%
Left	48	28.4%
Strong left	18	10.6%
Extreme left	3	1.8%

TABLE 1: CONTROL GROUP’S POLITICAL ORIENTATION DISTRIBUTION

The table above provides a detailed breakdown of participants’ political orientations by count and percentage. In contrast, the graph below aggregates respondents into three broad categories: left, right, and neutral. This simplification is intended to offer a clearer and more accessible overview of the respondents' political leanings.

In a nutshell, 54.5% of participants are left voters, 27.2% identify as right-wing, and 18% is possibly uncertain or “neutral”. Given these distributions, we can infer that participants in both Treatment 1 and Treatment 2 are likely to span a similar spectrum of political orientations.

FIGURE 12: POLITICAL ORIENTATION DISTRIBUTION GROUPED (CONTROL GROUP)

Control Group’s Political Affiliation:

Data reveal that the Democratic Party received the highest percentage of votes, accounting for approximately 35% of the total. This reflects and echoes the large group of left- and moderate-left voters observed in the previous graph. Additionally, a significant portion of the respondents, around 15%, indicated that they did not vote, highlighting a notable level of disengagement and uncertainty, typical characteristic of the enlarging movable middle discussed in the first chapter. The graph below further shows that the remaining participants predominantly voted for Movimento 5stelle, Lega per Salvini premier, Fratelli d’Italia, and Azione, with the rest being almost equally distributed among other minor parties.

FIGURE 13: PERCENTAGE OF VOTES FOR EACH PARTY (CONTROL GROUP)

Control Group's Interest Levels in Italian Politics:

The survey's outputs show that the largest group of respondents, about 40%, claims to follow Italian politics quite attentively. This high level of engagement suggests a potentially higher turnout impact among this group, as they are more likely to be informed about the current political debates and related political and public figures, and thus may be more easily influenced by the identity of the messengers presented in the treatments. Other significant portions of the sample, around 25% and 23% respectively, reported following politics moderately and only occasionally. This group might represent swing voters or the so-called movable middle, whose swaying engagement is likely to be easily influenced by specific issues, campaigns, or events. About 10% of the respondents do not follow Italian politics at all. Lastly, a small percentage, around 2%, reported following politics very attentively.

The Most Important Aspects of Italian Migration Policy According to the Control Group:

The analysis unveils several key trends and priorities. As pictured by the visual cloud graph below, the most frequently mentioned aspects can be categorized as pro-immigrant, with Humanitarian aid and Integration on the podium (with 56 and 78 votes respectively). Nonetheless, a significant number of respondents (31 and 23, together accounting for 26% of respondents) referred to Border Control and Repatriation Policies as preferred action plans. Few other participants cited also the necessity of agreements with third countries along with the management of migratory flows, the need to stop the exploitation of migrants' illegal labor, the urge to assist them in finding better living conditions, or to grant citizenship rights and jobs.

Overall, the majority of the sample seems to prioritize immediate assistance to migrants, indicating a wide concern for the welfare and basic needs of the newcomers. Alongside these sentiments, lies a quest for regulatory policies with over 30% of people expressing some anxiety about uncontrolled migration and its related corollary.

Perception of migrants' contribution to Italian Society within Control Group:

Participants' ideas about migrants' input into Italian Society seem to mirror Political Orientation's and Policy Preferences' results, previously analyzed. As illustrated before, a percentage close to 30% are right voters, supporting Lega per Salvini Premier and Fratelli d'Italia. Consistently, around one-third of respondents selected as priority migration policy, Border control followed by Repatriation policies. Similarly, 49 out of 172 people, approximately 28.5% of the Control group's sample, consider migrants' contribution to the Italian Economy as negative or very negative (in 12 cases).

Anyhow, the majority of participants perceive migrants' contributions as positive, followed by neutral (or uncertain) respondents (31%), invariably echoing previous observations. Both right-

end and left-end "Extremists" constitute the smallest groups (see table T1 in appendix).

FIGURE 14: PERCEPTION OF MIGRANTS' CONTRIBUTION TO THE ITALIAN SOCIETY ACCORDING TO CONTROL GROUP.

Control Group's Perceived Importance of Migration-Related Issues:

The survey data predictably indicate that a significant majority of the Control group's sample rates migration as *highly important*. The data presented fit perfectly with the broader academic discourse on the politicization and salience of migration issues, discussed in the previous chapter. As several scholars outline, despite stable global migration rates over the past fifty years, public and media attention on migration has increased tenfold (Jeannet *et al.*, 2021; Miller, 2017). In this era of economic and political discontent, with growing divisions in society, many feel vulnerable and left behind. Populist politicians have exploited and heightened this unease and hijacked people's concerns putting the blame firmly on migration.

In fact, several studies show how media coverage and political instrumentalization are the most effective factors contributing to the heightened political salience of migration, leading to its politicization (Helbling, 2014; Gattinara, 2016; Alto Analytics, 2019). The significant support for anti-immigration parties highlighted in the previous chapters, even without a corresponding rise in anti-immigration sentiment, unveils a paradox. Voters tend to back specific parties not only based on policy congruence but also on the salience of issues they prioritize (Lauwers *et al.*, 2021).

According to this premise, the high level of perceived importance observed among the Control Group’s participants (which can be projected onto the whole sample), suggests a potential dual outcome. The increasing prominence of these issues might either make some segments of the population particularly sensitive and exposed to different events, media messages and inputs, or may contribute to the reinforcing of mainstream frames making them harder to eradicate. In both case, the high salience placed on the migration debate by the sample, may “negatively” or “positively” affect the final results of the study (see table T2 in appendix).

FIGURE 15: PERCEIVED IMPORTANCE OF THE MIGRATION ISSUE TO THE CONTROL GROUP

Control Group’s Attitudes toward Migration:

1. People’s perception of the Economic Impact of Migration, where participants rated their agreement with the statement “Immigrants can contribute to Italy’s economic growth” on a five-point scale from Strongly disagree to Strongly agree.

The graph shows that over half of respondents (nearly 63%) (strongly) believe that immigrants contributed or can contribute to the Italian economic growth. Approximately 40 people (22,67%) claim to neither agree nor disagree with the statement, while over 14% of people argue that migrants don’t or couldn’t contribute to the Italian economy. As thoroughly explained above, these data lay out the baseline: they represent the whole sample’s attitudes toward migration before any kind of treatment. Hence, it can be assumed that in the absence of Treatments, 63% of the sample believes in a positive contribution of migration to the Italian economy, 22,67% is neutral or uncertain, and 14% is skeptical about the possible contribution of immigrants in economic terms.

In simpler terms, any significant deviation from this baseline observed in the two Treatment Groups would indicate that the treatments have had an impact.

FIGURE 16: LEVEL OF AGREEMENT TO THE STATEMENT “IMMIGRANTS CAN CONTRIBUTE TO ITALY’S ECONOMIC GROWTH (CONTROL GROUP)

2. Control Group’s Sense of Duty to Assist Migrants. Respondents evaluated their agreement with the notion that “Assisting migrants is a national duty,” using the same five-point scale as the previous item.

Almost half of the sample (over 45%) *strongly* agrees with the item, while 22.67 % agrees. A smaller number is neutral or uncertain, namely the 14%.

On the other end of the spectrum, almost 10% and 9%, disagree or strongly disagree respectively to the idea that assisting migrants is a national duty.

In this case, the baseline is settled at 77% of “positive” attitudes, 14% “neutral” and 19% “negative”. Once again, the Control Group’s attitudes toward migration are in line with data from the items above presented.

FIGURE 17: LEVEL OF AGREEMENT TO THE STATEMENT “ASSISTING MIGRANTS IS A NATIONAL DUTY (CONTROL GROUP)

Another interesting aspect to analyze is the comparison of responses to Statement 1 and Statement 2. This comparison helps to reveal the baseline priorities and attitudes of the Italian population regarding migration. Although these two statements represent only a small part of the broader migration issue, they might provide valuable insights into people’s primary

concerns and their most vulnerable and easy to influence ideas. The graphs on the right illustrate the comparison of the vote distribution between the two items' responses while the figure below the mean confrontation.

While means scores for both statements are approximately the same, the distribution of responses reveals some interesting differences.

The first graph shows a concentration of votes on the higher values (4 and 5) for both items, indicating strong overall agreement. However, there is a slight difference in the lower grades (1 and 2), with a

higher percentage of "strongly disagree" with the idea that "Assisting migrants is a national duty".

FIGURE 18: COMPARISON BETWEEN CONTROL GROUP'S RESPONSES TO THE TWO STATEMENTS

Specifically, the most significant difference lies in the 5th column: 31% of respondents "strongly agree" with the statement that "Immigrants can contribute to Italy's economic growth," compared to over 45% who "strongly agree" with the statement that "Assisting migrants is a national duty." This suggests a stronger consensus on migrant assistance as a national duty, with

more respondents expressing strong agreement rather than just agreement.

FIGURE 19: COMPARISON BETWEEN CONTROL GROUP'S RESPONSES TO THE TWO STATEMENTS (MEANS)

On the other hand, the second statement shows simultaneously a higher level of neutral and uncertain answers (13%) and a higher level of disagreement. This may indicate a slightly stronger polarization on this specific issue. In other words, while the perception of the economic contribution of immigration is more varied (likely due to the complexity and breadth of the topic, which may require further qualitative research), people tend to have a more definitive stance on the moral and national responsibility to assist migrants, either agreeing or disagreeing more decisively. This polarization could reflect underlying values and ethical considerations that are deeply ingrained in the population's attitudes towards migration (Arikan, & Ben-Nun Bloom, P. 2013; Schahbasi, *et al.* 2021).

4.1.1 Highlight of the Key Statistics, Patterns, or Trends

Before presenting and analyzing the main results of the research and the findings from the regression models, this section spotlights the most significant key patterns and trends connecting different demographic variables to the sample's attitudes toward migration attitudes. To this end, some pivot graphs were created in Excel. The different demographic categories are displayed on the y-axis while migration attitudes measured by two different items are shown on the x-axis.

- The lighter, left bars refer to the mean average agreement with the statement: *Immigrants can contribute to Italy's economic growth*, rated on a five-point scale from Strongly disagree to Strongly agree.
- The darker, right bars represent the mean average agreement with the notion that *“Assisting migrants is a national duty,”* using the same five-point scale.

Attitudes toward Migration versus

Age:

As shown by the three different graphs reflecting different age groups, there is no strong or significant difference in the attitudes toward migration between the different age categories.

FIGURE 20: PIVOT GRAPH. ATTITUDE TOWARD MIGRATION VS AGE (CONTROL GROUP)

However, when examining the graphs together, an interesting trend seems to emerge: there is a sharper increase in “negative” attitudes with age in the Control Group compared to the two Treatment Groups. This suggests that older individuals (those over 65 years old) may be more susceptible to influence from messages or messengers than younger individuals.

FIGURE 21: PIVOT GRAPH. ATTITUDE TOWARD MIGRATION VS AGE (TREATMENT GROUP 1)

Interestingly, respondents exposed to Treatment 2 (explicit public and political right-wing figures voicing positive messages on migration), tend to show a lower level of agreement in the age group from 25 to 54 compared to the other groups. According to several studies (Maraffi, 2018; Faggian et al., 2021) this age group is likely to include a majority of left-leaning voters and pro-immigrant individuals, who may be negatively influenced by messages from out-group messengers. Some research highlights indeed how the source of the message can trigger defensive or oppositional attitudes, leading to a rejection of the message itself, sometimes regardless of the content (see paragraphs below) (Seu, 2010; Johnson et al., 2018).

FIGURE 22: PIVOT GRAPH. ATTITUDE TOWARD MIGRATION VS AGE (TREATMENT GROUP 2)

Attitudes toward Migration versus Gender:

The graphs indicate a slight correlation between gender and attitudes towards migration across all groups. Specifically, women express a higher level of trust in migrants’ contribution to the Italian economic growth and a stronger sense of responsibility to assist them, with average differences of + 0.70 in the Control Group, + 0.5 in Treatment 1, and +0,6 in Treatment 2, compared to men.

FIGURE 23: PIVOT GRAPH. ATTITUDE TOWARD MIGRATION VS GENDER (CONTROL GROUP)

This discrepancy remains consistent after exposure to Treatments, indicating an equal effect of the latter in both genders.

FIGURE 24: PIVOT GRAPH. ATTITUDE TOWARD MIGRATION VS GENDER (TREATMENT GROUP 1)

Though slight, these findings are supported by several studies in the existing literature. Research has shown that women tend to exhibit lower levels of ethnocentrism and authoritarianism (Kimmelmeier, 2010) and often have more positive attitudes towards outgroups and less prejudice (Kite and Whitley, 1996; Sidanius and Pratto, 1999). These elements suggest that women's social beliefs are driven less by a personal need for cognitive structure and consistency (Kimmelmeier, 2010) and more by a concern for the well-being of others (Schultz and Searleman, 2002). In the context of this study, this includes greater empathy and support for migrants.

FIGURE 25: PIVOT GRAPH. ATTITUDE TOWARD MIGRATION VS GENDER (TREATMENT GROUP 2)

Attitudes towards migration versus Education level:

The analysis of migration attitudes by education level reveals a clear trend: positive attitudes towards migration increase with higher education levels. This finding aligns with the existing body of research, which suggests a strong correlation between education and positive migration attitudes (de Haas, 2010).

FIGURE 26: PIVOT GRAPH. ATTITUDE TOWARD MIGRATION VS EDUCATION LEVEL (CONTROL GROUP)

When examining the impact of the treatments, it appears that neither treatment had a significant overall impact on the distribution of positive attitudes across education categories. However, there is an exception among individuals with university degrees. For this group, positive attitudes towards migration visibly decreased, particularly under Treatment 2.

FIGURE 26: PIVOT GRAPH. ATTITUDE TOWARD MIGRATION VS EDUCATION LEVEL (TREATMENT GROUP 1)

This trend may correlate with age distribution patterns, where younger groups showed a decrease in positive attitudes due to Treatment 2.

Several scholars have noted that individuals with university degrees are more likely to be left-leaning and pro-immigrant. This demographic may be particularly susceptible to negative influences from out-group messengers (Maraffi, 2018; Faggian et al., 2021). Thus, the observed decrease in positive attitudes among university-educated individuals under Treatment 2 might be explained by these dynamics.

Both treatments had a notable impact on perceptions of migrants' contributions to Italian economic growth. This effect was especially pronounced among individuals with lower levels of education. Interestingly, individuals with no formal qualifications showed very high levels of agreement with the positive statements about migrants' contributions. However, due to the small sample size of this group, these results should be interpreted with caution as they may represent outliers.

FIGURE 27: PIVOT GRAPH. ATTITUDE TOWARD MIGRATION VS EDUCATION LEVEL (TREATMENT GROUP 2)

The other demographic variables collected (main occupation, geographic origin, and economic status) did not show any interesting or relevant trend or pattern for the purpose of this research. Therefore, they have been omitted from the analysis.

4.2 Presentation of the Main Findings: Regression Models

4.2.1 Regression Model 1 and 2: Control Group versus Treatment 1

Independent variable: Treatment 1

0 = control group, 1 = treatment1

Dependent variables: Attitudes toward Migration (Y)

1. Level of agreement with the item “*Immigrants can contribute to Italy’s economic growth*” (Y1)
2. Level of agreement with the item “*Assisting migrants is a national duty*” (Y2)

See table T3 (regression model 1) and T4 (regression model 2) in appendix.

Statistic	Explanation	Model 1 (Y1)	Model 2 (Y2)
Multiple R	Correlation coefficient between the observed and predicted values of the dependent variable. (value close to 0 = very weak relationship)	0.093939	0.130881
R Square	The proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that is explained by the Treatment	0.008824	0.01713
Adjusted R Square	Adjusted R Square adjusts the R Square value based on the number of predictors in the model. (Adjusted R square	0.005952	0.014281

	lower than the R square = adding more variables might not necessarily improve the model fit.)		
Standard Error	The standard deviation of the residuals (prediction errors).	0.499211	0.497115
Observations		347	347
df (Regression)	Degrees of freedom (N. of Independent Variables)	1	1
SS (Regression)	The sum of squares due to regression, indicating the variation explained by the model.	0.765467	1.485892
MS (Regression)	Mean square due to regression (SS divided by df).	0.765467	1.485892
F	It checks if at least one of the variables used to make predictions is helpful. (Higher values = more significant model)	3.071551	6.012748
Significance F	A value less than 0.05 typically indicates statistical significance.	0.080562	0.014698
df (Residual)	Degrees of freedom for residuals.	345	345
SS (Residual)	The sum of squares due to residuals.	85.97805	85.25762
MS (Residual)	Mean square due to residuals (SS divided by df)	0.249212	0.247124
Intercept Coefficient	The predicted value of the dependent variable when all independent variables are zero.	0.483568	0.475903
Intercept Standard Error	The standard error of the intercept estimate.	0.029299	0.029095
Intercept t Stat	The t-statistic for the intercept, testing whether the intercept is significantly different from zero. It checks if the base level of the model is meaningful.	16.504574	16.35707
Intercept P-value	The p-value for the intercept's t-statistic shows how likely it is that the intercept is just a random number. (Small number = significant, not random)	1.62E-45	6.34E-45
Intercept Lower 95%	The 95% confidence interval for the intercept	0.425941	0.418678
Intercept Upper 95%		0.541195	0.533128
Treatment Coefficient	The estimated effect of the Treatment on participants' Attitudes toward migration.	0.004246	0.005349
Treatment Standard Error	The standard error of the treatment coefficient.	0.002423	0.002181
Treatment t Stat	The t-statistic for the treatment, tests whether the treatment is significantly different from zero. It checks if the treatment has a real impact.	1.752584	2.452091
Treatment P-value	The p-value for the treatment's t-statistic shows how likely it is that the treatment's effect is just a random occurrence. (Small number = significant, not random)	0.080562	0.014698

Treatment Lower 95%	The 95% confidence interval for the treatment	-0.00052	0.001058
Treatment Upper 95%		0.009012	0.00964

TABLE T5: REGRESSION MODEL 1 AND 2 (COMBINED SUMMARY TABLE)

Significance F values less than 0.05 typically indicate statistical significance. Accordingly, Model 1 with a significance F value of 0.080562, likely represents a marginally significant model, while Model 2, with a significance F value of 0.014698, suggests a statistically considerable analysis.

In both models, the Intercepts T statistics (16.504574 and 16.35707) confirm that the intercept is significantly different from zero, determining a meaningful base level. Similarly, both Intercept P-values being small numbers (1.62E-45; 6.34E-45), exclude the possibility of randomness in the intercept, acknowledging its significance.

The treatment coefficients in both models, which indicate the estimated effect of positive migration-related messages (Treatment 1) on the sample's attitude toward migration, are positive but low (0.004246 and 0.005349), suggesting a slight increase in positive attitudes due to the treatment. The p-value for the treatment's t-statistic shows that the treatment effects are not random occurrences, with a stronger significance in the second model (0.080562; 0.014698).

The t-statistic for the treatment of both models is significantly different from zero (1.752584 for Model 1; 2.45209 for Model 2), indicating that the Treatment may have had a significant impact in both cases. However, since the threshold for statistical significance for large samples is settled at 1.96, this implies that the treatment in Model 1 may have had marginal effects, while Model 2 undoubtedly shows stronger evidence of impact.

The standard errors for both treatments are quite small (0.002423 and 0.002181), indicating that the estimated effects of the treatments are relatively precise. This suggests the true effect of each treatment is likely close to the estimated effect of this study. However, the 95% confidence interval for the treatment effect includes zero in the first case, indicating the effect is not definitively significant. In simpler terms, the confidence interval means that the true effect of the treatment could be anywhere between a slight decrease (-0.00052) and a small increase (0.009012) in the first Model. Because this range includes zero, it is not assured that the treatment had any real effect. In the second model the confidence interval ranges from a very small increase (0.001058) and a slight increase (0.00964), qualifying as statistically significant.

In sum, in both models, the treatment has a positive but (very) marginal influence on the attitudes toward migration, with Model 2 demonstrating a more pronounced and statistically significant effect. In other words, the exposure to migration-related positive messages (Treatment 1) had a positive effect in both case, but was far more impactful on people’s sense of responsibility and duty to assist migrants than on their perception of migrants’ benefits to economic growth.

4.2.2 Regression Model 3 and 4: Control group versus Treatment 2

Independent variable: Treatment 2

0 = control group, 2 = treatment2

Dependent variables: Attitudes toward Migration (Y)

1. Level of agreement with the item “*Immigrants can contribute to Italy’s economic growth*” (Y3)
2. Level of agreement with the item “*Assisting migrants is a national duty*” (Y4)

See table T6 (regression model 3) and T7 (regression model 4) in appendix.

Statistic	Explanation	Model 3 (Y3)	Model 4 (Y4)
Multiple R	Correlation coefficient between the observed and predicted values of the dependent variable. (value close to 0 = very weak relationship)	0.053079	0.037381
R Square	The proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that is explained by the Treatment	0.002817	0.001397
Adjusted R Square	Adjusted R Square adjusts the R Square value based on the number of predictors in the model. (Adjusted R square lower than the R square = adding more variables might not necessarily improve the model fit.)	-0.00011	-0.00153
Standard Error	The standard deviation of the residuals (prediction errors).	6.661303	5.604842
Observations		343	343
df (Regression)	Degrees of freedom (N. of Independent Variables)	1	1
SS (Regression)	The sum of squares due to regression, indicating the variation explained by the model.	42.75152	14.98954
MS (Regression)	Mean square due to regression (SS divided by df).	42.75152	14.98954
F	It checks if at least one of the variables used to make predictions is helpful. (Higher values = more significant model)	0.963459	0.477157
Significance F	A value less than 0.05 typically indicates statistical significance.	0.327013	0.490183
df (Residual)	Degrees of freedom for residuals.	341	341

SS (Residual)	The sum of squares due to residuals.	15131.18	10712.26
MS (Residual)	Mean square due to residuals (SS divided by df)	44.37296	31.41426
Intercept Coefficient	The predicted value of the dependent variable when all independent variables are zero.	3.839656	3.697951
Intercept Standard Error	The standard error of the intercept estimate.	0.50792	0.427365
Intercept t Stat	The t-statistic for the intercept, testing whether the intercept is significantly different from zero. It checks if the base level of the model is meaningful.	7.559575	8.652905
Intercept P-value	The p-value for the intercept's t-statistic shows how likely it is that the intercept is just a random number. (Small number = significant, not random)	3.77E-13	2.01E-16
Intercept Lower 95%	The 95% confidence interval for the intercept	2.840606	2.857347
Intercept Upper 95%		4.838706	4.538555
Treatment Coefficient	The estimated effect of the Treatment on participants' Attitudes toward migration.	-0.35305	-0.20905
Treatment Standard Error	The standard error of the treatment coefficient.	0.359678	0.302634
Treatment t Stat	The t-statistic for the treatment, tests whether the treatment is significantly different from zero. It checks if the treatment has a real impact.	-0.98156	-0.69077
Treatment P-value	The p-value for the treatment's t-statistic shows how likely it is that the treatment's effect is just a random occurrence. (Small number = significant, not random)	0.327013	0.490183
Treatment Lower 95%	The 95% confidence interval for the treatment	-1.06051	-0.80431
Treatment Upper 95%		0.354422	0.386216

TABLE T8: REGRESSION MODEL 3 AND 4 (COMBINED SUMMARY TABLE)

Significance F values less than 0.05 typically indicate statistical significance. Accordingly, Model 3 (0.327013) and similarly, Model 4 (0.490183) likely represent very marginally significant models.

In both cases, the Intercepts T statistics (7.559575; 8.652905) confirm that the intercept is significantly different from zero, determining a quite meaningful base level, though slighter than the first two models. Similarly, both Intercept P-values being small numbers (3.77E-13; 2.01E-16), exclude the possibility of randomness in the intercept, acknowledging its significance.

The treatment coefficients, which indicate the estimated effect of the exposure to right-wing messengers disseminating positive migration-related messages (Treatment 2) on the sample's attitude toward migration, are negative in both models, presenting very low values (-0.35305; -0.20905). They might suggest a very slight, but not significant, decrease in positive attitudes due to the treatment. Similarly, the p-value for the treatment's t-statistic shows that the treatment effects are not statistically relevant (0.327013; 0.490183).

The t-statistic for the treatment of both models is negative and close to zero (-0.98156 for Model 3; -0.69077 for Model 4), indicating that the Treatment did not have any significant impact.

The standard errors for both treatments are quite high values (0.359678 and 0.302634), indicating that the estimated effects of the treatments are not so precise. Furthermore, the 95% confidence interval for the treatment effect includes zero in both cases, indicating the effect is not definitively significant. In simpler terms, the confidence interval means that the true effect of the treatment could be anywhere between a decrease (-1.06051) and a small increase (0.354422) in the third Model, and between a very slight decrease (-0.80431) and a small increase (0.386216) in the fourth. Because this range includes zero, it is not assured that the treatment had any real effect.

In sum, in both models, the treatment had a very weak and non-significant effect on the attitudes toward migration. The coefficients suggest a slight decrease in these beliefs due to the treatment, but the confidence intervals include zero, indicating that the observed effects could be due to chance. In essence, the exposure to right-wing messengers voicing migration-related positive messages (Treatment 2) had a very weak, negative, and likely not significant effect in both case.

4.2.3 Regression Model 5 and 6: Treatment 1 versus Treatment 2

Independent variable: Treatment 1 and Treatment 2

1 = Treatment 1, 2 = treatment 2

Dependent variables: Attitudes toward Migration (Y)

1. Level of agreement with the item "*Immigrants can contribute to Italy's economic growth*" (Y5)
2. Level of agreement with the item "*Assisting migrants is a national duty*" (Y6)

See table T9 (regression model 5) and T10 (regression model 6) in appendix.

Statistic	Explanation	Model 5 (Y5)	Model 6 (Y6)
Multiple R	Correlation coefficient between the observed and predicted values of the dependent variable. (value close to 0 = very weak relationship)	0.143926	0.156436
R Square	The proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that is explained by the Treatment	0.020715	0.024472
Adjusted R Square	Adjusted R Square adjusts the R Square value based on the number of predictors in the model. (Adjusted R square lower than the R square = adding more variables might not necessarily improve the model fit.)	0.017868	0.021636
Standard Error	The standard deviation of the residuals (prediction errors).	9.598839	11.46163
Observations		346	346
df (Regression)	Degrees of freedom (N. of Independent Variables)	2	2
SS (Regression)	The sum of squares due to regression, indicating the variation explained by the model.	670.4526	1133.668
MS (Regression)	Mean square due to regression (SS divided by df).	670.4526	1133.668
F	It checks if at least one of the variables used to make predictions is helpful. (Higher values = more significant model)	7.276636	8.629645
Significance F	A value less than 0.05 typically indicates statistical significance.	0.00733	0.00353
df (Residual)	Degrees of freedom for residuals.	344	344
SS (Residual)	The sum of squares due to residuals.	31695.38	45190.95
MS (Residual)	Mean square due to residuals (SS divided by df)	92.13772	131.369
Intercept Coefficient	The predicted value of the dependent variable when all independent variables are zero.	8.702025	10.52078
Intercept Standard Error	The standard error of the intercept estimate.	1.626291	1.941896
Intercept t Stat	The t-statistic for the intercept, testing whether the intercept is significantly different from zero. It checks if the base level of the model is meaningful.	5.350841	5.417785
Intercept P-value	The p-value for the intercept's t-statistic shows how likely it is that the intercept is just a random number. (Small number = significant, not random)	0.00000016	0.000000114
Intercept Lower 95%	The 95% confidence interval for the intercept	5.503299	6.70129
Intercept Upper 95%		11.90075	14.34026
Treatment Coefficient	The estimated effect of the Treatment on participants' Attitudes toward migration.	-2.78423	-3.62046

Treatment Standard Error	The standard error of the treatment coefficient.	1.032143	1.232445
Treatment t Stat	The t-statistic for the treatment, tests whether the treatment is significantly different from zero. It checks if the treatment has a real impact.	-2.69752	-2.93763
Treatment P-value	The p-value for the treatment's t-statistic shows how likely it is that the treatment's effect is just a random occurrence. (Small number = significant, not random)	0.00733	0.00353
Treatment Lower 95%	The 95% confidence interval for the treatment	-4.81433	-6.04454
Treatment Upper 95%		-0.75412	-1.19639

TABLE T11: REGRESSION MODEL 5 AND 6 (COMBINED SUMMARY TABLE)

Significance F values less than 0.05 typically indicate statistical significance. Accordingly, Model 5 (0.00733) and similarly, Model 6 (0.00353) represent statistically significant models.

In both cases, the Intercepts T statistics (5.35084; 5.417785) confirm that the intercept is significantly different from zero, determining a meaningful base level, though slighter than the other models. Additionally, both Intercept P-values are very small numbers, significantly lower than the other models (0.00000016; 0.000000114), excluding the possibility of randomness in the intercept, acknowledging its significance.

The treatment coefficients, which indicate the estimated effect of right-win messengers on the sample's attitude toward migration, are negative and statistically significant in both models (-2.78423; -3.62046). They show a considerable decrease in positive attitudes due to the treatment. Similarly, the p-value for the treatment's t-statistic shows that the treatment effects are statistically relevant (0.00733; 0.00353).

The t-statistic for the treatment of both models is negative but significantly different from zero (-2.69752 for Model 5; -2.93763 for Model 6), indicating that the Treatment did have a real impact.

The 95% confidence interval for the treatment effect does not includes zero in three cases, indicating the effect is significant. In other words, the confidence interval means that the true effect of the treatment could be anywhere in the range from -4.81433 and -0.75412 in the fifth model and from -6.04454 and -1.19639 in the sixth. Because these spectra do not include zero, it means that the treatment had real effects.

In essence, both models showed a substantial negative shift in attitudes due to the messengers' identity. In other words, the exposure to right-wing messengers had a negative effect in both

case, suggesting that it significantly reduces the respondents' level of agreement with the statements.

Overall, Model 6 stands out as the most impactful model. It explains the highest proportion of variance (2.45%) among all models and has a highly significant treatment effect (p-value of 0.0035). The high significance and larger negative coefficient in Model 5 and 6, compared to the others, suggest that the identity of the messengers presented in the survey strongly influence respondents to perceive the economic impacts of migrants and the responsibility to assist them, less favorably. See T12 General comparative table in appendix.

4.2.4 Interaction Analysis Between Treatment 2 and participants' political orientation

Following Model 5 and 6 peculiar results, suggesting that the identity of the messengers overall "negatively" influences respondents' attitudes to migration, it becomes relevant to understand whether the messenger effect varies between right- and left-leaning voters. In other words, Specifically, do the messages from Vannacci and Feltri equally influence individuals across the political spectrum, or is the observed overall effect actually a combination of differing impacts on different political groups? To gain a deeper understanding of this complex interplay, an interaction term between attitudes and political orientation was calculated. This interaction term was then incorporated into two additional multiple regression models, each focused on one of the statements, to further analyze how political orientation may moderate the messenger effect.

The results from the multiple linear regression model indicate that both the treatment (whatever intervention or condition the participants were exposed to) and their political orientation play significant roles in shaping their level of agreement with the statements being assessed. The fact that the model explains 70.52% of the variance suggests that these two factors combined have a strong influence on how participants respond. The high statistical significance ($p < 0.001$) means that the observed effects are very unlikely to be due to random chance; they're robust and reliable. More specifically, the interaction between treatment and political orientation implies that the impact of the treatment isn't uniform across all participants; it varies depending on their political views. For instance, right-wing messengers might resonate more with individuals who hold a certain political orientation, leading them to agree more strongly with the statements, while those with a different orientation might react less favorably or even negatively (see Tables T12 and T13: Multiple regression models).

Once it is established that different political groups are impacted differently by the treatment, a deeper exploration of the messenger effect becomes necessary. The next step is to determine

which political groups are more negatively influenced and which are less affected or even positively influenced by the messengers' identity. To this end, participants in both Treatment 1 and Treatment 2 were categorized into three political orientation groups: right-leaning respondents (0-3), the movable middle (4-6), and left-leaning voters (7-10). For each of these groups, the average effect of the treatments was calculated. These averages were then compared across the groups to identify any discrepancies in the variance of the treatment effects. This approach aimed to visualize how the impact of the treatments varied across different political orientations, providing a clearer picture of which groups were most susceptible to the negative or positive influence of the messengers and which were less affected.

POLITICAL ORIENTATION'S INTERVAL GROUPS	AVERAGE EFFECT OF TREATMENT 1 (agreement with statement 1)
0-3	2,64
4-6	3,46
7-10	4,35
POLITICAL ORIENTATION'S INTERVAL GROUPS	AVERAGE EFFECT OF TREATMENT 2 (agreement with statement 1)
0-3	2,82
4-6	3,45
7-10	4,08

TABLE T14: EFFECT OF TREATMENT 2 ON DIFFERENT POLITICAL ORIENTATION'S INTERVAL GROUPS (STATEMENT 1)

POLITICAL ORIENTATION'S INTERVAL GROUPS	AVERAGE EFFECT OF TREATMENT 1 (agreement with statement 2)
media 0-3	2,56
media 4-6	3,57
media 7-10	4,78
POLITICAL ORIENTATION'S INTERVAL GROUPS	AVERAGE EFFECT OF TREATMENT 2 (agreement with statement 2)
media 0-3	3

media 4-6	3,53
media 7-10	4,18

TABLE T15: EFFECT OF TREATMENT 2 ON DIFFERENT POLITICAL ORIENTATION'S INTERVAL GROUPS (STATEMENT 2)

Effect of Treatment 2:

Statement 1: Immigrants can contribute to Italy's economic growth

- **Political orientation 0-3 (Right-wing):** Mean average 2,91 (0,18 increase)
- **Political orientation 4-6 (Movable middle):** Mean average di 3,45 (basically no variance)
- **Political orientation 7-10 (Left-wing):** Mean average di 4,17 (0,27 decrease)

Statement 2: Assisting migrants is a national duty

- **Political orientation 0-3 (Right-wing):** Mean average di 3,16 (0,44 increase)
- **Political orientation 4-6 (Movable middle):** Mean average di 3,53 (0,04 decrease)
- **Political orientation 7-10 (Left-wing):** Mean average di 4,34 (0,60 decrease)

According to the data, Treatment 2 had a slight positive impact on right-leaning participants for both statements. This suggests that pro-immigration statements delivered by right-wing politicians reinforced or created more favorable sentiments toward migration among right-wingers. Within the movable middle, and slightly left- or right-leaning voters, the treatment showed no significant effects. This group seems to be less sensitive to pro-immigration statements made by right-wing politicians. Lastly, confronting the effects of the Treatments within the left group, data prove that the messengers' identity had slight a negative effect on both statements, suggesting a controversial reaction of disagreement towards statements by right-wing politicians, which could be perceived out-groups and non-reliable.

CHAPTER 5: INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSION OF THE RESEARCH FINDINGS

This chapter provides a detailed presentation and interpretation of the research findings, aiming to contextualize the results within the framework of the initial research questions. The objective is to not only elucidate the key outcomes but also to assess their broader significance and implications. In the first section (*4.3 Interpretation and Discussion of the Research Findings within the Context of the Research Questions*), the results are interpreted in light of the research questions, discussing their implications and relevance. The fourth (*4.4 Potential Implications, Recommendations, and Key Limitations*) explores the broader implications of the findings, offers recommendations based on the results, and identifies key limitations of the study.

At first glance, the results reveal contrasting and unexpected outcomes. The first two models present a marginal but positive impact of the positive migration-related messages presented, whereas Models 2 and 3 show no significant impact of Treatment 2 (the combination of the above-cited messages and well-known right-wing deliverers). Surprisingly, the fifth and sixth models suggest that individuals' attitudes toward migration are negatively correlated to the exposure to the above-presented messengers alone. It is interesting to consider and discuss each regression model separately before evaluating the hypotheses' validity.

5.1 Models 1 and 2

The first two models compare the responses of the Control group and Treatment Group 1. Specifically, they examine whether positive messages about migration, to which participants in Treatment Group 1 were exposed, (while the Control Group received no treatment), could influence the sample's attitudes toward immigration and migrants.

The treatments consisted of the following:

Article from 01-16-2016: *“Immigration in Italy is a controversial topic, but it is worth examining its economic impact. Migrants can act as a growth engine for economic development, filling labor shortages or stimulating innovation and productivity in key sectors.”*

Book published in 2023: *“Preserving our identity is fundamental; however, welcoming those seeking refuge represents an innate duty of our nation. Assisting people fleeing armed conflicts, persecution, or poverty cannot be reduced to a mere act of generosity but must be recognized as an essential ethical and moral obligation.”*

As above-mentioned, the data show a marginally significant impact of Treatment 1 in the first two models, suggesting that the specific positive migration-related messages had a very weak but positive influence over people's attitudes toward migration. Treatment 1 was notably more

impactful toward respondents' sense of national duty to assist migrants compared to their perception of migrant's contribution to economic growth.

In the first assessment of peoples' perception of the economic impact of immigration, the multiple R, representing the correlation coefficient between the observed and the expected value of the dependent variable is very close to 0 (0.09) indicating a very weak relationships. Approximately 0,88% of the variance in attitudes could be explained by the impact of the treatment. Nonetheless, the treatment coefficient is positive (0.0042), suggesting a slight increase in belief due to treatment. The second model, considering people's sense of duty in assisting migration, is slightly more significant with a Multiple R of 0.13, and 1.7% of people being influenced by the treatment.

Despite the marginal impact, these models, show a slight but positive influence of these specific messages about migration on people's attitudes. Though modest, these results align with recent literature on the topic. For instance, Facchini et al. (2016) and similarly Nakata (2017), exposed individuals to positive information about the potential social and economic benefits of migration, resulting in reduced opposition to immigration, increased support for temporary visas, and even increased willingness to petition politicians.

The small effect showed in the models might be partially explained, among other limitations discussed below, by the very limited exposure to the treatment. The sentences were concise (taking less than one minute to read), and participants were exposed to them only once. Many scholars demonstrated that treatments and messages are more effective when exposure to information is longer (Carnahan et al., 2021; Grigoriev et al, 2016).

5.2 Models 3 and 4

The third and fourth models compared the control group's results with Treatment 2's, investigating the hypothesized impact of positive messages and their specific messengers on people's attitudes toward migration.

Treatment 2 included the following statements and premises:

Vittorio Feltri, an Italian journalist, wrote in an article for "Liberio" on January 16, 2016:

"Immigration in Italy is a controversial topic, but it is worth examining its economic impact. Migrants can act as a growth engine for economic development, filling labor shortages or stimulating innovation and productivity in key sectors."

In his 2023 book "Il Mondo al Contrario," **Roberto Vannacci**, a writer and general in the Italian army, argues: *"Preserving our identity is fundamental; however, welcoming those seeking refuge represents an innate duty of our nation. Assisting people fleeing armed conflicts,*

persecution, or poverty cannot be reduced to a mere act of generosity but must be recognized as an essential ethical and moral obligation.”

In this scenario, the messengers voicing these messages are explicitly specified, unlike in Treatment 1. The distinctive feature of this questionnaire is the choice of messengers. The public figures presented typically align with right-wing and anti-immigration sentiments, contrasting with the positive messages they convey. This contrast aimed to determine, in particular, whether right-wing, typically anti-immigrant voters might be influenced by positive messages when delivered by figures they trust and identify with, or else left-leaning or centrist people might be negatively influenced by someone they perceive as out-group, lowering their level of agreement with the statements.

The data from both models illustrate no significant effect on attitudes toward migration-related beliefs. In fact, the coefficients (-0.35305; -0.20905) suggest a slight decrease in these attitudes due to the treatment. However, the confidence intervals include zero, indicating that the observed effects could be due to chance. In essence, the third and fourth models present non-significant results, revealing the ineffectiveness of Treatment 2 in positively influencing participants' attitudes toward migration. These outcomes seem to contrast with results from Models 1 and 2. The latter demonstrate a positive correlation between exposure to positive migration-related messages and participants' migration attitudes, while Models 3 and 4, though very weakly, show a negative correlation between the two variables when messengers are made explicit. This implies that these specific messengers may have a “negative” impact on people's perception of messages and, in turn, on their attitudes towards migrants and migration. This “negative” influence could be somehow mitigated by the positive impact of the messages presented, possibly explaining the results' relative “weakness” and “neutrality”. Evidently, these are just hints and hypotheses that should be further investigated with qualitative or a deeper quantitative analysis (see limitations and recommendations for future research).

5.3 Models 5 and 6

The fifth and sixth models were the core models investigating the research's primary hypothesis: *Does the identity of the messengers influence respondents' agreement levels with statements regarding immigration?*

To this end, these Models compared responses to Treatment 1 (anonymous positive messages toward migration) with those to Treatment 2 (positive messages delivered by right-wing messengers). The focus was on whether the explicit identity of well-known messengers has a significant impact on migration attitudes. Specifically, the analysis sought to determine whether the same (positive) message yields different effects depending on whether it is delivered by

figures whom participants identify with and regard as authoritative and credible, or by figures whom participants dislike or disagree with, such as those affiliated with an opposing political party.

Models 5 and 6 stand out as the most impactful model. They account for the highest proportion of variance (close to 3 %) among all models and exhibit a highly significant treatment effect (p-values of 0.0073; 0.0035). These results indicate that the second treatment significantly decreases positive attitudes toward immigration-related responses.

In Model 5, the treatment coefficient is -2.78423 with a p-value of 0.0073. The negative coefficient implies that the presence of these specific right-wing messengers significantly reduces the belief that immigrants can contribute to Italy's economic growth.

Similarly, Model 6 shows a treatment coefficient of -3.62046 with a highly significant p-value of 0.0035. This finding demonstrates, once again, that the explicit identity of the messengers presented above, significantly diminishes the belief that assisting migrants is a national duty. The negative impact is even more pronounced in Model 6 compared to Model 5.

In other words, messengers who typically align with right-wing and anti-immigration sentiments (like the ones selected for the study), are particularly effective in reducing supportive attitudes towards both the economic contributions of immigrants and the perceived duty to assist them.

Consequently, it can be inferred that positive messages, even if delivered by right-wing messengers, do not overall foster more favorable attitudes toward migration among the whole population. In fact, the models demonstrate that these messengers' identities did have a significant impact on attitudes, albeit negatively. Consistently with results from Models 2 and 3 (that show no effect of Treatment 2 despite the positive impact of migration-related messages demonstrated by Models 1 and 2), this suggests that right-wing messengers may have influenced a segment of the left-leaning population. Indeed, individuals, upon recognizing the specific messenger, may experience an immediate, automatic reaction based on their pre-existing perceptions of the messenger. If the messenger represents something they dislike or disagree with, their initial reaction may be skepticism or distrust. As they process the message, pro-immigrant or uncertain individuals may face a conflict between the positive content of the message and their negative perception of the messenger. This can create *cognitive dissonance*, a psychological discomfort resulting from holding two contradictory beliefs simultaneously (see previous chapter) (Metzger, 2008; Martin, & Marks, 2019; John, *et al.* 2019). To overcome the dissonance, individuals may engage in *motivated reasoning* or *self-validation*, a process where they selectively interpret information in a way that aligns with their pre-existing viewpoints and attitudes. In this scenario, they may downplay or dismiss the positive aspects of

the message because it conflicts with their negative view of the messenger, which might prevail. (Menon, & Blount, 2003; Clark, 2013). Furthermore, in order to protect their consistent belief system, individuals might resort to *psychological defense mechanisms*. For example, they may question the messenger's intentions, assuming that the specific anti-immigrant messenger has a hidden agenda or dual purposes for delivering positive messages about immigration, thereby discrediting the message itself. Again, people may focus on the messenger's past negative actions or statements, which can overshadow the current positive message. (Menon, & Blount, 2003). In addition, the *social identity theory* posits that people derive part of their identity from the social groups to which they belong. Accordingly, if the messenger's identity is closely associated with a group that the audience identifies with negatively (e.g., right-wing groups promoting anti-immigrant rhetoric), the message is likely to be perceived with skepticism or outright rejection, regardless of its content. (Leeflang, 2016; Aromando, 2021; McVeigh, *et al.* 2023).

Due to all the combined effects mentioned above, pro-immigrant, left-leaning individuals (categorized within the movable middle) may end up paying less attention to the actual content of the message. Or else, they might even reject the message outright because it is voiced by someone they despise or from which they diverge. As a result, the positive messages about immigration are not effective on left voters or even counterproductive when delivered by right-wing messengers. This can lead to a decrease in positive attitudes toward immigration among the pro-immigrant.

As previously mentioned, this hypothesis is further supported by prior models' results, which show that positive messages alone produce slightly positive effects on people's migration attitudes (in Models 1 and 2), while the same positive messages combined with right-wing messengers nullify and almost reverse the findings, with positive attitudes toward migration weakly decreasing (Models 3 and 4).

Furthermore, as shown by the graphs in the previous chapter, approximately 40% of the total sample follows Italian politics attentively enough to recognize and associate these messengers (Feltri and Vannacci) with specific likable or unlikable frames, making them easily influenced by these figures. Similarly, the distribution of migration attitudes by age and education levels shows a decrease in positive attitudes specifically in treatment 2 (positive messages delivered by explicit messengers), particularly among the younger group and graduated individuals. As explained in the previous paragraph, this demographic group is more likely to vote left, and thus most likely to be "negatively influenced" by right-wing and typically anti-immigrant messengers.

The interaction analysis between the messenger effect (Treatment 2 impact) and participants' political orientation, further completes this picture. It reveals that while right-wing messengers had a slight positive influence on respondents identifying as right-wing—leading to a modest increase in positive reactions to both statements—this effect was counterbalanced by a more substantial negative impact on left-leaning voters. Data showed a more pronounced decrease in agreement with positive statements on migration among left-leaning individuals, while attitudes among those in the center remained largely unchanged. This dynamic explains the overall negative effect observed in Models 5 and 6, where the minor positive impact on right-wing participants was outweighed by the stronger negative response from left-leaning respondents.

If this hypothesis holds, it implies that the messenger can significantly influence how messages are received, potentially overriding the content of the message. This highlights the importance of considering not just the content of the communication, but also who is the target audience and accordingly, who is delivering the message when attempting to shift public opinion on contentious issues like immigration.

Now, to gain a clearer understanding of the results, it is interesting to revisit them within the context of the research questions:

H: The identity of the messenger influences the agreement levels of respondents on statements regarding immigration.

Sub-H1: Respondents will exhibit higher levels of agreement with statements on immigration if the messenger is affiliated with their own political party.

Sub-H2: Simultaneously, participants will show lower levels of agreement with messages that are perceived as coming from an out-group member.

Starting from the first sub-hypothesis, data clearly illustrate a slight increase in the level of agreement with statements when the messenger's identity was revealed, compared to responses of Treatment 1 where the messages were anonymous. The interaction models and the subsequent analysis of the political group of interval's average, indicated a slight increase, suggesting that anti-immigrant individuals may slightly reconsider their attitudes when exposed to positive messages delivered by in-group members. Even though the significance of the Models is weak and the sample is very limited, the sub-hypothesis 1 seems to be confirmed. Anyhow a more valid affirmation would require a wider and deeper study.

Regarding sub-H2, the data support the idea that participants may have shown lower levels of agreement with messages perceived as coming from out-group members. The sample included

20% of centrists individuals and over 50% of left-leaning participants. This combined 70% is likely to view the messengers (Vanacci and Feltri) as out-group figures. This perception could have potentially triggered negative associations with migrants and migration, leading participants to pay less attention to or even reject the statements, regardless of their content.

In summary, it can be declared that the hypothesis is confirmed. Right-wing respondents did show a small increase in positive attitudes toward migrants due to the exposure to right-wing messengers, whilst left-leaning participants may have disagreed with and discounted the statements because they perceived the messengers as non-credible, out-group members. Hence, this aligns with the hypothesis suggesting that the messenger's identity can have a stronger influence than the message content itself, often overshadowing it. This research, though revealing modest results, sets the stage for further and more in-depth studies testing the messenger effect on the effectiveness of communication strategies. It underscores the idea that the success of communication campaigns depends not only on the message content but also significantly on the identity of the messenger, especially when it contrasts sharply with the audience's social or political affiliations.

5.4 Potential Implications, Recommendations, and Key Limitations

5.2.1 Consistency with prior studies and new insights

As thoroughly explained in the previous chapters, within the limited realm of “messenger research” in migration-related contexts, scholars have primarily focused on the content of messages, the target audience, and their relationships; the impact of religious in-group biases on attitudes towards pro-immigration messages that challenge group norms; or shifts in public perceptions based on the degree of migrants’ integration. None of these studies has specifically tested hypotheses regarding the differential impact of various messengers on the same target population. Additionally, no study found significant evidence on the messengers’ impact or influence on people’s migration attitudes (Dennison, J., 2020; Donnelly et al., 2020; Dennison, J., 2022). In this context, the present research offers some new insights into how right-wing messengers specifically influence attitudes toward immigration, though the effects are slight and not fully confirmed.

The “negative” impact of positive messages delivered by these specific messengers suggests that the messenger’s political affiliation and the audience’s perception are critical factors in message reception. These intuitions are consistent with a broader body of literature, focusing on the messenger’s influence within different contexts (excluding migration-related contexts). Several studies argue that the credibility and perceived intentions of the messenger play an important role in message acceptance. For instance, research demonstrates how individuals are more inclined to reject information from sources they distrust or view as opposing their beliefs

and vice versa. This study's findings align with several well-established theories that explain attitude change, including Cognitive Dissonance, Motivated Reasoning, and Social Identity Theory. According to Cognitive Dissonance Theory, individuals experience discomfort when exposed to information that contradicts their pre-existing beliefs. To alleviate this unease, they attempt to reconcile or rationalize the new information to maintain internal consistency. Motivated Reasoning Theory posits that people process information in a biased manner, favoring evidence that supports their existing attitudes and disregarding contradictory information. Social Identity Theory explains that individuals derive a significant part of their identity from their social groups. As a result, they are likely to accept messages from in-group members and reject ideas voiced by perceived out-group, in order to protect their group identity and cohesion. Together, these theories offer a comprehensive framework for understanding the seemingly contradictory results of this study: positive messages from right-wing messengers brought right-leaning people closer to positive sentiments toward migrants, whilst leading to a decreased agreement among left-leaning participants (Menon, & Blount, 2003; Mettelle, 2008; Clark, 2013; Leeflang, 2016; Martin, & Marks, 2019; John, *et al.* 2019; Aromando, 2021; McVeigh, *et al.* 2023).

5.2.2 Practical Implications for Policymaking and Advocacy

These new insights extend to practical applications for policymakers and advocacy groups. The hypothesis that the messenger might have a relevant effect on the reception of messages opens new territories for strategic communication campaigns aiming to spread positive migration messages. Selecting messengers who are perceived as credible and who share the values of the target audience becomes a priority. As many scholars and advocacy practitioners emphasize, the messenger is often as important as the message. Put simply, if the source of the message is trusted by the target audience and has legitimacy in the community, it will be a lot easier to get the message across. Conversely, as partially demonstrated by this study, the opposite is also true: if the source is untrusted, the message may be dismissed or ignored. Within the current context of strategic communication directed at the migration debate, the extreme right-leaning and anti-immigrant population is often the target group most advocacy campaigns aspire to "change". However, as shown by the study's results, the attempt to engage anti-immigrant individuals by using right-wing or anti-immigrant sources can easily be overall counterproductive, especially if the broader audience is mainly composed of left-leaning people. Some studies, researching how to better engage the public in the migration debate, are interestingly focusing on the so-called movable middle. As explained in the previous chapters,

in most countries there's a significant group of people in the middle who are neither strongly pro nor anti but are concerned and confused about many issues around migration. If the aim is to change the debate, it could be interesting to focus on engaging this group, starting with the selection of the messenger.

In campaign plans, it is crucial to look for messengers that are trusted by the most conservative target segment(s) of the middle, and for these segments, these can often include people like community leaders, journalists from trusted newspapers, people wearing a uniform (police, firemen, etc), faith leaders, and teachers (Kahneman, D., 2011; International Centre for Policy Advocacy, 2018).

In summary, this study highlights the importance of selecting credible messengers who resonate with the majority of the target audience's values and identities, which is essential for the success of strategic communication campaigns on migration. It further demonstrates how selecting a right-wing messenger to influence the anti-immigrant population can be generally ineffective and even counterproductive. The main takeaway may be to shift the focus of communication campaigns from targeting right-wing and anti-immigrant individuals (who have strong, entrenched attitudes and are only slightly influenced) to addressing the 'movable middle,' prioritizing the use of credible and trustworthy messengers for this audience.

5.2.3 Limitations of the Study

This study has several limitations that need to be addressed, especially in future research. Firstly, the focus exclusively on the economic contributions and the national duty to assist migrants may limit the generalizability of the findings to broader immigration attitudes. Furthermore, although a pilot test was conducted, the statements and treatments are somewhat vague, which might have led to misunderstandings and misinterpretations. Additionally, the attitudes were measured with only a few items, restricting the validity of the results.

Secondly, the small sample size impacts the statistical power and generalizability of the findings. A larger, more diverse sample would enhance the robustness of the conclusions.

Thirdly, the study did not include qualitative research, which could provide valuable contextual understanding and help explain the mechanisms underlying the observed effects.

Fourthly, the experimental design involved brief and rapid exposure to the messages, which does not accurately reflect the dynamics of real-world exposure, where repeated exposure typically occurs over a more extended period.

Finally, the study's low validity is further limited because actual messengers did not deliver the messages in person or through media, excluding the influence of non-verbal cues and the authenticity of the messenger.

5.2.4 Recommendations for Future Research

Future research and advocacy campaigns, especially when targeting the movable middle, should consider different independent variables or treatments. One avenue for further investigation is to expand the scope of migration attitudes examined, including cultural impact, security concerns, and humanitarian perspectives, to provide a more holistic understanding of public opinion on immigration. It could be interesting to preliminarily inquire about people's anxieties and concerns before selecting the message content to target more salient and relevant aspects for the target population and observe their reactions.

Future studies should also consider longitudinal designs to examine the impact of prolonged and repeated exposure to messages over time, reflecting real-world conditions more accurately. A larger and more demographically diverse sample would contribute to the study's validity, generalizability, and significance. Additionally, research involving real messengers, utilizing various media platforms, and accounting for non-verbal communication cues would provide a more realistic assessment of the messenger effect.

Given the negative results of the study, it would also be very interesting to directly investigate the factors contributing to the decrease in negative attitudes toward migration. Additionally, building on the existing directions, it would be valuable to further explore the 'movable middle' and identify which messengers are most likely to influence them.

Lastly, for comprehensive research and to understand the dynamics behind the decreasing effects of the identity of the messenger, it could be very useful to interview a smaller group of the sample, conducting a more qualitative analysis. This approach could yield more accurate results and clarify the hypothesis stated above, according to which anti-immigrant people are modestly positively influenced by familiar and anti-immigrant messengers, while other segments may be negatively influenced. Since the statements were very vague, it could also be interesting to investigate people's perception, understanding, and interpretation of the messages to better grasp their reactions.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

In conclusion, this research highlights the crucial role that messenger identity plays in shaping public attitudes toward migration within a politically polarized environment. The findings reveal a nuanced dynamic between political orientation and the effectiveness of communication strategies. Consistently with initial expectations, right-wing respondents demonstrated increased agreement with pro-migration statements when familiar, in-group messengers delivered these (though weakly). On the other side of the spectrum, left-leaning respondents showed a significant decrease in agreement when exposed to the same messages attributed to right-wing figures perceived as out-group members. This reaction likely reflects cognitive biases, where the messenger's identity outweighs the content of the message, leading to its rejection regardless of substance.

These results underscore the importance of strategic messenger selection in communication campaigns, especially on contentious issues like migration. The study suggests that successful campaigns must go beyond creating the message itself and consider the credibility, relatability, and perceived alignment of the messenger with the target audience's political and social identities. For political actors and NGOs, these insights stress the need for a more sophisticated approach to strategic communication, one that anticipates and addresses the potential biases and preconceptions of the audience. Ultimately, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of how political affiliations and messenger identity interact to shape public opinion, laying a modest but interesting groundwork for future, more robust efforts to understand and influence attitudes on migration.

ANNEXES

Groups' demographic distribution for statistical weighing:

A. Age:

ITALIAN POPULATION	
18-24	7.01%
25-34	10.32%
35-44	11.85%
45-54	15.12%
55-64	15.11%
Over 65	27.00%

B. Gender

ITALIAN POPULATION	
Men	48,91%
Women	51,09%

C. Education level

ITALIAN POPULATION	
No qualification	8.3%
Elementary license	16.4%
Middle school license	32.8%
High school diploma	31.8%
Bachelor's degree	6.4%
Master's degree	3.1%
PHD	1.2%

D. Occupation

ITALIAN POPULATION	
Student-worker:	4.1%
Self-employed:	14.7%
Employee:	49.6%
Retired:	14.3%
Unemployed:	4.8%
Student:	12.5%

E. Geographic origin

GEOGRAPHIC ORIGIN

ITALIAN POPULATION

North	45.9%
Center	19.7%
South	34.4%

F. Economic status

CONTROL GROUP - economic status

TREATMENT 1 - economic status

TREATMENT 2 - economic status

ITALIAN POPULATION

Insufficient	15.4%
Precarious	25.7%
More than sufficient	40.6%
Wealthy	12.3%
Well-off	6.0%

Tables:

TABLE T1: PARTICIPANTS PERCEPTION OF IMMIGRATION'S CONTRIBUTION TO THE ITALIAN ECONOMY (CONTROL GROUP)

Participants perception of immigration's contribution to the italian economy	Count	Percentage
1 Very negative	12	6.9
2 Negative	37	21.5
3 Neutral	54	31.3
4 Positive	57	33.1
5 Very positive	12	6.9

TABLE T2: PARTICIPANTS' PERCEIVED IMPORTANCE OF THE MIGRATION ISSUE

Perceived importance of the Migration issue	Counts	Percentage
1 I do not consider the issue of migration important at all	0	0%
2 I consider the issue of migration to be of little importance	10	5.8%
3 I consider the issue of migration to be moderately important	24	14%
4 I consider the issue of migration to be quite important	57	33.3%
5 I consider the issue of migration to be very important	80	46.8%

TABLE T3: REGRESSION MODEL 1 (Y1 IMMIGRANTS CAN CONTRIBUTE TO ITALY'S ECONOMIC GROWTH)

OUTPUT

Regression statistics	
Multiple R	0.093939
R Square	0.008824
Adjusted R Square	0.005952
Standard error	0.499211
Observation	347

ANOVA

	<i>gdl</i>	<i>SQ</i>	<i>MQ</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	0.765467	0.765467	3.071551	0.080562
Residual	345	85.97805	0.249212		

Total 346 86.74352

	<i>Standard</i>		<i>Significance</i>			
	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>error</i>	<i>T stat</i>	<i>value</i>	<i>Inf. 95%</i>	<i>Sup. 95%</i>
Intercept	0.483568	0.029299	16.50457	1.62E-45	0.425941	0.541195
“Immigrants can contribute to Italy’s economic growth”	0.004246	0.002423	1.752584	0.080562	-0.00052	0.009012

TABLE T4: REGRESSION MODEL 2 (Y2 ASSISTING MIGRANTS IS A NATIONAL DUTY)

OUTPUT

<i>Regression statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.130881
R square	0.01713
Adjusted R square	0.014281
Standard Error	0.497115
Observations	347

ANOVA

	<i>ddl</i>	<i>SQ</i>	<i>MQ</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	1.485892	1.485892	6.012748	0.014698
Residual	345	85.25762	0.247124		
Total	346	86.74352			

	<i>Standard</i>		<i>Significance</i>			
	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>error</i>	<i>T stat</i>	<i>value</i>	<i>Inf. 95%</i>	<i>Sup. 95%</i>
Intercept	0.475903	0.029095	16.35707	6.34E-45	0.418678	0.533128
“Assisting migrants is a national duty”	0.005349	0.002181	2.452091	0.014698	0.001058	0.00964

TABLE T6: REGRESSION MODEL 3 (Y3 IMMIGRANTS CAN CONTRIBUTE TO ITALY’S ECONOMIC GROWTH)

OUTPUT

<i>Regression statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.053079
R square	0.002817
Adjusted R square	-0.00011

Standard Error 6.661303
 Observations 343

ANOVA

	<i>gdl</i>	<i>SQ</i>	<i>MQ</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	42.75152	42.75152	0.963459	0.327013
Residual	341	15131.18	44.37296		
Total	342	15173.93			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard error</i>	<i>T stat</i>	<i>Significance value</i>	<i>Inf. 95%</i>	<i>Sup. 95%</i>
Intercept	3.839656	0.50792	7.559575	3.77E-13	2.840606	4.838706
<i>“Immigrants can contribute to the Italian economic growth”</i>	-0.35305	0.359678	-0.98156	0.327013	-1.06051	0.354422

TABLE T7: REGRESSION MODEL 4 (Y4 ASSISTING MIGRANTS IS A NATIONAL DUTY)

OUTPUT

Regression statistics

Multiple R	0.037381
R square	0.001397
Adjusted R square	-0.00153
Standard Error	5.604842
Observations	343

ANOVA

	<i>gdl</i>	<i>SQ</i>	<i>MQ</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	14.98954	14.98954	0.477157	0.490183
Residual	341	10712.26	31.41426		
Total	342	10727.25			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard error</i>	<i>T-stat</i>	<i>Significance value</i>	<i>Inf. 95%</i>	<i>Sup. 95%</i>
Intercept	3.697951	0.427365	8.652905	2.01E-16	2.857347	4.538555
<i>“Assisting migrants is a national duty”</i>	-0.20905	0.302634	-0.69077	0.490183	-0.80431	0.386216

TABLE T9: REGRESSION MODEL 5 (Y4 IMMIGRANTS CAN CONTRIBUTE TO ITALY'S ECONOMIC GROWTH)

OUTPUT

<i>Regression statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.143926
R square	0.020715
Adjusted R square	0.017868
Standard Error	9.598839
Observations	346

ANOVA

	<i>gdl</i>	<i>SQ</i>	<i>MQ</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	670.4526	670.4526	7.276636	0.00733
Residual	344	31695.38	92.13772		
Total	345	32365.83			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard error</i>	<i>T-stat</i>	<i>Significance value</i>	<i>Inf. 95%</i>	<i>Sup. 95%</i>
Intercept	8.702025	1.626291	5.350841	1.6E-07	5.503299	11.90075
<i>“Immigrants can contribute to the Italian economic growth”</i>	-2.78423	1.032143	-2.69752	0.00733	-4.81433	-0.75412

TABLE T10: REGRESSION MODEL 6 (Y6 ASSISTING MIGRANTS IS A NATIONAL DUTY)

OUTPUT

<i>Regression statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.156436
R square	0.024472
Adjusted R square	0.021636
Standard Error	11.46163
Observations	346

ANOVA

	<i>gdl</i>	<i>SQ</i>	<i>MQ</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significatività F</i>
Regression	1	1133.668	1133.668	8.629645	0.00353
Residual	344	45190.95	131.369		

Total 345 46324.62

	<i>Coefficienti</i>	<i>Errore standard</i>	<i>Stat t</i>	<i>Valore di significatività</i>	<i>di Inferiore 95%</i>	<i>Superiore 95%</i>
Intercept	10.52078	1.941896	5.417785	1.14E-07	6.70129	14.34026
“Assisting migrants is a national duty”	-3.62046	1.232445	-2.93763	0.00353	-6.04454	-1.19639

TABLE T12: GENERAL COMPARATIVE TABLE

Statistic	Model 1 (Y1)	Model 2 (Y2)	Model 3 (Y3)	Model 4 (Y4)	Model 5 (Y5)	Model6 (Y6)
Multiple R	0.093939	0.130881	0.053079	0.037381	0.143926	0.156436
R Square	0.008824	0.01713	0.002817	0.001397	0.020715	0.024472
Adjusted R Square	0.005952	0.014281	-0.00011	-0.00153	0.017868	0.021636
Standard Error	0.499211	0.497115	1.00151	5.604842	9.598839	11.46163
Observations	347	347	343	343	346	346
df (Regression)	1	1	1	1	2	2
SS (Regression)	0.765467	1.485892	0.966371	14.98954	670.4526	1133.668
MS (Regression)	0.765467	1.485892	0.966371	14.98954	670.4526	1133.668
F	3.071551	6.012748	0.963459	0.477157	7.276636	8.629645
Significance F	0.080562	0.014698	0.327013	0.490183	0.00733	0.00353
df (Residual)	345	345	341	341	344	344
SS (Residual)	85.97805	85.25762	342.030714	10712.26	31695.38	45190.95
MS (Residual)	0.249212	0.247124	1.003023	31.41426	92.13772	131.369
Intercept Coefficient	0.483568	0.475903	1.024917	3.697951	8.702025	10.52078
Intercept Standard Error	0.029299	0.029095	0.06106	0.427365	1.626291	1.941896
Intercept t Stat	16.504574	16.35707	16.785462	8.652905	5.350841	5.417785
Intercept P-value	1.62E-45	6.34E-45	1.62E-46	2.01E-16	0.00000016	0.000000114
Intercept Lower 95%	0.425941	0.418678	0.904816	2.857347	5.503299	6.70129
Intercept Upper 95%	0.541195	0.533128	1.145019	4.538555	11.90075	14.34026
Treatment Coefficient	0.004246	0.005349	-0.00798	-0.20905	-2.78423	-3.62046
Treatment Standard Error	0.002423	0.002181	0.00813	0.302634	1.032143	1.232445
Treatment t Stat	1.752584	2.452091	-0.981559	-0.69077	-2.69752	-2.93763
Treatment P-value	0.080562	0.014698	0.327013	0.490183	0.00733	0.00353
Treatment Lower 95%	-0.00052	0.001058	-0.023972	-0.80431	-4.81433	-6.04454

Treatment	Upper						
95%		0.009012	0.00964	0.008011	0.386216	-0.75412	-1.19639

TABLE T13: MULTIPLE REGRESSION MODEL - INPUT Y: EFFECT OF TREATMENT 2 (STATEMENT 1: IMMIGRANTS CONTRIBUTE TO ITALY'S ECONOMIC GROWTH) INPUT X: POLITICAL IDENTIFICATION AND INTERACTION TERM)

OUTPUT

Regression statistics	
Multiple R	0,839733
R square	0,705152
Adjusted R square	0,701642
Standard Error	2,041476
Observations	171

ANOVA

	<i>gdl</i>	<i>SQ</i>	<i>MQ</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	2	1674,487	837,2434	200,8923	2,79E-45
Residual	168	700,1606	4,167623		
Total	170	2374,647			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard error</i>	<i>T stat</i>	<i>Significance value</i>	<i>Inf 95%</i>	<i>Sup 95%</i>
Intercetta	4,472029	0,370537	12,06904	1,5E-24	3,74052	5,203538
Variabile X 1	-0,72535	0,064417	-11,2602	2,85E-22	-0,85252	-
Variabile X 2	0,18611	0,010265	18,12998	2,14E-41	0,165844	0,206376

TABLE T13: MULTIPLE REGRESSION MODEL - INPUT Y: EFFECT OF TREATMENT 2 (STATEMENT 2: ASSISTING MIGRANTS IS A NATIONAL DUTY) INPUT X: POLITICAL IDENTIFICATION AND INTERACTION TERM)

Regression statistics

Multiple R	0,848716
R square	0,720319
Adjusted R square	0,716989
Standard Error	2,011652

ANOVA

<i>gdl</i>	<i>SQ</i>	<i>MQ</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
2	1750,96	875,4799	216,3417	3,31E-47
168	679,8532	4,046745		
170	2430,813			

<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard error</i>	<i>T stat</i>	<i>Significance value</i>	<i>Inf 95%</i>	<i>Sup 95%</i>
4,55407	0,364932	12,47923	1,04E-25	3,833627	5,274513
-0,75138	0,063719	-11,792	9,08E-24	-0,87717	-0,62558
0,18979	0,010011	18,95786	1,37E-43	0,170026	0,209554

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